

THE RIGHT TO FREEDOM
FROM ARBITRATION
DETENTION: ARTICLE 9 OF
THE UNIVERSAL
DECLARATION ON HUMAN
RIGHTS (UDHR)

SAMUEL ULRIC BETTS ESQ.

This work was submitted to the University of Sierra Leone, Fourah Bay College, Faculty of Social Sciences and Law, Department of Law in fulfilment of one of the requirements for the conferment of the degree of Bachelor of Laws with Honours upon completion of a four-year degree programme at the end of the academic year 2019/20. It is hereby being republished by the author for educational purposes and general contribution to the development and research on international Human Rights Law.

ABOUT THE AUTHOR

At the date of republication, the author, [Samuel Ulric Betts Esq.](#), is a qualified and seasoned Barrister and Solicitor of the High Court of Sierra Leone whose practice areas involve commercial, corporate, civil and international human rights law.

He holds a Bachelor of Laws Degree (LL. B Hons) from Fourah Bay College, University of Sierra Leone and a Utter Barrister (BL) degree from the Sierra Leone Law School. He is a member of the Sierra Leone Bar Association.

CHAPTER ONE

OVERVIEW/BACKGROUND OF STUDY

1.1 INTRODUCTION: ARTICLE (9) OF THE UNIVERSAL DECLARATION OF HUMAN RIGHTS

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights is the universal standard for the protection and promotion of human rights the world over. It lays the foundation of human rights and serves as a precursor to many human rights documents today. It sets as its objective the promotion of equality for all human beings, and maintains a continued relevance in amendments and promulgations around the world. Its thirty (30) fundamental rights ensure that every human right is protected and respected equally. Amongst these fundamental human rights, our inquiry centres on its **Article 9**, which provides that:

“No one shall be subjected to arbitrary arrest, detention or exile.”

The right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention, i.e. **Article 9**, protects every individual from being unjustly and arbitrarily detained. It goes further to also ensure procedures and mechanisms in place are duly adhered to in the execution of every arrest, and during periods of detention. This has catered for a bit of sanity in the law enforcement institutions, and law-making bodies. Some of these procedures require the arresting officer to act professionally and according to laid-down best practices during every arrest by having a warrant of arrest, informing the victim the reason for arrest, and ensuring detention does not span over the stipulated duration as permitted by law.

Our research embarks on the journey to answer critical questions, posed to uncover the reason for, the dispute about, and solution for arbitrary detention in our society. It relies on factual evidence, testimony, interviews and conclusive researches into the area and goes further to analyse these data in alignment with objective of the study. By extension, it finds out efficient ways of dealing with the issue of arbitrary detention in our society.

The right of freedom from arbitrary detention and arrest remains relevant to an extent that its deprivation more often than not results in unfavourable situations and comes with immense cost. And as with every right, it affords equal measures of duty and obligations, and extends to every individual within the state they reside.

“The right to personal liberty is fundamental and extends to all persons at all times and circumstances, ... irrespective of their citizenship, nationality or migratory status.”¹ (UNWG, February 2018)

The significance of the right of freedom from arbitrary detention goes as far back as in 1215, the period when the Magna Carta, “The Great Charter”, was issued, which greatly influenced the development of the Common Law and required kings to renounce certain rights, respect certain legal procedures and accept that the laws bound him. It unequivocally protected certain rights of the King's subjects, whether free or fettered—most notably the writ of habeas corpus, allowing appeal against unlawful imprisonment. It provided:

“No Freeman shall be taken or imprisoned, or be disseised of his Freehold, or Liberties, or free Customs, or be outlawed, or exiled, or any other wise destroyed; nor will We not pass upon him, nor condemn him, but by lawful judgment of his Peers, or by the Law of the Land. We will sell to no man, we will not deny or defer to any man either Justice or Right.”²

This clearly shows that human rights practices, especially the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention, started with its early primitive forms, which had existed, even though they did not have the same modern-day conception of universal human rights as we do now (Freeman, 2002).³

Our research then looks into the guiles under which arbitrary detention may occur. Guided by the research questions posed in Chapter two (2), and data findings collected in Chapter four (4), it explores in-depth into the relevance, impact, implementation, and challenges that pertains arbitrary arrest and detention. It compares our present-day society in Sierra Leone, and its adhering mechanism to international standards as set in **Article 9** of the UDHR.

Even though the UDHR is not binding in international law, its obligatory or customary effect has compelled state leaders to act in accordance with its rights and thread cautiously in fear of being penalised, or dubbed “a human right-abusing country’. Its far-

¹ UN Working Group on Arbitrary Detention, February 2018

² Clause XXIX of the Magna Carta

³ Michael Freeman (2002), Human Rights: An Interdisciplinary Approach.

reaching effect is seen in other international convention, protocols and statutes, amongst which is Article 9 of the International Convention on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) which similarly protects individual from arbitrary arrest and detention and grants rights to liberty and security of persons. In this study, other such documents protecting the freedom of the individual from abuse are given due consideration as well.

Although Sierra Leone is our sample state, the research encompasses a broader sphere of international and national human rights laws, which reflects the right of freedom from arbitrary detention in other jurisdictions and legal systems. This is so because the peculiarity of every domestic legal system differs considerably, even though having some similarities. And most times it will be for each domestic judge, prosecutor, and lawyer to himself well informed as to the manner of incorporation of the state's international legal obligations into national law (Henry, 2000).⁴

The right to personal liberty under the UDHR is, however, not unlimited, i.e. detention must be in accordance with national and international law. It makes clear that authorities should only detain persons following clear, public procedures and these procedures must not in any way be influenced politically by the government of the day.

With Article 9, part of the large section of the UDHR (Articles 6-11) devoted to standards for the administration of justice, the Universal Declaration makes clear that a person's freedom does not automatically evaporates on arrest or conviction. The individual still possess rights in court or behind bars — and the rights to hold arresting or imprisoning authorities to specific standards.⁵

On this note, this study is hereby commissioned on the footing of assessing in particular **Article 9** of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights — its relevance, impact, implementation, and challenges, whilst staying congruent with international standards already set in the self-same document and other international statutes, treaties, and conventions on protecting against arbitrary arrest and detention.

1.2 ORIGIN AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE UDHR – “*From fawn scrolls to white sheets of paper*”

⁴ Henry J. Steiner and Philip Alston, *International Human Rights in Context. Law, Politics, and Morals*, 2nd ed. (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2000)

⁵ Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights Speech in celebration 70th Anniversary of the UDHR on Article 9 of the UDHR

“Our abiding commitment to the rule of law is the very bedrock of our civilization. It is what makes all else possible, from the flowering of the arts to the steady advance of the sciences. The idea that men must govern themselves not by the arbitrary commands of a ruler but by their own considered judgment, is the means whereby chaos is replaced by order.” – Margaret Thatcher

On December 10, 1948, the General Assembly of the United Nations adopted and proclaimed the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. Following this historic act, the UNGA called upon all Member countries to publicize the text of the Declaration and "to cause it to be disseminated, displayed, read and expounded principally in schools and other educational institutions, without distinction based on the political status of countries or territories."

The UDHR (1948) spells out rights that must be protected but it is not binding in international law. There are, however, accompanying covenants which carry some form of obligatory force on parties who have ratified them: the 1996 International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and International Covenants on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights. The Commission of Human right has power to discuss gross violations of human rights but not to investigate. The HRC set up in 1977 has power to hear complaints from individuals under certain circumstances about alleged breaches of the 1966 Covenant on Civil and Political Rights.

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), adopted by the UN General Assembly in 1948, laid the foundations for international human rights law.

With its nine (9) core, distinct human rights instruments, the UN has developed a range of mechanisms to monitor and promote compliance with human rights treaties. This includes the monitoring by different bodies of both the general human rights situation and also of the implementation of state parties obligations in key instruments.

Last year marked the 70th Anniversary of the UDHR (1948-2018) since the signing of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights on December 10, 1948. Representatives of 48 countries came together at the United Nations in Paris to make a profound statement on the value and dignity of human life. After several drafts and much debate, the final version of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights emerged. It was a list of basic rights that the international community agreed upon as the inborn (inherent) legacy due

to all human beings on earth.

There are 30 articles in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, covering various categories of human rights, such as basic rights (e.g., life, security of the person, freedom); political rights (e.g., right to vote); civil rights and liberties (e.g., freedom of opinion and expression); equality rights (e.g., the right to be free from discrimination); economic rights (e.g., the right to fair wages and safe working conditions); social rights (e.g., access to education and adequate health care); and cultural rights (e.g., the right to speak your native language and practice your culture).

There are two main themes contained in the preamble: The first is the belief that in order to support a better quality of life for all, laws that protect human rights must be enforced and respected universally. The second is the belief that, by upholding human rights, "*freedom, justice, and peace in the world*" can be achieved. In short, respecting human rights means a better world for everyone.

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights is a profoundly important document for people all over the world because it is founded on three key principles. Human rights are *inalienable*: no one can ever take them away from you. Human rights are also *indivisible*: you cannot be entitled to some of them and denied others. Finally, human rights are *interdependent*: they are all part of a larger framework and work together so you can enjoy a safe, free, and productive life. Failure to protect one right can lead to abuse of other rights, just as taking action to fulfill one right can lead to the fulfillment of other rights.

Using the Universal Declaration of Human Rights as a guide, governments are responsible for creating national laws to protect universal human rights. Citizens can then use their own judicial and legal systems to prosecute individuals or groups that have violated human rights.

Fifty-six nations that belonged to the United Nations agreed to follow the ideas in this document. Today, more than 185 nations around the world have taken the ideas from the UDHR and put them in their own constitutions. In Sierra Leone, the Chapter 3 of 1991 Constitution guarantees these universal rights.

As it was proclaimed thus:

"Now, therefore, The General Assembly, Proclaims this Universal

Declaration of Human Rights as a common standard of achievement for all peoples and all nations, to the end that every individual and every organ of society, keeping this Declaration constantly in mind, shall strive by teaching and education to promote respect for these rights and freedoms and by progressive measures, national and international, to secure their universal and effective recognition and observance, both among the peoples of Member States themselves and among the peoples of territories under their jurisdiction.”

1.2.1 CLARIFICATION OF KEY TERMS – ARBITRARY DETENTION AND ARREST

Before proceeding, it is important we clarify what falls under detention or arrest and what amounts to it being arbitrary. In other words, clarifying the meaning of ‘arrest’ and ‘detention’ within the context of which the researcher hopes the reader assesses this body of work against. The difference in meaning between the two terms is critical. This is so because, if an individual classes an act as detention or falsely defines his situation as amounting to undue arrest, that will in reality prevent the operation of **Article 9** of the UDHR. It goes then without saying, that a summary of different opinions on the meaning of arrest and detention is warranted, highlighting the nuances and shades of meanings assigned to these words accordingly. We shall briefly examine three (3) distinct authors in this context.

The battle over semantics is often hard-won. The consensus over meaning of words is fairly reached. These nuances are the motive of this particular exercise.

Laurent Marcoux Jr. (1996) in his publication entitled **“Protection from Arbitrary Arrest in International Law”** Volume 5., provided his context of the words arrest and detention, aligning with United Nations Committee on the Study of the Right of Everyone to be Free from Arbitrary Arrest, Detention and Exile. In his publication, arrest was defined as:

“The act of taking a person into custody under the authority of the law or by compulsion of another kind and includes the period from the moment he is placed under restraint up to the time he is brought before an authority competent to order his continued custody or to

release him”.⁶

From his definition, two elements became noticeable that is, the manner in which the arresting authority mounts the restraint on the individual’s personal liberty, and the length of time for which a suspect may be held in custody on the basis of the arrest. This takes into account that arrest is done the moment a person’s bodily movement is curtailed by another as per force. His definition also captures the overall bearings of an arrest, which in most cases will involve the elements aforementioned. He went on to define what entails detention as:

*"The act of confining a person to a certain place, whether or not in continuation of arrest, and under restraints which prevent him from living with his family or carrying out his normal occupational or social activities."*⁷

The essence of his definition of detention focused exclusively on confinement and deprivation of personal liberty and qualified it with the discontinuation of the individual’s normal activities, either as a citizen or a ‘family man’.⁸

Secondly, Jared McPherson (2004) in his research “**Indefinite Detention: A Democratic Counterterrorism Policy**”, advocated strongly for clarity on the circumstances that will qualify as arrest and detention. That is, what it actually entails and how it is done, and done properly. He proposed the idea that arrest and detention done in accordance to law poses no problems, and as long as the due process of the law is maintained. He opened his research by stating that a fundamental liberty safeguarded by democracy is the right to “due process” of law and while due process may be referred to by different terms in different countries, under US law it refers to those laws and legal proceedings that curb the power of the government on behalf of the individual. He goes further to say that due process restricts a government’s ability to deprive an individual of “life, liberty, or property” without first taking steps to protect his or her fundamental rights: such as by providing a trial by jury, the right to counsel, or protection against self-incrimination.

⁶ (1996), Laurent Marcoux, Jr., *Protection on Arbitrary Arrest and Detention Under International Law*, 5 B.C. Int'l & Comp. L. Rev. 345 (1982), United Nations, Study of the Right of Everyone to be Free From Arbitrary Arrest, Detention and Exile, 34 U.N. ESCOR Supp. (No.8) at 5, U.N. Doc. E/CN.4/826/Rev. I (1964),

⁷ Ibid.

⁸ The definitions of "arrest" and "detention" would also cover the phenomenon of the "disappeared" individuals abducted through the complicity, consent or conspiracy of governments which later deny that the victim is in their custody or in the custody of their agent, *Amnesty International, Disappearances: A Workbook (1981)*.

Thirdly, Douglass Cassel (2009), in his publication “**International Human Rights Law and Security Detention**”, for Notre Dame School of Law, shows that a different scenario may exist for such individuals who ‘held’ for the purpose of security detention.¹⁰ In this case, the act of arrest is broadened to include scenarios which contravene procedural rules of arrest as set in the Body of Principles and Human Rights Committee General Comments No. 8 or other such documents regulating arrest and detention in international law. This form of detention, however, should not be confused with arbitrary detention even though it is easier for elements of arbitrariness to be present. Security or preventative detention is restraining the individuals for the purpose of investigation or custody.

The Sierra Leone Criminal Procedure Act 1965, which regulates arrest and detention rules in respect of persons exercising such authority, finally sets the threshold of forceful pressure to be allowed during arrest.¹¹ It further detailed special circumstances where authorities can arrest with or without warrant. Also, in addition to the arrest, in Section (15) demands for the individual to be informed of cause of arrest, and not just arbitrarily detained without any factual cause or basis. With these in mind, it is important to know when, then, a detention becomes arbitrary.

2.2.1 WHEN IS DETENTION “ARBITRARY”?

The United Nations Working Group on Arbitrary Detention categorically stated three (3) scenarios. That is, the deprivation of liberty is arbitrary if a case falls under one of the following categories:

The **first category** is when it is clearly impossible to invoke any legal basis justifying the deprivation of liberty (as when a person is kept in detention after the completion of his sentence or despite an amnesty law applicable to him).

The **second category** is when the deprivation of liberty results from the exercise of the rights and freedoms guaranteed by articles of 7, 13, 14, 18, 19, 10 and 21 of the

⁹ MacPherson, Jared Lee B.A Brigham Young University (2014): *Indefinite Detention: A Democratic Counterterrorism Policy*, Wright State University, p. 1. -

¹⁰ Cassell, Douglass (2009): “*International Human Rights Law and Security Detention*”, Notre Dame School of Law

¹¹ Section 8 of the Criminal Procedure Act, 1965

Universal Declaration of Human Right and insofar as State Parties are concerned, by articles 12, 18, 19, 21, 22, 25, 26, and 27 of the ICCPR.

The **third and final category** is when the total or partial non-observance of the international norms relating to the right to a fair trial, spelled out in the UDHR and in the relevant international instruments accepted by States concerned, is of such gravity as to give the deprivation of liberty an arbitrary character.

Therefore, when a case falls under these headings, it is automatically a gross breach of that individual's right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention.

However, whether the word "arbitrary" has any substantive content remains a question. This issue was considered in the *travaux preparatoires* of the UDHR, during which it emerged that term "arbitrary" means the same as "illegal", or "unjust" or "both illegal and unjust". In the end, none of these expressions was included in the text of the Declaration.¹² Later, in 1965, the UN Study on this article adopted the following definition:

"An arrest of detention is arbitrary if it is (a) on grounds or in accordance with procedures other than those established by law, or (b) under the provisions of a law the purpose of which is incompatible with respect for the right to liberty and security of person".¹³

The publication then developed and somewhat clarified the circumstances wherein individual's claim for breach of his right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention is valid at law.

1.3 PROBLEM STATEMENT

One truth that remains clear today is the fact that the tragedies of the two World Wars were what compelled the international community to fight for human rights to be determined and protected. It resulted in a concerted effort aimed towards the protection and recognition of human rights and freedoms. However, a lesson to be drawn from this is that when a State pursues a deliberate policy of denying persons within its territory

¹² Human Rights Commission E/CN.4/SR.47, para. 43. Third Committee of the GA A/4045, para. 43-49

¹³ United Nations, " Study of the Right of Everyone to be Free from the Arbitrary Arrest, Detention and Exile". UN Publication Sales No 65.XIV.2 (1965), para. 7

their fundamental rights, not only is internal security of the State in Jeopardy, but in serious situations there is spillover effect that imperils the peace and security of other states as well. This hard-won lesson has been confirmed on numerous occasions in every part of the world. (Salvator, 1999)¹⁴

These rights fought for as enshrined in UDHR thus became sacrosanct, and deserving of respect from every authority, from every corner of the state. Among these inalienable rights is the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention. Guaranteed in Article 9 of the UDHR, and further in Section 17 of the 1991 Sierra Leone Constitution, the right of freedom from arbitrary detention becomes obligatory, mandatory and enforceable. This is the core of our study.

The attention drawn to arbitrary arrest and detention is well deserved. Studies have suggested that more than half of all suspects invited to the police station end up being detained and during this period of detention, are subjected to physical and psychological abuse.¹⁵ Worst of it, most times these people end up being released later without any charge or factual basis for their arrest. They were just arbitrarily detained.

The right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention gnaws at the very core of the rights to liberty and security of persons.¹⁶ Clearly, the act of depriving an individual's freedom is costly, it is badly placed in any society and many times, these abuses are functions of political injustice, abuse of power and weak enforcement mechanisms at national levels. When these abuses are allowed to continue unchecked, the consequences become weighty and burdened by this apparent lack of respect for this right, the government can only stand dishabille in the face of public outcry when it comes to their rights being covered.

It is also important to note that detainees are not only stripped of their right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention, they are also stripped of their rights to liberty and security of person, their rights to freedom of movement, and also their rights to freedom from torture, cruel, and inhuman treatment. This '*indivisibility effect*' is captured herein.

In Sierra Leone, the Sierra Leone Police (SLP) is the primary body responsible for arrest and detention and away from this obvious right which they continually abuse, they are also charged with the duty for protecting the state and its citizens, this they do, by

¹⁴ Salvatore Peledda, (1999) On being Human. Interpretations of Humanism from the Renaissance to the Present, 1997.

¹⁵ Interview with Lawyer Alimamy Sultan Koroma

¹⁶ Article 3 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, 1945.

ensuring the rights of each and every person is respected and accorded the sufficient amount of recognition reasonable for it to be practiced. However, the contrary is the prevalent.

The institution's modus operandi is brought aback by their open maltreatment of convicted persons, whether they proved resistant or not, detaining individuals without sufficient factual basis, and holding them for longer durations than necessary. Their administrative structure suffers for lack of respect for the citizen and still continues to be plagued by issues of bribery and corruption. And these happen to not be mere claims or personal conjectures, as our study will explore these areas respectively.

After all, the symptoms of our malaise are too familiar, and it calls for attention and action. The solutions must not be rushed. And it will only take deliberate government actions and commitment to international human right standards set in **Article 9** of the UDHR and other such documents in protecting the citizen's rights. And also, a robust feedback mechanism to follow-through with institutions dealing with human rights in particular where arbitrary arrest and detention is concerned, ought to be in place. This will uncover the lacuna in the implementation and enforcement of international standards to the promotion and development of human rights in Sierra Leone.

1.5 AIMS AND OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

The aim of this study is to solely examine the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention. It looks at both international and national documents protecting the right and analysing data in alignment with the objective of the study. It goes further to clarify the circumstances under which this right may be threatened and where it is insecure. Even though **Article 9** of the Universal Declaration Human of Rights is not binding per se, yet its influence in successive international human rights documents (ICCPR, ICESCR etc.) remains visible. Therefore, when necessary, these documents are integrated into the researcher's analysis and examination. The study, thus, sets as its objective the following:

1. To examine the relevance of the right freedom from arbitrary detention to the development of Human Right Law in Sierra Leone
2. To assess the impact created by Article 9 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights.

3. To examine the structures and systems adopted at national level to curb the practice of arbitrary arrest and detention.
4. To evaluate challenges faced in the implementation of the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention.
5. To suggest ways that will further improve the protection of the individual's right from arbitrary arrest and detention, and by extension the development of human right practices in Sierra Leone.

1.6 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The core of our research is driven by these research questions, i.e. every data, analysis, examination and findings are carefully aligned with these research questions below:

1. What relevance has the right of freedom from arbitrary detention posed in the development and implementation of Sierra Leone's Human Rights Law?
2. What has been the impact of Article 9 of the UDHR thus far?
3. Do our local policing procedures adequately abide by international legal standards applicable to arrest and detention?
4. Has Sierra Leone as a country faced any challenges in the implementation and practice of Article 9 of the UDHR?
5. What mechanism has the government put in place to promote the protection of the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention?

1.8 METHODOLOGY FRAMEWORK

Research data for this piece of work will be collected from various sources ranging from in-depth interviews, questionnaires, surveys, reports, group and personal discussions altogether in a bid to ascertain the underlining issue of arbitrary detention, its enforcement and challenges. The research methodology adopted thus will be both quantitative and qualitative.

1.9 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This study will undoubtedly serve as:

- (a). A means to actually identify what is arbitrary detention, its unlawfulness and abuse, by extension increasing public awareness as regards the issue.
- (b). A reference document, providing the bulk of vital knowledge on the right of freedom from arbitrary detention and arrest, urging the government to re-assert its commitment to upholding the right.
- (c). A go to guide whenever the issue is debated on or just generally when doubts are shuddered over it acting as an intentional point of view for right activists
- (d). A means to contextualise the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention within the larger framework of international human rights
- (e). An invaluable resource on the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention for human right students, researchers, policy makers, government workers, constitutional administrative, human right activists and political pundits alike.

1.8 SCOPE AND LIMITATION OF STUDY

The scope of this study centers on the relevance of right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention, its relevance, impact as human rights, its implementation, enforcement, and challenges encountered. The precise wording of Article 9 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights contains four essential concepts: (a) "*arbitrary*," (b) "*arrest*," (c) "*detention*," and (d) "*exile*."²⁰ However, this research exclusively focuses on the imposition of restrictions on personal liberty within a state rather than with the expulsion of a person from the country of which he is a national. Therefore, the author will concentrate on an analysis of the first three concepts strictly. The entirety of the study is guided and engulfed in three (3) words: ***Paradox, Possibility & Panacea***. They are, however, not exclusive chapters, but guiding doctrines for the research.

PARADOX – Challenges that militate against the protection and enforcement of the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention.

POSSIBILITY – Situations that exist under the law that may result in the infringing the individual's liberty or where the may be threatened.

PANACEA – Recommendations going further for the protection of the individual’s right of freedom from arbitrary detention

1.9 STRUCTURE OF DISSERTATION

The structure of this research is designed thus:

This dissertation is divided into five (5) chapters, each, being a part of the whole, contributing towards a coherent body of work, and advancing the object of the research linearly.

The first chapter will commence by introducing, or giving a background of **Article 9** of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, and follows it by tracing its origin and development. It further clarifies the meanings of arrest and detention in a context within which the researchers wants the reader to understand it, and finally sets the stage for the rest of the chapters to build upon progressively.

The second chapter is a literature review on the topic, the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention. It comparatively examines relevant literatures, ranging from books, journals, thesis, articles and reports dealing with topic, reviewing them in light of the research and adapting them with added reference to Sierra Leone, and drawing analytical conclusions accordingly.

The third chapter gives away the methodology and research techniques employed in the collection of data during research and most importantly why certain forms of approach are preferred over the other. This is done in a bid to ensure justice is done to the issue and no stones are left unturned.

The fourth chapter presents data findings from the researches conducted via interviews, questionnaires, in-depth discussions, and focus groups towards the set objectives and align these findings in light of the research questions asked and objective of the research.

The final chapter summarizes the entire research and concludes the study. It goes on to provide recommendations as ‘*Panacea*’, through which the right of freedom from arbitrary detention can be further strengthened, protected and respected in Sierra Leone.

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

There have been, for the most part, instrumental reviews on the issue of arbitrary detention and arrest, the cruelty of the practice, its devastating impact on human rights laws, and sometimes just on the act itself: the sheer deprivation of an individuals' liberty for no justifiable cause. This practice of arresting and detaining an individual without basis and trampling on the individuals' freedom is often legally unwarranted. A majority of these reviews were undertaken with the sole object of having a voice against the pervasiveness of the act, and the cruelty and arbitrariness that comes with it. These are most times activism of some kind, which have resulted in little stride or progress achieved in settling the idea of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention in **Article 9** of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. However, the reviews are in terms with the singular idea, that is, the act is a gross violation of human rights and freedoms; hence it must be muzzled.

International human right laws set the framework for national governments in the formulation and development of the human right laws that regulate them internally. These national governments carry state obligations to effectively implement the standards set by these documents whether they are of obligatory or customary force; or ratified by them as per treaty. Sierra Leone is no exception. That is, every treaty or convention that it has ratified binds the government to protect and conform to these standards. Mostly, compliance often saw the national government incorporating elements from these conventions and treaties into their national legislation, for example **Article 9** of the UDHR and **Article 9** of the ICCPR influenced **Section 17** of the 1991 Constitution of Sierra Leone. Protecting the same right, they are all aimed at the promotion of the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention, achieved through different means, but culminating towards the same end.

Our review will therefore focus exclusively on the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention, carefully assimilating relevant literatures ranging from books, journals, articles, reports, and researches on the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention. It further embarks on comparative analysis and in-depth application of the propositions advanced and developed, aligning them where necessary to our modern day society in Sierra Leone. These works examine and analyse the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention in light different circumstances, for example, as it applies to asylum-seeker, executive detention,

2.5.0 THE RIGHT OF FREEDOM FROM ARBITRARY DETENTION AND ARREST

2.5.1 THE PRACTICE AND SCOPE OF PROTECTION OF ARTICLE 9.

The right of freedom from arbitrary detention and arrest is embedded in the responsibility of every state and governing authority. The duty to protect its citizens became mandatory with the crystallization of moral rights into human right laws, empowering persons whose rights have been violated to seek redress. Therefore In Article 9 of the UDHR, this freedom is protected from those arrests and detentions that are carried out arbitrarily, disregarding set procedures and standards relating to the proper execution of arrest and detention in local legislation.

Sarah Perrella (2014), in her embodying research work, divided into (3) Chapters entitled: **“The Maltese Practice of Detention of Asylum-seekers and Irregular Migrants in light of International Standards”** opened her enquiry and research into the practice of arbitrary and unlawful detention by making her case at the onset, that the absence of real grounds for detaining asylum-seekers, the prolonged period of detention and the absence of effective legal assistance and legal avenues to challenge this detention make this deprivation of liberty unlawful and arbitrary. Hence, her reason for looking into arbitrary or ‘unlawful’ detention as it pertains asylum-seekers in the Malta.

The main thrust of her thesis was that the Maltese legislation did not provide for differential treatment for individuals seeking asylum as compared with irregular migrants entering the country. They were both subject to hostile treatment in detention centers and denied the privilege to challenge their detention. This, she continued, undermined their universal human rights as provided for in the UDHR, especially in **Article 9**, protecting their right of freedom for arbitrary arrest and detention. In her abstract, she discredited

the Maltese government superstitious reason for unlawfully detaining migrants purely on basis of assumption of insecurity that they migrants posed to their country.

In her [**Chapter 1**] she made her case for asylum-seekers and why this issue of detaining migrants did not augur well for asylum-seekers also. They being in earnest need for refuge and protection are treated equally as the irregular migrants and subjected to unlawful detention in custody centers pending deportation. This was the author's main contention. In other jurisdictions, their policies in place as regards the handling and treatment of migrants may considerably differ, in that, foreigners are rarely ever detained, not to mention unlawfully arrested. In Sierra Leone, for instance, our national police force are accustomed to treating foreigners with special treatments with high hopes of getting tokens in return for that special treatment. And these officers are at the drop of a hat, ready to detain their fellow citizens in the name of political order, under the guise of sustaining peace.

According to her research, the prevalence of arbitrary detention in the Malta was alarming. In her introductory chapter, she stated that since 2002, more than 18,000 individuals arrived in Malta by boat and the country has been dealing on the one hand with the practical management of high numbers of boat arrivals during summer months and, on the other hand with the public impression and fear of being unable, due to the dimensions of the island, to cope with the influxes of asylum-seekers and migrants. Those facts and feelings, together with the existence of a very restrictive immigration legislation have led to a practice, whereby anyone entering the country in an irregular manner is [arbitrarily] detained upon arrival, regardless of his or her being an asylum-seeker or a migrant.

Examining the scope of protection of the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention, and even though international legal experts agree that the term "arbitrary" imposes a standard to which national legal norms must conform, they encounter difficulty in delineating the scope of the standard. Most commentators, in trying to define "arbitrary," have referred to several imprecise ethical standards. Thus, the exact scope of protection still remains vague and unclear. In fact, "arbitrary" may not be susceptible of a single, all-encompassing definition. However, several criteria do give content to the standard. In the following discussion, the author reviews these criteria and then suggests a methodology by which the word "arbitrary" may be used to evaluate national legal

norms (Sarah Perrella, 2014).¹⁷

In [Chapter 1.1.1.3], titled: “*Right to Liberty and Security of the Person and Freedom of Movement.*”—— She made a precise and important case for these asylum-seekers. She contested even though these people are refugees, yet they are human beings, and thus subject to the fundamental human rights and should not be discriminated against. These are rights that any individual anywhere is entitled to. In our case, Article 9 of the UDHR prohibiting the restricting of the individual’s freedom arbitrarily or unlawfully and also, Article 3 of the UDHR, guaranteeing the right to life, liberty and security of person. This made even more the application of Article, both in the UDHR and ICCPR and as such, the Maltese’s government non-adherence to these inherent and inalienable rights attracted penalties. In Sierra Leone, despite the issue of refugees and asylum-seekers is at all-time low, yet the country is also signatory to the ICCPR and sworn to respect the fundamental human rights as contained in the UDHR. These documents serves as guide for the development of human rights law in the country. This is no more than the idea that every human being no matter his state of origin, nationality, status or class, is entitled to the fundamental human rights contained in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights.

She also quoted Meredith (2010) in her work: “*Asylum and the European Convention on Human Rights.*” outlining Article 5 of the European Convention on Human Rights, which established that detention for any reason which is not listed in Article 5, is automatically unlawful and the word “security” which is mentioned in the Article, precisely refers to the protection from unlawful or arbitrary detention. This, she continued, goes further to enlist the right of freedom from arrest and detention as mandatory in scope of protection to any that the act is valid and reasonable at law. The same article also foresaw that States provide for a speedy judicial review of the lawfulness of detention and grant the individual the right to take proceedings to challenge the lawfulness of detention and that an individual shall be immediately released if detention was not lawful. Additionally, where a prospect of removal no longer existed, detention ceases to be justified and the person shall be released.¹⁸

¹⁷ Sarah Perrella (2014), *The Maltese Practice of Detentions of Asylum-seekers and Irregular Migrants in light of International Standards*, Wien University.

¹⁸ N. Mole, C. Meredith, *Asylum and the European Convention on Human Rights*, Human Rights Files No. 9, Council of Europe Publishing Editions, Strasbourg, 2010, p. 143. The precise meaning of the Article and the way it should be implemented will be further analyzed from p. 26 onwards.

Further on page 37 [Chapter 1.2.2], entitled: “*Arbitrary Detention versus Right to Liberty and Security of the Person and Freedom of Movement.*” ——— She delved into the comparisons between arbitrary detentions i.e. the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention versus the right to liberty and security of the person and freedom of movement. The thrust of her argument was that arbitrary detention as practiced by the Maltese government was not absolute and as such the rights to liberty and security of persons are also not absolute. This, she goes to say, defines the scope of application of Article 9 of the UDHR. The situation of irregular migrants sought to reveal the hostile treatment and cruelty persons subjected to “temporary, arbitrary detention” encountered. Her conclusion sought to uncover the law that justified the application of a detention policy to asylum-seekers as whether they are provided for in national legislation, as prescribed in Article 9 of the ICCPR, and Article 5 of the European Conventions.¹⁹

However, her line of contention draws across the simple fact that the scope of Article 9 covers asylum-seekers, and even migrants who may have entered the county irregularly, despite the national legislation providing otherwise. She bases her argument of the element of universality of human rights, especially the rights to security of persons and liberty and freedom from arbitrary detention. In her evaluation of whether the policy of detention in Malta is arbitrary, many factors were taken into consideration. In fact, she proposed, the right to liberty and security of the person and freedom of movement are not absolute and immigration detention is not prohibited per se. However, for detention to be lawful and not arbitrary, it has to be authorized by law and to respect the principles of reasonableness, necessity, proportionality and non-discrimination.²⁰

Edwards (2011) in his work: “*Back to Basics: The Right of Liberty and Security of Persons: Alternatives to Detention*” further clarified the issue by noting that the

¹⁹ Council of Europe, *Convention for the protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms*, Art. 5, in Sandy Ghandhi (ed.), *Blackstone’s International Human Rights Documents* (8 edition), Oxford University Press, 2012, p. 258 and UNGA, *International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights*, Art. 9, in Sandy Gandhi (ed.), *Blackstone’s International Human Rights Documents* (8 edition), Oxford University Press, 2012, p. 35.

²⁰ A. Edwards, *Back to Basics, The Right to Liberty and Security of Person and “Alternatives to Detention” of Refugees, Asylum-Seekers, Stateless Persons and Other Migrants*, UNHCR Legal and Protection Policy Research Series, United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees, Geneva, April 2011, p. 20.

arbitrariness of detention refers to a broader concept, involving elements of inappropriateness, injustice and lack of predictability which do not necessarily equate to “against the law”. However, for detention to be lawful and not arbitrary, it has to be authorized by law and to respect the principles of reasonableness, necessity, proportionality and non-discrimination.²¹ He encapsulated the principles of reasonableness, necessity, proportionality and non-discrimination on which detention should be based. Striking the balance between these, he wrote requires state actors and authorities in power to conform to the rules and regulations prescribed by treaties and conventions as well as local legislation. So far, he concluded, the unlawfulness of the Maltese practice of detention has been discussed and it has emerged that deprivation of liberty of asylum-seekers is unlawful for the absence of *legitimate* grounds provided for by national law.

She further considered two circumstances of detention; one was legally permissible circumstance under which detention may occur and the duration or length of period of the detention. First, as regards the legality of detention, she quoted that the UNHCR maintains that detention of asylum-seekers must be a measure of last resort, which may exceptionally be permissible only in order to protect public order, public health or national security. Additionally, incarcerating an individual must be deemed necessary on the basis of an individual assessment and the necessity must exist over the whole time period of detention. An asylum-seeker may be detained to prevent absconding or in case of likelihood of non-cooperation with the authorities, in case of manifestly unfounded or abusive claims, for initial identity or security verification, in order to record the initial claim for international protection if not obtainable without detention, to carry out health checks or to avoid threats to national security. Nevertheless, the lengthy period of detention to which asylum-seekers are subjected to in Malta does not fit with cases in which this kind of controls have to be conducted.

Second, and very important in her work, on page 41, [Chapter 1.2.2] she also considered the duration and length of detention, which may also render detention as arbitrary; in which she maintained that the principle of proportionality foresaw that the action taken against an individual should not exceed what is necessary to obtain the pursued objective. Specifically, she continued, the interests of the State must be balanced with the

²¹ Ibid, p. 19

individual's right to liberty and security of the person and freedom of movement. She concludes that the duration of detention in Malta clearly exceeds any objective related to medical or security controls or prospects of removal and it is therefore not proportionate. Maltese law sets no maximum limits on the duration of detention of asylum-seekers and, in practice, persons are released once they are granted some form of protection by the Office of the Refugee Commissioner. Prior to December 2003, Malta even employed a policy of indefinite detention of migrants and asylum-seekers who had entered the country irregularly, in accordance with the Immigration. An asylum-seeker thus stays in detention either until his or her asylum procedure is concluded positively or for a minimum period of one year if the decision is still pending. It must be highlighted that the reasons for detaining asylum-seekers should be provided for by law together with a precise time period and that it is not appropriate to base the duration of detention of persons claiming for international protection on Article 11 of the EU Reception Conditions Directive, which regulates access of asylum-seekers to the labor market.²² However, the fact that access to labor market can be prohibited for a period of time shall not mean that Member States are justified to detain asylum-seekers during that period.

According to her research, the grounds for detaining asylum-seekers have been clearly listed in European and international law and detention ought to never last longer than the existing purpose justifying it, otherwise it would become disproportionate. This will undoubtedly result in that detention being arbitrary as has been the case with the Maltese government. Simply put, however, an act of detention or arrest, which goes against laid down procedures and rules. Duration of detention should therefore be clearly regulated by national primary law, and be based on clear purposes regulated by legal provisions. From this, it can be inferred that her case pleaded for an issue of adherence to the international standards as set in the Body of Principles for the Protection of All Persons under Any Form of Detention or Imprisonment, Article 9 of the ICCPR and the UDHR. This is so because, there appears to be no plausible reason provided in the legislation and in practice for the detention of asylum-seekers as such, the same shortcoming is reflected in the duration of detention, which fails to be justified by any plausible and solid ground. In other words, these detentions happened to be baseless and thus unlawful.

²² Council Directive 2003/9/EC of 27 January 2003 laying down minimum standards for the reception of asylum-seekers, OJ L31/18, Art 11(2).

In **Chapter 2**, she delved in-depth into the legal frameworks, both international, and regional framework, that regulate the freedom of the individual and security persons as it related to vulnerable persons within the group of asylum-seekers, for example, children, elderly, women etc. She made a case that the persons are detained without an assessment of their needs and without any consideration of the impact that detention may have on their wellbeing. It has already been argued, she noted, that asylum-seekers, being individuals, shall not be deprived of their liberty, and the deprivation of liberty of these vulnerable subgroups of asylum-seekers made it even less justifiable and a general principle taken from the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) and from the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights and Freedoms should be applied in general and should work as a guidance especially in the treatment of vulnerable persons: “*All persons deprived of their liberty shall be treated with humanity and with respect for the inherent dignity of the human person*”.²³

The inherent dignity of vulnerable persons, she proffered, clearly required particular analysis and attention, as the needs of vulnerable persons have to be assessed in order for their dignity to be respected. And detention created the risk of clashing with the fundamental right to respect for physical and mental health of persons.²⁴

In this chapter, she examined at four (4) groups: children, family, disabled persons, and elderly all within the context of unlawful detention and the deprivation of their right to freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention. Each of these groups being entitled separately to the rights that governs and protects them against such deprivation of freedom. These rights, she explored and identified, are enshrined in respective conventions and treaties that the Maltese government is a signatory. In juxtaposing both national and international legal frameworks, it can be drawn that the Maltese government unreasonably pursued a policy or arbitrarily detaining individuals without any factual or justifiable reason, they also keep them locked up for longer period without attention and during these period, members of these vulnerable groups often fall extremely ill and risked dying.

In her final chapter, she brought home her argument with the deplorable conditions in

²³ UNGA, *International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights*, Art. 10, in Sandy Gandhi (ed.), Blackstone’s International Human Rights Documents (8 edition), Oxford University Press, 2012, p. 36.

²⁴ European Union, Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (2000), OJ C364/1, Art. 3, in Sandy Gandhi (ed.), Blackstone’s International Human Rights Documents (8 edition), Oxford University Press, 2012, p. 353.

these detention centers and called attention to the prisoners rights despite being arbitrarily detained, in other word, in as much they, may have been detained arbitrarily, they still possessed ‘rights behind bars’. What, however, stood out as similar situations exist in Sierra Leone prison centers is the inadequacy of the buildings and resulting overcrowding and detention should take place in specifically designed centers, in conditions adequate to their legal status and to their particular needs.²⁵ And they possess the right entitling them to adequate privacy, space, security, lighting, ventilation, basic infrastructure and adequate location, as well as protection from cold and other threats to health and sustainable access to natural and common resources, safe drinking water, energy for cooking, heating and lighting, sanitation and washing facilities, means of food storage, refuse disposal, and these are abided by, simultaneously breaching the standards of the ICCPR and UDHR. Her work ended on a firm note that asylum-seekers are individuals, equally entitled to human rights, and should, as a principle, not be detained, unless serious grounds justify their deprivation of liberty and the same applies to vulnerable persons. Detention as a punishment and even less, as a deterrent against irregular migration, are no legal grounds for justifying the deprivation of liberty of a person.

From her work, then, it became evident that the enemy of the rights of individuals turn out to be governments and state authorities, who, for one reason or the other refuse to adhere to Article 9 of the UDHR, and ICCPR in dealing other people.

Claire Macken, in her research, structured in articles of five (5) broadly entitled: **“Preventive Detention and The Right of Personal Liberty and Security under the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, 1966: *Preventative Detention and Personal Liberty.*”** (2005) *Adelaide Law Review*, juxtaposed the right of personal liberty and security i.e. the freedom of the individual, and a situation of preventive detention, which enables a person to be deprived of his liberty, by executive determination, for the purposes of safeguarding national security or public order without that person being charged or brought to trial.

Ms. Macken, thus, looked at the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention in

²⁵ UN Congress on the Prevention of Crime and the Treatment of Offenders, *Standard Minimum Rules for the Treatment of Prisoners*, U.N. Doc. A/CONF/611, Geneva, 30th, August 1955, Arts. 46-47, Council of Europe, *European Prison Rules*, Recommendation Rec (2006) 2 of the Committee of Ministers to member states, 11 January 2006, Arts. 71, 72 (1, 3).

light of preventive detention, i.e. when is the threshold of arbitrariness crossed.

The line is drawn between arbitrary detention and executive detention, which makes up the bulk of her study. She explained preventative detention as the deprivation of personal liberty prior to criminal conviction in modern legal systems characteristically occurring as a precautionary measure to ensure that the administration of criminal justice is not frustrated or obstructed by those who may become subject to its processes. In other words, a person is arrested on reasonable suspicion that they have committed a criminal offence, and is detained in custody until a trial takes place to pass judgment on their suspected criminal conduct. The principal objective of criminal law is to punish convicted offender.²⁶ In all cases, the courts are generally empowered to judicially determine whether a person should be deprived of their liberty in accordance with grounds enumerated in national legislation or international instrument. Yet, in recent decades, decisions of the executive arm of government have increasingly eschewed all of the typical features of the criminal justice system through the practice of preventive detention. ‘Preventive detention’ is often called ‘administrative detention’ for the reason that such detention is ordered by the executive and the power of decision rests solely with the administrative or ministerial authority.

Her work looked at arbitrary detention along the lines of preventive detention, which, away from the previous review, are the many ‘*guises*’ under which arbitrary arrest and detention may appear

According to her research, the sole purpose of preventive detention is to safeguard national security or public order. A person is detained, not for punishment for a proven transgression of the criminal law, but because the individual is considered a potential threat to state security.²⁷ The accusation typically refers to some imprecise activities, allegedly prejudicial to the public interest and in which, it is claimed, and the detainee is likely to become involved unless detained.²⁸ In some cases the suspicion itself is based on the detainee’s past criminal infractions or associations, but in other cases, such suspicion may be purely speculative.

²⁶ John Hatchard, *Individual Freedoms & State Security in the African Context: The Case of Zimbabwe* (1993), 46.

²⁷ In *R v Halliday* (1917) AC 216, Lord Finlay described it as ‘not a punitive but a precautionary measure’.

²⁸ Andrew Harding and John Hatchard (eds), *Preventive Detention and Security Law: A Comparative Survey* (1993).

Very important is as we have learned that detention becomes arbitrary when there is no factual or justifiable reason for detaining the individual, however, under this kind of preventive detention, it occurs without charge or trial. As it is preventive in that no criminal offence has actually been committed, the detainee is not subjected to a charge, nor afforded the opportunity of trial before a competent court.

In a bid to achieve distinct clarity between these forms of detention and where it may overlap, i.e. arbitrary versus preventive detention, she offered two (2) definitions, First, it was defined in the case of **Union of India v Paul Nanickan and Anr**, the Supreme Court of India stated:

“The object of preventive detention is not to punish a man for having done something but to intercept him, before he does it, and to prevent him from doing it. No offence is proved, nor any charge formulated; and the justification for such detention is suspicion or reasonable probability and not criminal conviction, which can only be warranted by legal evidence.”²⁹

Another definition, she proffered, is that by the International Commission of Jurists’ Study on States of Emergency, who defined ‘administrative detention’ as they termed it, as:

“The deprivation of a person’s liberty, whether by order of the Head of State or of any executive authority, civil or military, for the purposes of safeguarding national security or public order, or other similar purposes, without that person being charged or brought to trial.”³⁰

The contention therefore was whether preventive detention was banned under international law. Mr. Louis Joinet, Special Rapporteur of the United Nations Commission on Human Rights, Sub-Commission on Prevention of Discrimination and Protection of Minorities in an explanatory paper concerning administrative detention stated:

²⁹ Union of India v Paul Nanickan and Anr, Appeal (Crl) 21 of 2002, (13 October 2003).

³⁰ International Commission of Jurists, States of Emergency: Their Impact on Human Rights (1983), 394.

“...contrary to what one might suppose, administrative detention is not banned on principle under international rules.”

The purpose of this explanatory paper was to address the question of whether preventive detention is a permissible deprivation of personal liberty under one international instrument, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, 1966 (‘ICCPR’). Further, it also assumed preventive detention is lawful under the ICCPR, thus what safeguards apply to those in preventive detention?

She then opened her **Chapter 2**, or second article, in her body of (5) articles, sub-titled: *“The Prohibition of Arbitrary Arrest And Detention.”* With a rather bold opening she contested that preventive detention is not explicitly prohibited by the ICCPR and that whether preventive detention is a permissible deprivation of liberty depends on whether it falls within the prohibition on arbitrary arrest and detention under Article 9(1) of the ICCPR. This Article states:

“Everyone has the right to liberty and security of person. No one shall be subjected to arbitrary arrest or detention. No one shall be deprived of his liberty except on such grounds and in accordance with such procedure as are established by law.”

This is further corroborated by **Article 9** of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, and **Article 3** of same, protecting against the arbitrary restriction of the individual’s freedom and person.

She sought the application of a textual analysis of these documents, in particular, the ICCPR, consistent with Article 31(1) of the Vienna Convention, which recommends:

“A treaty shall be interpreted in good faith and in accordance with the ordinary meaning to be given to the terms of the treaty in their context and in the light of its object and purpose.”

She then went on to provide two (2) interpretive situations where ‘arbitrary’ might come in. That is to say: a) An arrest or detention is ‘arbitrary’ if it is unlawful, that is, not in accordance with procedure as laid down by law; (*‘narrow interpretation’*); and b) An arrest or detention is ‘arbitrary’ if it is unlawful or unjust, that is, under the provisions of a law that do not accord with the principles of justice. Arrest or detention is ‘arbitrary’ if under a law the purpose of which is incompatible with respect for the right to liberty and security of person (*‘wide interpretation’*).

Firstly, in her narrow interpretation narrative, she x-rayed the content of **Article 9(1)** of the **ICCPR**, which states:

‘No one shall be deprived of his liberty except on such grounds and in accordance with such procedures as are established by law’.

And she concluded that by referring to the procedure as established by law, it could be argued the word ‘arbitrary’ was simply requiring arrest and detention to be ‘lawful’, that is, in accordance with legislative procedures. In light of this, she contended that the provisions of the ICCPR providing for judicial review of detention similarly support a restrictive interpretation of the word ‘arbitrary’. Article 9(4) of the ICCPR provides:

‘Anyone who is deprived of his liberty by arrest or detention shall be entitled to take proceedings before a court, in order that court may decide without delay on the lawfulness of his detention and order his release if the detention is not lawful.’

The right to compensation in Article 9(5) also applies to unlawful arrest and detention.

She further concluded that the very fact that the Article referred to ‘lawful’ and ‘unlawful’ arrest and detention arguably militated in favour of a restrictive interpretation of the word ‘arbitrary’, that is, contrary to a procedure established by law. This made her conclude that if the narrow interpretation of ‘arbitrary’ is correct, preventive detention is permissible under the ICCPR once it is within the scope of, and in accordance with, the legislative or executive authorisation permitting the detention to occur. Preventive detention, even as a result of despotic, tyrannical, objectively unreasonable legislation, would therefore be acceptable under this Article of the ICCPR.

This was one of her very logical stance that she took in de-intertwining the ‘arbitrary’ apart from the ‘preventive’ nature of this kind of detention, which is the main thrust of her study.

Lastly, she considered the “*wide interpretation*” of arbitrary in context with preventive detention, and drawing the lines clearly, she looked at the effect of the narrow interpretation of ‘arbitrary’ as concerns preventive detention, she stated that it is contended the wide interpretation of ‘arbitrary’ is more persuasive. The word ‘arbitrary’ should not just require a deprivation of liberty to be in accordance with procedures as established by law, but also imposes an additional higher requirement. The word

‘arbitrary’ is concerned with the actual content of laws, not just compliance with procedures in accordance with law. Her research also delved into the bare meaning of arbitrary and concluded it leaned towards a contention that the term in the ICCPR should be accorded a wide interpretation. The ordinary meaning of the word ‘arbitrary’, she tendered, clearly contemplates more than just ‘unlawful’.

She then embarked on what she called a “*structural analysis of Article 9 of the ICCPR*” and concluded that the word ‘arbitrary’ should be accorded a wide meaning is also supported by a structural analysis. She parsed the content of Article 9(1), identifying its parts, and divided it into three sentences:

Everyone has the right to liberty and security of person [first sentence].

No one shall be subjected to arbitrary arrest or detention [second sentence].

No one shall be deprived of his liberty except on such grounds and in accordance with such procedure as are established by law [third sentence].

In the Article, she dissected:

- (a) There is a right accorded to personal liberty and security in the first sentence;
- (b) There is a prohibition on arbitrary arrest and detention in the second sentence; and
- (c) There is a requirement that a deprivation of liberty be in accordance with procedures established by law (‘the principle of legality’) in the third sentence.

She submitted that if the drafters had intended a restrictive interpretation of the word ‘arbitrary’, there would be no point in including both the second and third sentences of the Article. The prohibition on arbitrary arrest and detention would be entirely superfluous because protection against solely unlawful arrest and detention would be covered by the principle of legality. And she continued by stating that on a structural analysis, a different meaning must have been intended for the prohibition on arbitrary arrest and detention, distinct from the principle of legality, protecting unlawful arrest and detention. As drafted, the Covenant is consistent if a distinct meaning is attributable to the prohibition on arbitrary detention (focusing on unlawful arrest and detention), and the principle of legality (concerned with the protection from arbitrary laws in addition to unlawful acts).³¹

³¹ Laurent Jr Marcoux, 'Protection from Arbitrary Arrest and Detention Under International Law' (1982)

Macken then proceeded on to analyse Article 9 of the UDHR in particular in a section titled: *“The Travaux Préparatoires of Article 9 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights 1948.”*

Here, she sought to further clarify the scope of protection of Article 9 of the UDHR as concerns preventive detention. This seeking of clarification is consistent with the rule of interpretation recommended in Article 32 of the Vienna Convention, which provided for ‘supplementary means of interpretation’. She proceeded to obtain further insight as to the appropriate interpretation of the word ‘arbitrary’, assisted by considering travaux préparatoires of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights 1948 (‘Universal Declaration’). As pointed out by Marcoux, although an **18** year difference exists between the adoption of the Universal Declaration and the adoption of the ICCPR, the initial drafting work of the two documents began at the same time.³² ‘Both instruments were not only drafted by the same bodies, but generally by the same draftsmen as well’.³³

The Articles in both instruments are similarly worded. Article 3 of the Universal Declaration states: ‘Every person has the right to life, liberty and security of person’. Article 9 states: ‘No one shall be subject to arbitrary arrest, detention or exile’, and tracing the drafting of **Article 9** of the Universal Declaration (**UDHR**) through the travaux préparatoires revealed that the draftsman intended a wide definition of the term ‘arbitrary’. She mentioned the initial draft of the Article, which prohibited arrest and detention ‘save in the cases provided for and in accordance with the procedure prescribed by law’.³⁴

And she concluded from the various drafting stages that Article 9 of the UDHR went through and concluded that clearly the travaux préparatoires of the Universal Declaration support a wide interpretation of the word ‘arbitrary’.

She later under the sub-heading: **United Nations Study Analysis of ‘Arbitrary Arrest and Detention’**, submitted that the Commission on Human Rights, at its twelfth session mandated the United Nations Economic and Social Council to conduct a study into the

5(2) Boston College International and Comparative Law Review 345, 359.

³² See Marcoux, above in p. 27, 359.

³³ Ibid.

³⁴ This, in fact, was the Secretariat draft examined and revised by Mr Rene Cassin of the Commission on Human Rights Drafting Committee. The drafting of the Universal Declaration in fact started with a United Nations Secretariat draft Declaration prepared by Dr John Humphrey. For a detailed discussion of the drafting process of the Universal Declaration see Marcoux, above n 14, 351–57.

phrase ‘arbitrary arrest and detention’ and in defining the terms of the Study, the suggestion was made that the word ‘arbitrary’ should be understood to mean arrest and detention either: **a)** on grounds or in accordance with procedures other than those established by law; or **b)** under the provisions of a law the basic purpose of which is incompatible with respect for the right to liberty and security of person.³⁵

To define the scope of ‘arbitrary’, the United Nations Committee had to consider the travaux préparatoires of Article 9 of the Universal Declaration and Article 9(1) of the ICCPR, as well as the United Nations Seminars on the Protection of Human Rights in Criminal Law or Procedure and finally adopted the following: “*An arrest or detention is arbitrary if it is (a) on grounds or in accordance with procedures other than those established by law, or (b) under the provisions of a law the purpose of which is incompatible with respect for the right to liberty and security of person.*”³⁶

The Committee therefore adopted the wide interpretation of ‘arbitrary’, in particular stating that ‘while an illegal arrest or detention is almost always arbitrary, an arrest or detention which is in accordance with law may nevertheless be arbitrary’.³⁷

She quoted the case of **Van Alphen v The Netherlands**, a case law of the human rights committee. In *Van Alphen v The Netherlands*, the Human Rights Committee considered the meaning of ‘arbitrary’ in Article 9(1) of the ICCPR. The brief fact was that the applicant was detained from 5 December 1983 to 9 February 1984 (a period of over nine weeks) without criminal charge or trial.

The Committee confirmed that ‘*arbitrariness*’ is not to be mistaken with ‘against the law’, but must be interpreted more broadly to include elements of inappropriateness, injustice and lack of predictability. This means that remand in custody pursuant to lawful arrest must not only be lawful but reasonable in all the circumstances.³⁸

This case then became one of the landmark cases in the determination of whether an individual can claim arbitrary arrest or detention or be refused the claim. That is, one cannot talk about arbitrary arrest and detention and refuse to mention the *Van Alphen* case. From her study, however, she went at length to draw the fine line between arbitrary

³⁵ United Nations 1964 Study,

³⁶ *ibid.*

³⁷ *ibid.*

³⁸ *Van Alphen v The Netherlands*, Communication No. 305/88, UN Doc. CCPR/C/39/D/305/1988.

detention and preventive detention. Another case was mentioned in her work which saw similar results and that was the case of in **A v Australia** where the Human Rights Committee held:

The Committee recalls that the notion of ‘arbitrariness’ must not be equated with ‘against the law’ but interpreted more broadly to include such elements as inappropriateness and injustice.³⁹

In concluding this section of interpretation, she referenced the thirteenth session of the Third Committee of the General Assembly where one meaning of ‘arbitrary’ submitted as arrest or detention pursuant to a law which was in itself ‘unjust’ or ‘incompatible with the dignity of the human person’ or incompatible with the respect for the right to liberty and security of person’.⁴⁰

It is therefore consistent to draw from her work, in order of review — ranging from a textual and structural analysis of Article 9(1), to the travaux préparatoires of both the Universal Declaration, UDHR and ICCPR, case law of the Human Rights Committee and the United Nations Study that the prohibition on arbitrary arrest or detention that it should be accorded a wide interpretation. And this will in turn lead to two propositions:

a) The deprivation of liberty must be lawful, in that it must accord with procedures as established by law. The arrest and detention must be specifically authorised and sufficiently circumscribed by law;⁴¹ and

b) The legislative enactment that permits arrest and detention must not itself be arbitrary. Legislation must conform to the principles of justice or with dignity of the human person, and must not be inappropriate or unjust.

To have a contrary interpretation would mean that any act or oppressive law of a government would be indomitable provided arrest and detention accorded with legislative enactment.⁴²

³⁹ A v Australia, Communication No. 560/1993, UN Doc. CCPR/C/59/D/560/1993 (30 April 1997).

⁴⁰ United Nations 1964 Study, above n 1, 6, referring to Official Records of the General Assembly, Thirteenth Session, Annexes, Agenda Item 32, document A/4045, [43–9].

⁴¹ Sarah Joseph, Jenny Schultz and Melissa Castan, *The International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights: Cases, Materials, and Commentary* (2000), p. 211

⁴² Parvez Hassan, 'The International Covenants on Human Rights: An Approach to Interpretation' (1969-1970) 19 *Buffalo Law Review* 35, 37.

This interpretation of the word ‘arbitrary’, she concluded, is consistent with the purposes of the Universal Declaration, in particular ‘protecting individuals from despotic legislation and to establish that deprivations of liberty, such as occurred under the Nazi regime, are not consistent with human rights merely because they were prescribed by national law’.⁴³ Further, ‘only an international minimum standard which operates independently of the vagaries of national legal systems can effectively protect human rights’.⁴⁴

To conclude her entire work, she looked at “**The Prohibition On Arbitrary Arrest and Detention as Applied to Preventive Detention**” ———

Preventive detention, she noted, is not explicitly provided for in international human rights law, nor does the prohibition on arbitrary arrest and detention exclude preventive detention per se. That preventive detention is not prohibited under the arbitrary arrest and detention provisions of the international human rights instruments is supported by the fact that the authoritative international institutions have refused on several occasions to condemn the practice in unequivocal terms.⁴⁵ She factually stated that preventive detention was clearly contemplated by the General Comments of the Human Rights Committee on Article 9 of the ICCPR:

“Also if so-called preventive detention is used, for reasons of public security, it must be controlled by these same provisions i.e. it must not be arbitrary, and must be based on grounds and procedures established by law (para. 1)....”⁴⁶

Also that preventive detention is consistent with the right to personal liberty and security and does not offend the prohibition on arbitrary arrest and detention is a view similarly evidenced by India’s reservation to Article 9 of the ICCPR⁴⁷, she protested.

⁴³ Yoram Dinstein, 'Right to Life, Physical Integrity, and Liberty' in Louis Henkin (ed), *The International Bill of Rights: The Covenant on Civil and Political Rights* (1983), 131.

⁴⁴ *ibid*, p. 130

⁴⁵ Derek P Jinks, 'The Anatomy of an Institutionalised Emergency: Preventive Detention and Personal Liberty in India' (2001) 22 *Michigan Journal of International Law* 311, 27.

⁴⁶ Human Rights Committee, General Comment 8, Article 9 (Sixteenth Session, 1982), UNDoc.HRI/GEN/1/Rev.1, 8 (1994).

⁴⁷ David H Bayley, *Preventive Detention in India: A Case Study in Democratic Social Control* (1962) and Derek P Jinks, 'The Anatomy of an Institutionalised Emergency: Preventive Detention and Personal Liberty in India' (2001) 22 *Michigan Journal of International Law* 311

A reservation in international law is a statement that purports to exclude or modify the legal effect of a treaty in its application to a State. According to General Comment 24 of the Human Rights Committee, ‘if a so-called reservation merely offers a State’s understanding of a provision but does not exclude or modify that provision in its application to that State, it is, in reality, not a reservation’.⁴⁸ The Indian Government’s view is that preventive detention laws under Article 22 of the Constitution of India do not involve an arbitrary or an unlawful deprivation of liberty.

Macken, also, looked at the decision of the Human Rights Committee in the case of **Campora Schweizer v Uruguay**, in which it was stated and confirmed that Article 9(1) can be used in cases of preventive detention. According to **Article 9(1)** of the Covenant, no one shall be subjected to arbitrary arrest or detention. In the case the applicant was kept under ‘prompt security measures’ without charges at the disposal of the executive authorities. He had been arrested on grounds of ‘association to break the law’. The Court held that the applicant’s imprisonment violated Article 9(3) and (4) since he had not been brought before a judge and could not take proceedings to challenge his arrest and detention.

Macken was later led to consider that although preventive detention is not in itself a violation of the ICCPR, the wide definition of ‘arbitrary’ discussed above has significant consequences for preventive detention. The wide definition of ‘arbitrary’ means unjust preventive detention legislation will violate Article 9(1) ICCPR. Therefore, if the provisions of a law authorising preventive detention have elements of inappropriateness, injustice and lack of predictability, it will be ‘arbitrary’ for the purposes of the right to personal liberty and security. For example, when preventive detention is used to counter-terrorism it may be considered arbitrary, an issue beyond the scope of this paper.

Further, she cautioned that although preventive detention is not, per se, excluded by the prohibition on arbitrary arrest and detention, detention will be ‘arbitrary’ when a detainee is not accorded procedural safeguards. In cases where preventive detention abrogates the safeguards in Article 9, there will be a breach of the prohibition on arbitrary arrest and detention, as well as a violation of the specific Article in question.

⁴⁸ Human Rights Committee, General Comment No. 24: Issues relating to reservations made upon ratification or accession to the Covenant or the Optional Protocols thereto, or in relation to declarations under Article 41 of the Covenant, CCPR/C/21/Rev.1/Add.6 (04/11/94), 2.

However, as we have learned in the previous review that as with every detention, the individual rights do not dissipate upon arrest, there are still “right behind bars”, these rights were considered in the concluding segment of her work. These are, as he termed them, “Safeguards applicable to those in preventive detention”: Article 9(2) –Right to be Informed of the Reasons for the Detention, Article 9(3) – Trial Within a Reasonable Time and Article 9(4) – Right to Challenge Detention Article 9(4) ICCPR. These are also basically ways you can avoid arbitrariness, a criteria was laid down by UDHR and ICCPR, i.e. (a) Everyone who is arrested shall be informed, at the time of arrest, of the reasons for his arrest. (b) Everyone who is arrested shall be promptly informed of any charges against him. (c) Anyone arrested or detained on a criminal charge shall be brought promptly before a judge or judicial officer. (d) Anyone who is deprived of his liberty shall be entitled to take proceedings before a court to have the lawfulness of his detention determined. (e) It shall not be the general rule that persons awaiting trial shall be detained in custody. Anyone arrested or detained on a criminal charge shall be entitled to a trial within a reasonable time or to release. Anyone who has been the victim of unlawful arrest or detention shall have an enforceable right to compensation. (f) No one shall be held guilty of any criminal offense on the basis of an act or omission, which did not constitute a criminal offense at the time that it was committed. No one shall be subjected to a heavier penalty than the one that was applicable at the time when the criminal offense was committed. (g) No one shall be imprisoned merely on the ground of inability to fulfill a contractual obligation.

The great bulk of Macken’s literature on delineating arbitrary detention and preventive illumines further another of the guises under which arbitrary detention may appear. This makes the distinction between ‘arbitrary’ detention and other forms of arrest and detention really clear.

Another work we shall review is closely related in content with the previous literature but differs in opinion, providing the richness the researcher envisaged for this study on arbitrary detention. It also uncovers another guise under which arbitrary detention may take form:

Helena Sola Martin, in her research, entitled: “**Right to Liberty and Prohibition of Preventive Detention**”, sought to delineate the scope of prohibition of preventive detention. That is, contrary to the previous review, she delved into the seeming overlap

between states' counter terrorism policies (preventive detention) and fundamental human rights. Her examination was captured in light of the ECHR. Stating the main thrust of her research, she submitted that States have traditionally vindicated the need to loosen up standards of detention to face extraordinary circumstances. In the political context dominated by the global War on Terror, there is an ongoing debate among scholars and lawmakers about the use of preventive detention as necessary means to prevent further terrorist attacks. The use of arbitrary detention in Guantánamo and the breach of the absolute prohibition of torture have widely raised concerns as regards the interplay between counter-terrorism and human rights. Nevertheless, less striking practices such as an abusive use of pre-trial detention, or obstacles to the right to effectively challenge the lawfulness of the detention, can equally shake the foundations of highly developed constitutional democracies by impairing the right to personal liberty and the presumption of innocence.

In the work the author zeroed in on **Chapter 2** to address issues relating to arbitrary detention, under Chapter 2.1, which she titled: "*Right of Liberty: "The Preferential Freedom."*" She considered the right to liberty⁴⁹ as enshrined in **Article 3** of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR)⁵⁰ and **Article 9** of the ICCPR, as well as in the regional human rights conventions, aimed at ensuring the freedom of bodily movement, that is, liberty of person understood in the physical sense.⁵¹ She also stated that an interference with personal liberty would be culminated when individuals are forced to remain within a constrained area, such as detention facilities (of which prisons are the most common example), psychiatric facilities, detoxification facilities and orders of house arrest. However, it is made clear that deprivation of liberty brings about the limitation or even interference with other human rights such as the right to private life, the right to freedom of expression, etc. Hence, this curtailment of the personal liberty entails a very grave measure of coercion on individuals, which, even when it has been

⁴⁹ Idea extracted from Trechsel, 2006, p. 463.

⁵⁰ The right to liberty can be traced back to the English Magna Carta (1215), clause 39, and the US Declaration of the Rights of Man and Citizen (1789). Even though the Magna Carta only guaranteed rights to a limited group of people, namely feudal noblemen, it nevertheless required that arrest or detention be lawful, and protected the individual against the excesses of his/her ruler (Icelandic Human Rights Centre, The Right to Liberty, available at: <http://www.humanrights.is/the-human-rights-project/humanrightscasesandmaterials/humanrightsconceptsideasandfora/substantivehumanrights/therightstoliberty/> (consulted on 14 April 2011).

⁵¹ Nowak, 2005, p. 212.

recognised as a potential lawful interference, needs to be applied in a very narrow and cautious manner.⁵²

She then moved on to index **2.2.1**, entitled: “*Lawfulness and Prohibition of Lawfulness*” where she dealt with the lawfulness of detention in context of the right of freedom to liberty and security of persons, and freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention in light of the ECHR’s jurisprudence. She first, as similar researchers, set out to examine the term “arbitrariness.” Exploring arbitrariness, she looked at the broader scope than the mere illegality, as was already pointed out by the majority of delegates assigned with the drafting of the ICCPR. As it was stated by the HRC, the term “arbitrariness” “must be interpreted more broadly to include elements of inappropriateness, injustice and lack of predictability”.⁵³ She further looked at General Comment no. 16 (1988), dedicated to Article 17 of the ICCPR on the right to a private life, which developed further the final meaning of arbitrariness saying that this concept “*is intended to guarantee that even interference provided for by law should be in accordance with the provisions, aims and objectives of the Covenant and should be, in any event, reasonable in the particular circumstances*”.⁵⁴ Along the same lines, the ECHR has said, “the law must itself be in conformity with the Convention, including the general principles expressed therein”.⁵⁵

The concept of arbitrariness, she contended, is not only linked to the nature and procedures governing detention but also to the manner this is executed and extended over time. This was clear as she further examined in the comment on para. 3 of Article 5, that arbitrariness can also be found “ad hoc” if the detention lasted beyond the period for which the authorities can provide appropriate justification.

Article 5 para. 1 of the ECHR had stated that no one is to be deprived of liberty save for the purposes set out in the same provision and in accordance with a procedure prescribed by law. Therefore, for the deprivation of liberty to be in compliance with personal liberty

⁵² Trechsel, 2006, p. 407: “One of the most frequently invoked human rights is the right to personal liberty. This is of little surprise as the interference with this right certainly causes considerable suffering. Moreover, contrary to the right to life and to physical integrity, it is a right, which the authorities regularly and lawfully interfere with, particularly in the context of crime control. It is the most serious measure of coercion permitted both by domestic and international criminal-procedure law and by the international human rights instruments”.

⁵³ *Van Alphen v Netherlands*, no. 305/1988, 23 July 1990, para. 5.8

⁵⁴ HRC, General Comment 16 (1988), para. 4.

⁵⁵ Macken, 2005, see above, p. 6: “the word ‘arbitrary’ is concerned with the actual content of laws, not just compliance with procedures in accordance with law, considering her wide interpretation”.

and respectful of the presumption of innocence, she suggested a double test of legality to be done i.e. procedures which regulate the above-mentioned interference are required to be “prescribed by law” which referred to domestic law and the arrest or detention ought to be “lawful”, that is, according to substantive rules as prescribed by these human rights documents.

This as comparatively applied to Article 9 of the UDHR, it shows that in as much as states do validate their domestic laws as in the name of sovereignty, a concept which in itself deserved clarity as most states even Sierra Leone has mistaken non-interference for not owing any obligation whatsoever.

Furthermore, she examined the interpretation given by the ECHR, in a bid to achieve clarity, the legal provisions need to satisfy certain qualities: be accessible to all individuals subject to the jurisdiction and precise enough, that is, grounds enabling the detention or arrest are required to be clearly set out as to allow individuals to foresee the consequences of their acts. The required level of precision will be assessed in the light of the nature, content and scope of the piece of legislation in question. Also, an unlimited power of discretion is precluded and therefore the legal provisions mentioned must afford mechanisms of protection against “arbitrary interferences” by public authorities, that is, in words of the ECHR, “the law must indicate with sufficient clarity the scope of any such discretion and the manner of its exercise”.

As previously mentioned, when it comes to ‘arbitrary’, it normally entails ‘discretion’ and police officers and state authorities often abuse this discretionary power.

Thus, if we looked at Article 9 of the ICCPR, which set out explicitly the condition of non-arbitrariness, Article 5 of the ECHR, however, does not mention this prerequisite. However, the exhaustive list of exceptions or categories in Article 5 para. 1 arises as a guarantee against “arbitrary deprivation of liberty” enhanced by the fact the Court has stated that only a narrow interpretation is “consistent with the aim of that provision”. Furthermore, the Court has repeated that the basic safeguard laid down in Article 5 is precisely impeding arbitrary interferences with the right to liberty. Hence, it can be asserted that the prohibition of arbitrariness constitutes the second general limitation; it is applicable both to the provisions enacted and to enforcement practices.

Her work proceeded to look at the grounds that can render an arrest or detention lawful, recalling the focus of her work which was to be the use of the so-called “pre-trial detention

framework” framed within the evolving meaning of the ECHR, which, to date, under the ECHR does not contemplate the so-called “preventive detention” outside proceedings conducted in the context of criminal justice as a lawful precautionary interference with the right to liberty. That is, unlike in many countries outside the European continent where schemes of detention that are not aimed to bring the suspected terrorist to trial but to thwart a predicted terrorist threat have been adopted under the ICCPR, the ECHR has maintained a very restrictive interpretation by which the possibility to take measures amounting to detention without charge in normal times under the auspices of the ECHR has been discarded.

Finally, she supported the right to be informed of the reasons for arrest and any charges, mainly in a bid to enhance clarity and transparency in procedures and systems. Her work then went on to conclude that indeed, pre-trial detention can be a useful tool when it is the only mechanism considered appropriate in order to ensure that the suspect will not abscond and that evidence can be gathered without risk of collusion, manipulation or destruction. In the context of the prevention and prosecution of terrorism-related offences, the decision to order detention on remand is often the last useful resort to avoid manoeuvres by well-organised and sophisticated networks.

In any case, she advocated, the need for detention on remand ought to be carefully assessed by courts in the light of individual rights [of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention] at stake. That is, according to the international standards protecting the right to liberty, this measure has to be applied when it is strictly necessary and this need should be only exceptionally affirmed. Nevertheless, practices in place do not live up to the normative framework. In the prosecution of crimes involving terrorism, requirements of pre-trial detention are applied leniently and what should be the exception often became the rule. It is important to note that her work dedicated the other chapters to peculiar situations having to do with terrorist prevention and may not directly have any significant bearing to this study, hence they were ignored.

The practice and scope of protection of Article 9 has been brought under the radar to the extent by which national legislations define arrest and detention in light of international laws, the UDHR and ICCPR in particular. Technically, the sphere within which the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention exists becomes strictly defined to the extent of only allowing abuses, which the arrest or detaining is executed on very little factual, evidential or procedural basis. So it is very clear that, the scope of the terms of

“arrest” and “detention” extends to all forms of deprivation of one’s liberty, but cannot be understood narrowly as criminal coercive measures (Cao Hua, 2003).

The deprivation of liberty is permissible only if it is ‘in accordance with procedures as are established by law’. Hence, arrest and subsequent detention must be specifically authorized and sufficiently circumscribed by law (Y. Dinstein, 2001).⁵⁶

As to the *principle of legality*, the Human Rights Committee has held that “it is violated if an individual is arrested or detained on grounds which are not clearly established in domestic legislation”; in other words, the grounds for arrest and detention must be “established by law”.⁵⁷ In a case where a person was arrested without a warrant, which was issued more than three days later, contrary to the domestic law that lays down that a warrant must be issued within seventy-two (72) hours after arrest, the Committee concluded that article 9(1) had been violated because the author had been “deprived of his liberty in violation of a procedure as established by law”.⁵⁸

With regard to the meaning of the words “*arbitrary arrest*” in article 9(1), the Committee has explained that ‘arbitrariness’ is not to be equated with ‘against the law’, but must be interpreted more broadly to include elements of *inappropriateness, injustice, lack of predictability and due process of law*. This means that remand in custody pursuant to lawful arrest must not only be lawful but reasonable in the circumstances. Remand in custody must further be necessary in all the circumstances, for example, to prevent flight, interference with evidence or the recurrence of crime”.⁵⁹ From the above, it is clear that the scope of arbitrary arrest covers every instance of arrest and detention that goes against article (9) of the UDHR, it strictly defined in so far as it involved an arrest which was inappropriate, a sign of injustice or against the law.

This tapers down to reliability of state actors in the execution of arrest and confinement within the confines of the law as laid down. In the In the Matter of **Buzurgmehr Yorov v. Government of the Republic of Tajikistan (2018)** - the issue of breach of the Body of Principles for the Protection of All Persons under Any Form of Detention or

⁵⁶ Y. Dinstein 2001: *Right to Life Physical Integrity and Liberty* in L. Henkin ed.

⁵⁷ Communication No. 702/1996, *C. McLawrence v. Jamaica* (Views adopted on 18 July 1997), in UN doc. *GAOR, A/52/40* (vol. II), pp. 230-231, para. 5

⁵⁸ Communication No. 770/1997, *Gridin v. Russian Federation* (Views adopted on 20 July 2000), in UN doc. *GAOR, A/55/40* (vol. II), p. 175, para. 8.1.

⁵⁹ Communication No. 458/1991, *A. W. Mukong v. Cameroon* (Views adopted on 21 July 1994), in UN doc. *GAOR, A/49/40* (vol. II), p. 181, para. 9.8; footnote omitted from the quotation; emphasis added.

Imprisonment and rules 1, 41(3), 43(1)(b) and 45, 61, 111(2) of the United Nations Standard Minimum Rules for the Treatment of Prisoners (the “Mandela Rules”).⁶⁰ The petition encircled the reason for Yorov’s detention and highlighted it breached the laid procedures of both national and international law, Article 9 of both the ICCPR and UDHR underlined the abuse as intolerant and against the rights of the individual. The case also demonstrated a clear fact of the state whose responsibility revolves around protecting its citizens, the self-same state acting contrariwise. Also, it much more revealed that Yorov, a lawyer on very high-profile cases, had his rights violated by his own government.

In Cao Hua research thesis entitled: **“Right to Liberty and Pre-trial Detention: A Comparative Study on International Human Rights Standards and Chinese Law and Practice”**, in delineating the significance of the right to liberty, he leaned towards the idea of physical liberty being entrenched into the right of liberty and security of persons. He, however, disputes the fact that freedom of movement is distinguished from Article 9 of the UDHR, or the right to security of persons,. The right to security, on the other hand, is the right to the protection of the law in the exercise of the right to liberty, he added.

This, however, contradicts with other schools that consider liberty, freedom and security as one yet different element. The right to liberty contemplates individual liberty in its classic sense, that is, the physical liberty of the person. Its aim is to ensure that a person is not deprived of his liberty in an arbitrary manner. The right to security, on the other hand, is the right to the protection of the law in the exercise of the right to liberty.

“Liberty and security are the two sides of the same coin.”⁶¹

He considered Nihal Jayawickrama’s work in her book, *“The Judicial Application of Human Rights law, Cambridge 2002,”* pp. 405. Where she addressed the aspect of judicial control as it comes to arbitrary detention and detainees held pending trial, established that in the event of persons held in detention centers the appropriate judicial control ought to be exercised, quoting Article 9(3) of the ICCPR. Mr. Nihal went further to establish the elements of judicial control. First, the judicial control should be prompt.

⁶⁰ Summary Petition to UNWG on Arbitrary Detention in Buzurgmehr Yorov (Citizen of the Republic of Tajikistan) v. Government of the Republic of Tajikistan (“State”) October 22, 2018

⁶¹ J.E.S. Fawcett, *The Application of the European Convention on Human Rights* (Oxford: Charendon Press, 1987), p. 70

Second, it must be automatic. It cannot depend on a previous application by the detained person. Thirdly, the judicial officer must himself or herself hear the detained person before taking the appropriate decision.

In the researcher's view, this augurs well for detainees in that it reduces the attempt of torture or repression under arrest. There have been numerous circumstances where detainees are deprived of their legal entitlements, and rights further violated. The practice and scope of detention whirled around the lawfulness of the act and protects "rights behind bars" in every circumstance.

Nowak, in his commentary work, "**UN Covenant on Civil and Political Rights: CCPR Commentary**" goes further to point out that the term liberty of person provided for in article 9 of ICCPR must not be, however, confused with that of liberty in general. Liberty of person relates only to a very specific aspect of human liberty: the freedom of bodily movement in the narrowest sense. An interference with personal liberty results only from the forceful detention of a person at a certain, narrowly bounded location in the cases enumerated in General Comment 8. All less grievous restrictions on freedom of bodily movement, such as limitations on domicile or residency, exile, or expulsion from State territory do not fall within the scope of the right to personal liberty but instead under freedom of movement.

In the case of *Celepi v Sweden*, the HRC commentary held similar opinion to Novak.⁶² Therefore, drawing from the above, it goes further to show that, also, in as much as Article 9 of the UDHR guarantees freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention, its scope of protection is regulated and defined.

However, in the researcher's view, the article 9 of the UDHR seemed less inclusive as compared with its successor in Article 9 of the ICCPR. Article 9 (1) of ICCPR reads:

"Every one has the right to liberty and security of person. No one shall be subjected to arbitrary arrest and detention. No one shall be deprived of his liberty except on such grounds and in accordance with such procedure as are established by law."

This aptly embraces the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention, this is not to say Article 9 of UDHR became redundant, it is, of course, a parent document to the

⁶² *Celepi v. Sweden* (456/91), CCPR/C/51/D/456/1991, para. 6.1

ICCPR. The UDHR and ICCPR, together with other international human right instruments, further widen the sphere of persons protected by human rights. Article 2(1) of ICCPR and Principle 5 of the *Body of Principles for the Protection of All Persons under Any Form of Detention or Imprisonment* which was adopted by General Assembly resolution 43/173 of 9 December 1988 express that all of their State parties should ensure the rights prescribed in the instruments apply to all persons within the territory of any given State, without distinction of any kind, such as race, color, sex, language, religion or religious belief, political or other opinion, national, ethnic or social origin, property, birth or other status. The documents equally share in responsibility and power to protect the individual similarly. Also, it must be borne in mind that it is not the deprivation of liberty in and of itself that is disapproved of but rather, that which is arbitrary and unlawful.⁶³

The role of international law in the protection of the individual's freedom, thus, can hardly be overemphasized. The right to liberty and security of person, expressed in Article 9 of ICCPR, as well in other international and regional human rights instruments, remains one of the oldest and most fundamental rights. It is to be found in medieval charters, beginning with the Magna Charta Libertatum in 1215.⁶⁴ Prohibition of arbitrary arrest and detention as provided for in those documents mentioned above shares a common history with the more programmatic slogan of the right to liberty.⁶⁵

The purpose of reviewing this commentary is the alignment of both the views expressed in the commentary and that of Nowak's, combining two will further illuminate this aspect of freedom from arbitrary arrest in Article 9 and generally the right to liberty and security of persons, Article 3 of the UDHR.

Massoud Zamani, in an exhaustive research work he titled: “**Detention without Trial: Historical Evolution, International Law, States' Authority.**” examined situations where detainees are kept for longer period without their case being charged to court for hearing, and during these periods of arbitrary detention, are subjected to maltreatment and ill conditions.

⁶³ E/CN.4/234; E/CN.4/SR.96, 9.

⁶⁴ M. Nowak, UN Covenant on Civil and Political Rights: CCPR Commentary, 1993, Strasbourg, p. 159

⁶⁵ G. Alfredsson and A. Eide (eds.), *The Universal Declaration of Human Rights: A Common Standard of Achievement*, p. 209

The study, structured in five (5) chapters, started in its first chapter by examining the history and background of the practice of detention in common law era, titled: “*The Historical Evolution of the Practice of Detention without Trial in the Common Law Tradition*”, using England as his samples state, during the time when licentiousness was punished with detention without trial. He started looking at the seventeenth century, when the arbitrary uses of the prerogative of their rulers then, e.g. Charles I, Charles II and James II; in order to exercise detention without trial started to gain criticism by the Parliament, These criticism then emerged an implicit review of the contours of arbitrary power in the political discourse requiring an articulation of the boundaries of the use of prerogative. It was by the virtue of such boundaries that the scope of deference to liberty or the measures aimed at containing licentiousness would be determined.⁶⁶

Zamani highlighted the two opposing practices in the modern history of England that determined the limits of liberty in a confrontation against licentiousness and these were habeas corpus and detention without trial. The former was tasked to ensure that the subjects’ loss of liberty was undertaken on the basis of reasons standing compliant to the known law of the realm. The latter was, however, a legal vehicle generated by necessity, specifically utilized for “depriving” subjects of their physical liberty. That is to say, when licentiousness was to gain ground, necessity would force authorities to resort to detention without trial for containing the liberty of individuals.

He quoted some wisdom from the valuable scholarship of the legal historian A.W.B. Simpson on detention without trial, identifying the three primary methods for authorizing detention without trial from the eighteenth century onwards. These methods, he established, were the suspension of habeas corpus, martial law, and special regulations.⁶⁷

He continued on to page 25, examining the Magna Carta as regards the unauthorised deprivation of the liberty and freedom of the individual, stating the ultimate value of the Magna Carta was to enforce the idea that “the king was not above the law.”⁶⁸ This

⁶⁶ J. Philip Reid, *The Concept of Liberty in the Age of American Revolution* (Chicago: Chicago University Press, 1988) at 33-36.

⁶⁷ A. W. B. Simpson, *Human Rights and the End of Empire: Britain and the Genesis of the European Convention* (Oxford: OUP, 2001).

⁶⁸ C. Daniell, *From Norman Conquest to Magna Carta: England 1066-1215* (Abingdon: Routledge,

ensured that inasmuch during those times the king possessed seeming absolute powers, they were subject to power checks, which limited or ‘defined’ the scope of their powers.

His work also looked at the emergence of the “Writ of Habeas Corpus”, as regards the freedom of the individual. It sought to explain the importance of the physical liberty of subjects, looking to an important attribute of subjecthood, which existed back then and has been described by Halliday, as:

‘a condition one entered by coming into a particular kind of relationship with the king: his protection.’

However, the protection of the king could only be spread to subjects, if they would in turn commit their bodies to protect the king. The meaning of this formula was that a jailed subject by the arbitrary imprisonment orders of the JPs could not commit his body to protect the king. Thus, it was the king’s need to have an account of the cause of his subjects’ deprivation of liberty that gave rise to the writ of habeas corpus as an instrument by which judges could enquire into the cause of subjects’ detention.⁶⁹

His work, after solidifying the background of the right of freedom to liberty and security and similarly freedom arbitrary arrest and detention, assessed the practice of detention without trial in light of the outcomes of the Second World War.

In the post Second World War era, Zamani submitted, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) became the first major international instrument to include the protection of the right to liberty by putting an emphasis on the importance of physical liberty and the prohibition of arbitrary arrest and detention.⁷⁰ As the human rights regime thrived in the following decades to the adoption of the UDHR, an elaborate body of human rights standards emerged to govern the issues of the right to liberty and its deprivation in the form of detention without trial. Thus, Article 9 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR),⁷¹ Article 5 of the European Convention

2003) at 51.

⁶⁹ P. D. Halliday, *Habeas Corpus: From England to Empire* (Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 2010)

⁷⁰ Universal Declaration of Human Rights, 10 December 1948, 217 A (III), Article 9.

⁷¹ International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, 16 December 1966, United Nations, Treaty Series, vol. 999, p. 171, Article 9.

on Human Rights (ECHR),⁷² Article 7 of the American Convention on Human Rights (ACHR),⁷³ and Article 6 of the African Charter of Human and Peoples' Rights (ACHPR) have in turn encompassed international and regional standards regulating the matter of deprivation of liberty.⁷⁴ Each and every one of these articles is followed by a complex set of principles and interpretive mechanisms developed by the concerned international and regional bodies during the last couple of decades.⁷⁵

He then proceeded to look at under the heading titled: **“The UDHR Detention without Trial.” pg. 107**, which he looked at Article 3, 9, and 10 of the UDHR, and later zeroing in on Article 9 and discussing its literary and formative origin, from its drafting stage and clarifying the word “arbitrary” in context.

Article 3 states that ‘everyone has the right to life, liberty and security of person’. According to **Article 9**, ‘no one shall be subjected to arbitrary arrest, detention or exile’, and **Article 10** posits that ‘everyone is entitled in full equality to a fair and public hearing by an independent and impartial tribunal, in the determination of his rights and obligations and of any criminal charge against him’.

In his exclusive discussion of Article 9 of the UDHR, he examined the *“test of arbitrariness”*, where he quoted Malik, and concluded:

The word ‘arbitrarily’ was not synonymous with ‘illegally’; it had a wider scope. The Commission had wished to use a general term suggesting a criterion above and beyond the laws of States, to which those laws should conform.⁷⁶

After settling on the its test of arbitrariness, he looked the Article 5 of the ECHR document and a case on the, which quoted:

⁷² European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, as amended by Protocols Nos. 11 and 14, 4 November 1950, ETS 5, Article 5.

⁷³ American Convention on Human Rights “Pact of San Jose, Costa Rica” (B-32), 22 January 1969, Article 7.

⁷⁴ African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (“Banjul Charter”), 27 June 1981, 21 I.L.M. 58 (1982), Article 6.

⁷⁵ A. De Zayas, ‘Human Rights and Indefinite Detention’ (2005) 87 International Review of the Red Cross 15.

⁷⁶ J. Morsink, *The Universal Declaration of Human Rights: Origins, Drafting and Intent* (Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press, 1999) at page 356.

“The “lawfulness” of an “arrest or detention” has to be determined in the light not only of domestic law but also of the text of the Convention, the general principles embodied therein and the aim of the restrictions permitted by Article 5 par. 1 (art. 5–1)”⁷⁷

One of the most significant results of putting this restriction upon the detaining authority is that its powers cannot be deemed to be absolute and therefore free from normative legal constraints. This is particularly true with regard to areas where states have historically reserved exclusive rights of sovereignty for themselves, such as the issue of exclusion and expulsion of foreign nationals.⁴⁷ This is an important point, to which we shall return later on in this chapter.⁴⁸

As the years have gone by, the European Court has become more tentative to employ the language of arbitrariness instead of lawfulness in the same mode as used in the ICCPR (infra).⁴⁹ Thus, the Court in 2009 concluded:

The notion of “arbitrariness” in Article 5 &1 extends beyond lack of conformity with national law, so that a deprivation of liberty may be lawful in terms of domestic law but still arbitrary and thus contrary to the Convention.⁷⁸

Even though the above quote is about the ECHR, yet it still applies to the UDHR, as both articles are protecting similar rights.

Here, he then went on to “non-arbitrary and arbitrary Preventive detention”, however the large part of his opinions square on the similar procedure techniques already looked at in previous reviews in this study

One key area he also looked the qualification of arbitrariness, under an heading titled “**Clarifying the Contours of Arbitrariness**” in page **120**, which sought to distinguish or draw the thin lines between arbitrary detention and non-arbitrary preventive detention even though it may seem as if it may be breaching international standards. However, this argument has continued to rage on from research to research, whilst one may argue that it breaches the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention, another may fight to disprove this argument.

⁷⁷ Van Droogenbroeck v. Belgium, Application No. 7906/77, Judgement of 24 June 1982, para 48.

⁷⁸ A and others v. United Kingdom 2009 (Application no. 3455/05) para 164.

In the researcher's view, judging from the compendium of works on the subject, the issue of motive has also been looked into in respect of whether the intention of the detaining authority is that of unjustly detaining the individual or sincerely for the sake of custody or the commencement or continuation of a trial process or just an execution of 'executive order'

He looked at Donald El Hindi's research entitled: "*Guilty Until Proven Innocent: Reports on the Causes of Arbitrary Arrest, Lengthy Pre-trial Detention, and Long Delays in Trial*", on the scope and content of arbitrary detention in international law, established that the law in Article 9 must be "accessible, understandable, non-retroactive, applied in a consistent and predictable way to everyone equally, including authorities, and must be applicable with other law."⁷⁹ While an illegal or unlawful arrest is almost always arbitrary, he continued, an arrest or detention, which is in accordance with the law, might nevertheless be arbitrary if it contains elements of "injustice, unpredictability, unreasonableness, capriciousness and unproportionality." The International Commission of Jurists examines these measures against set standards. He also shed light on the issue of judicial control as regards detention prescribing that the ability to challenge the lawfulness of detention before a court of law is of utmost importance and applies equally to criminal and administrative detentions alike. The right to challenge the legality of detention must be readily available. This, in the researcher, will equally cater for the protection and strengthening of the right enshrined in Article 9 of the UDHR and equally other documents protecting it. What remains then is for the legal systems or jurisdictions to adequately provide an enabling environment where victims of arbitrary detention or arrest can freely seek redress and whatever the outcome thereafter be treated as a respectable person. However, Hindi's research primarily focused on government policies that are unfavorable in administration of justice particularly as it regards delays in trial processes.

He concluded his work by saying no draconian measure exercised by states has gained the attention of legal scholars as much as detention without trial, which equal to detaining arbitrarily. And one of the reasons for this dedication of lawyers to the question of detention without trial is that this practice concerns the most central concept of the legal

⁷⁹ Donald E. Hindi, "*Guilty Until Proven Innocent: Reports on the Causes of Arbitrary Arrest, Lengthy Pre-trial Detention, and Long Delays in Trial*", p. 25

profession, the rule of law and much like the rule of law, no one could pinpoint the precise attributes of it. However, he supposed that procedures should be maintained at all cost, and also instead of saying “unlawful detention”, it is better to say “arbitrary” in its place, as there will be no “law” that ‘arbitrarily’ works against a person in sense. He declaimed on the irony of the test of arbitrariness and took his argument back to respect for the individual’s freedom.

The OHCHR and International Bar Association Journal, *Professional Training Series, No. 9, Human Rights in the Administration of Justice: A Manual on Human Rights for Judges, Prosecutors, and Lawyers*. The objective of the manual was to convey a basic knowledge of, and skills in, the implementation of international human rights law to judges, prosecutors and lawyers – legal professions without which there can be no truly efficient protection of the rights of the individual at the domestic level. The study, in its first chapter, introduced the history of the United Nations Charter and the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) in context of international human rights law, highlighting the sources of law and setting the background of the study. However, the study dedicated precisely Chapter 5 to look at the issue of arbitrary detention its effect to the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and freedom to liberty and security of person, that is, in other words, both Article 3 and 9 of the UDHR.

Chapter 5 provided an analysis of the basic legal rules governing arrest, detention on remand and administrative detention in international human rights law. In so doing, it dealt in some depth with the reasons justifying arrest and continued detention and the right of a person deprived of his or her liberty to challenge the legality of this deprivation of liberty. Emphasis was laid on the jurisprudence of the Human Rights Committee, the Inter-American and European Courts of Human Rights, and the African Commission on Human and Peoples’ Rights ACHPR, which provide interpretations which are indispensable for a full understanding of the meaning of the international legal rules governing arrest and detention.

A very important submission it made was that since it is clear that all human beings have the right to enjoy respect for their liberty and security, there it is axiomatic that, without an efficient guarantee of the liberty and security of the human person, the protection of other individual rights becomes increasingly vulnerable and often illusory. Yet, as is evidenced by the work of the international monitoring organs, arrests and detentions without reasonable cause, and without there being any effective legal remedies available

to the victims concerned, are commonplace. In the course of such arbitrary and unlawful deprivations of liberty, the detainees are frequently also deprived of access both to lawyers and to their own families, and also subjected to torture and other forms of ill treatment. This trend of torture or maltreatment during detention is seen from this study” previous review and happening even in detention centres and prisons in Sierra Leone. The conditions are deplorably bad.

The manual also looked at the situation of state of emergencies in that from the experience of, inter alia, the Working Group on Arbitrary Detention has shown that the main causes of arbitrary detentions are related to states of emergency. However, the question of emergency powers relating to deprivation of liberty was considered primarily in light of ‘executive detention another form of ‘preventive detention’ discussed in previous review of this research. It looked at Article 9(1) of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, article 6 of the African Charter of Human and Peoples’ Rights, article 7(1) of the American Convention on Human Rights and article 5(1) of the European Convention on Human Rights which guarantee a person’s right to “liberty” and “security”. With these in context, it quoted International Court of Justice’s dictum in the Hostages in Tehran case, that “wrongfully to deprive human beings of their freedom and to subject them to physical constraint in conditions of hardship is in itself incompatible with the principles of the Charter of the United Nations, as well as with the fundamental principles enunciated in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights”,⁸⁰ It follows that, notwithstanding that a State may not have ratified or otherwise adhered to any of the preceding human rights treaties, it is nonetheless bound by other legal sources to ensure a person’s right to respect for his or her liberty and security.

Article 3 of the UDHR, which guarantees “the right to life, liberty, and security of person”, offers similar ‘freedom’ protection.

The chapter looked at the deprivations of liberty, but importantly pointed out that, in spite of being linked to the concept of “liberty”, the notion of security of person, as such, it concluded, has a wider field of application. The Human Rights Committee held that Article 9(1) of the Covenant ICCPR “protects the right to security of person also outside the context of formal deprivation of liberty”, and that an interpretation of Article 9

⁸⁰ Case Concerning United States Diplomatic and Consular Staff in Tehran (United States of America v. Iran), ICJ Reports 1980, p. 42, para. 91.

“which would allow a State party to ignore threats to the personal security of non-detained persons subject to its jurisdiction would render totally ineffective the guarantees of the Covenant”. And quoted Article 9(1) of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights reads as follows:

“1. Everyone has the right to liberty and security of person. No one shall be subjected to arbitrary arrest or detention. No one shall be deprived of his liberty except on such grounds and in accordance with such procedure as are established by law.”

Article 6 of the African Charter on Human and Peoples’ Rights provides that:

“Every individual shall have the right to liberty and to the security of his person. No one may be deprived of his freedom except for reasons and conditions previously laid down by law. In particular, no one may be arbitrarily arrested or detained.”

On the notion of arbitrariness As to the principle of legality, the Human Rights Committee has held that “it is violated if an individual is arrested or detained on grounds which are not clearly established in domestic legislation”; in other words, the grounds for arrest and detention must be “established by law”. In a case where a person was arrested without a warrant, which was issued more than three days later, contrary to the domestic law that lays down that a warrant must be issued within 72 hours after arrest, the Committee concluded that article 9(1) had been violated because the author had been “deprived of his liberty in violation of a procedure as established by law”.

With regard to the meaning of the words “arbitrary arrest” in article 9(1), the Committee has explained that “‘arbitrariness’ is not to be equated with ‘against the law’, but must be interpreted more broadly to include elements of inappropriateness, injustice, lack of predictability and due process of law. This means that remand in custody pursuant to lawful arrest must not only be lawful but reasonable in the circumstances. Remand in custody must further be necessary in all the circumstances, for example, to prevent flight, interference with evidence or the recurrence of crime”. In other words, remand in custody pursuant to lawful arrest must not only be “lawful” but also “reasonable” and “necessary” in all the circumstances for the aforementioned purposes. It is for the State party concerned to show that these factors are present in the particular case.

The chapter then also looked at the prohibition of arbitrariness also of course means that deprivations of liberty must not be motivated by discrimination. As further explained in Chapter 13, the States parties to the human rights treaties examined in this Manual undertake to ensure the enjoyment of rights and fundamental freedoms without distinction on such grounds as race, colour, sex, language, religion, and political or other opinion. The African Commission on Human and Peoples' Rights consequently concluded that arrests and detentions carried out by the Rwandan Government "on grounds of ethnic origin alone, constitute arbitrary deprivation of the liberty of an individual"; such acts are thus "clear evidence of a violation of" article 6 of the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights.

The study also considered reasonable motive when trying to determine whether an arrest or detention is arbitrary or not as the European Court has held that the "reasonableness' of the suspicion on which an arrest must be based forms an essential part of the safeguard against arbitrary arrest and detention, which is laid down in" Article 5(1)(c) of the European Convention, and that the fact of "having a 'reasonable suspicion' presupposes the existence of facts or information which would satisfy an objective observer that the person concerned may have committed the offence"; however, what "may be regarded as 'reasonable' will ... depend upon all the circumstances".⁸¹ In conclusion, it contended that the Deprivation of liberty can be justifiable if it is on grounds of educational purpose, mental dysfunction, deportation or extradition yet **Article 9** of the UDHR protects against arbitrary exile yet, preventive for reasons of public, it also support the right to be informed of reason for arrest or detention and ought to be brought promptly before a judge.

From these reviews, a thread of similarity of positions runs across them. That is, their response to the 'arbitrariness' of detention can all be weighed against the scale of disregard for procedure and breaches the individual's right to freedom arbitrary arrest and detention.

⁸¹ Eur. Court HR, Case of Fox, Campbell and Hartley v. the United Kingdom, 30 August 1990, Series A, No. 182, p. 16, para. 32; emphasis added.

Laurent Marcoux, Jr. in his 33-page journal: **“Protection from Arbitrary Arrest and Detention Under International Law.”** touched on the idea of arbitrary arrest and detention, drawing from the background since the adoption of the United Nations Charter in 1945, the international community, in recognition of the vital importance of securing respect for human rights and freedom from fear, has developed an impressive body of international human rights law. Among the most fundamental of all human rights, he asserted, is the right to personal liberty. One significant dimension of this right, he considered, is freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention. In recognition of the right to this freedom, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (Universal Declaration), adopted by the General Assembly of the United Nations in 1948, provides in Article 3 that "everyone has the right to life, liberty and security of person," and in Article 9 that "no one shall be subjected to arbitrary arrest, detention or exile."³ Similarly, Article 9(1) of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (Covenant on Civil and Political Rights) states: "Everyone has the right to liberty and security of person. No one shall be subjected to arbitrary arrest or detention. No one shall be deprived of his liberty except on such grounds and in accordance with such procedure as are established by law." This article attempts to clarify the extent to which international law protects an individual from arbitrary arrest and detention. Codifying mankind's shared aspirations to human dignity in juridical texts is a difficult task. As a consequence, the right to freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention, like much of human rights law is imprecise and vague. Concept clarification, therefore, is needed in order for this aspect of international human rights law to be functionally applicable.

In his 33-page journal, he looked briefly at the history of the concept of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention, this article focuses, through an analysis of legislative history, on the significance of Article 9 of the Universal Declaration and Article 9(1) of the Covenant on Civil and Political Rights. The author demonstrates that both the Universal Declaration and the Covenant on Civil and Political Rights have established a standard of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention which includes and extends beyond protection from "unlawful" arrest or detention; the standard is designed to protect individuals from "arbitrary" laws as well as "unlawful" acts, and is a standard to which the very content of national legal systems must conform. The author, therefore, suggests the scope of the standard imposed by the two instruments through an examination of the

various criteria that give some content to the standard. In conclusion, the author proposes a methodology for dealing with specific cases by which tribunals and organizations concerned with human rights can determine whether an individual has been arbitrarily arrested or detained by a state. The methodology, he continued, also provides guidelines for the drafting of legislation and regulations involving the right to personal liberty. The approach is designed to maximize protection of an individual's personal freedom under international law.

Dating back, he delved into the concept of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention appeared in several early European documents, such as the Magna Carta, the Habeas Corpus Acts of England, and the French Declaration of the Rights of Man and the Citizen. These texts provided the first definitions of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention, and form the foundation upon which the Universal Declaration and the Covenant on Civil and Political Rights rest. Article 39 of the Magna Carta states:

*No Freeman shall be taken or imprisoned, or be disseised of his Freehold, or Liberties, or free Customs, or be outlawed, or exiled, or any otherwise destroyed; nor will we not pass upon him nor condemn him, but by lawful Judgment of his Peers, or by the Law of the Land.*⁸²

He concluded his work by restating his premise, that if the states continue with their policy of non-adherence to international human rights law, under the veil of sovereignty and domestic procedures, the rights of the individual is insecure.

Douglass Cassel (2009), in his legal studies research paper on international human rights law strictly in context of security detention, titled: *“International Human Rights Law and Security Detention.”* opened with this quote:

If so-called preventive detention is used, for reasons of public security, ...it must not be arbitrary, and must be based on grounds and procedures established by law.... information of the reasons must be given... and court control of the detention must be available ... as well as compensation in the case of a breach.”⁸³

⁸² Magna Carta, I Statutes of the Realm 6-7 (1810).

⁸³ U.N. Human Rights Committee, *General Comment No. 8: Right to Liberty and Security of Persons*, 4,

The purpose of his study was to analyse the grounds, procedures, and conditions required by International Human Rights Law for preventive detention of suspected terrorists as threats to security. Such detentions generally permitted, provided it is based on grounds and procedures previously established by law; is not arbitrary, discriminatory, or disproportionate; is publicly registered and subject to fair and effective judicial review; and the detainee is not mistreated and is compensated for any unlawful detention. In Europe, however, preventive detention for security purposes is generally not permitted. If allowed at all, it is permitted only when a State in time of national emergency formally derogates from the right to liberty under the European Convention on Human Rights. The article concludes that if preventive detention for security purposes is to be allowed at all, its use must be kept to an absolute minimum, and the European model should be followed, allowing detention only by formal derogation during national emergency, and then only to the extent and for the time strictly required.

We shall proceed to review an important article, uncovering the multi-faceted aspects of abuses and violations that the right to freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention maybe subjected to.

Also, an article by the Canadian Department of Justices, analyzing “**Article 9 of the Canadian Charter of Rights and Freedoms**”⁸⁴ is worth reviewing. It examined the practice of arbitrary detention under its many guises, making it extremely useful to contribute to the richness and depth of this research. Similarly, as with Article 9 of the UDHR, Section 9 of the CCRF also provided thus:

“9. Everyone has the right not to be arbitrarily detained or imprisoned.”

The analysis opened with recognizing the significance of arbitrary detention, Article 9 of the UDHR, and cited conventions and statutes protecting it the world over. Some of these include: s2 (a) of the Canadian Bill of Rights, article 9(1) of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights; article 37(b) of the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child; and article XXV of the American Declaration of the Rights and Duties of Man (art. XXV), articles 7(2) and 7(3) of the American Convention on Human Rights; article 5 of the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms etc. It sought to delineate the scope of protection of Section 9 by

U.N. Doc. HRI/GEN/I/Rev.7 (June 30, 1982) [hereinafter HRC GC 8].

⁸⁴ <https://www.justice.gc.ca/eng/csjsjc/rfc-dlc/ccrf-ccd1/check/art9.html>

submitting that a person's right to liberty is easily intertwined with his right to freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention, which are the principles of fundamental justice. Therefore, their Section 9 served to protect individual liberty against unlawful state interference.⁸⁵

In their analysis, they recognized that the protection offered in these legal instruments might be raised to challenge the reasons for detention, the procedures, which result in detention being ordered, and the character and nature of the detention. And it went to contest that during arbitrary detention, not only the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention is breached, but also the individual's right to liberty, freedom of movement, and freedom from torture and inhuman treatment. Thus, this cascading effect of arbitrary arrest or detention was the main thrust of their analysis.

Therefore, Article 3 of the UDHR is summoned when Article 9 is breached. This argument was supported by two (2) cases where the rights of liberty and security are deemed as intertwined with the individual's freedom from arbitrary arrest.⁸⁶

The analysis discussed the issue of "burden of proof" as it comes to arbitrary detention in which it said that the individual who has been detained borne the burden of proving that he or she was arbitrarily detained or imprisoned. Then, the analytical framework for determining whether the law may apply will involve two (2) questions:

1) Was the individual 'detained' or 'imprisoned'?

2) Was that detention or imprisonment 'arbitrary'?⁸⁷

These two (2) questions have opened our enquiry into a broader aspect of delimiting the scope and practice of arbitrary arrest and detention. The analysis exceptionally detailed that circumstances under which it may be concluded that the individual was indeed arbitrarily detained.

Examining the first question: "*Was the individual "detained" or "imprisoned"?*", the analysis submitted that detention should require some form of physical or psychological

⁸⁵ R. v. Grant, [2009] 2 S.C.R. 353 at para 54.

⁸⁶ R. v Swain, [1991] 1 S.C.R. 933 at 1008-1013.

⁸⁷ R. v Hufsky, [1988] 1 S.C.R. 621 at paragraphs 12-13.

restraint by the state. It therefore ought to be “a suspension of the individual’s liberty by a significant physical or psychological restraint”.⁸⁸

He examined also ‘Psychological Detention’, another guile under which arbitrary detention may take place. This, it said, occurs where the subject is legally required to comply with a direction or demand or where, in the absence of such a direction, state conduct would lead a reasonable person to conclude that he or she had no choice but to comply.⁸⁹ In cases, however, it concluded, where there is no physical restraint or legal obligation to comply, determining whether a person has been detained may be more challenging. Therefore, it offered that to determine whether the reasonable person in the individual’s circumstances would conclude that he or she had been deprived by the state of the liberty of choice, the court might have to consider certain factors:

(a) The circumstances giving rise to the encounter as they would reasonably be perceived by the individual: whether the police were providing general assistance; maintaining general order; making general inquiries regarding a particular occurrence; or, singling out the individual for focussed investigation;

(b) The nature of the police conduct, including the language used; the use of physical contact; the place where the interaction occurred; the presence of others; and the duration of the encounter; and

(c) The particular characteristics or circumstances of the individual where relevant, including age; physical stature; minority status; level of sophistication.⁹⁰

The above analysis involved an objective determination, made in light of the circumstances of the encounter as a whole. Strikingly, the analysis went to caution that not every interaction between a police officer and a member of the public is a detention. The police cannot be said to “detain” an individual when stopped for purposes of identification, or even interview. The person who is stopped will in all cases be “detained” in the sense of “delayed”, or “kept waiting”. But the constitutional sense of the law is not engaged by delays that involve no significant physical or psychological restraint.⁹¹

⁸⁸ R. v. Grant, [2009] 2 S.C.R. 353 at para 44.

⁸⁹ Ibid, para 30-31, 44

⁹⁰ ibid para 44.

⁹¹ R. v. Mann, [2004] 3 S.C.R. 59 at para 19, cited in R. v. Suberu, [2009] 2 S.C.R. 460 at para 23.

Therefore, an investigative detention, as it termed it, does not necessarily arise the moment police engage an individual for investigative purposes or ask preliminary questions. Thus, if we apply the objective test set out in Grant’s case to determine whether the individual has been psychologically detained, the perspective of the reasonable person must be informed by the fact that a bystander is under no legal obligation to comply with a police request for information or assistance. The onus is on the applicant to demonstrate deprivation of liberty in the circumstances.⁹² So, a driver, for example, is not detained for the purposes of their Charter when he or she is statutorily required to remain at the scene of an accident, technically speaking.

It then looked into the second question, which happened to be: “*Was the detention or imprisonment ‘arbitrary’?*” Arbitrariness, it claimed, can arise either from the law itself or from the conduct of officials. In the analysis, it submitted that an unlawful detention that is not authorized by statute or common law is always arbitrary and unjustifiably limits the operation of law. In other words, a lawful detention is not arbitrary within the meaning of law, “unless the law authorizing the detention is itself arbitrary”.⁹³

It also showed that a law authorizing automatic and indeterminate detention without any standards is arbitrary. So also, a law compelling the automatic detention of individuals on the basis of the danger they present to society will be arbitrary if there are no criteria or standards in place to determine if they are in fact dangerous. Considering discretion, it looked at an aspect of law that authorised the random stopping of motor vehicles can be found to be arbitrary if it gave police officers an “absolute discretion” in the selection of which drivers to stop, quoting “A discretion is arbitrary if there are no criteria, express or implied, which govern its exercise.”⁹⁴ Detention undertaken for improper motives may taken to be arbitrary.

It also examined that the length or duration of the detention following arrest but prior to charge or appearance before a justice, if unreasonable on the facts, will render a detention arbitrary.⁹⁵ It also noted that an initial arbitrary detention does not render subsequent lawful detentions arbitrary. An arbitrary detention (i.e., detention that is not authorized by law or not Charter-compliant) will end once the police have a reasonable suspicion

⁹² R v Suberu para 22, 28

⁹³ R v Grant para. 54

⁹⁴ R. v Hufsky, [1988] 1 S.C.R. 621 at paragraphs 13.

⁹⁵ R. v. Storrey, [1990] 1 S.C.R. 241 at 251-25

that an individual may have committed an offence.⁹⁶ Even if the police initially trespassed in entering onto a property, this does not affect the lawfulness of a subsequent detention as long as that detention was supported by reasonable suspicion. However, this is a context-specific assessment, which could yield a different outcome if the police trespassed for the purpose of detaining the appellant or if it could be shown that the improper entry onto the property somehow interfered with the appellant's personal rights or liberty.

In summary, the analysis examined the nuances that may qualify a situation of detention as lawful, unlawful or arbitrary. It further examined the conditionals, both existing and supposing scenarios, to clarify the scope of detention. From considering arbitrary detention in light of psychological, investigative, and discretionary detention it thus opened up our enquiry to the other guises of arbitrary detention

An article by Lawyer Alimamy Sultan Koroma Esq. titled: “**Clarifying The Law Relating to the Detention of Suspects in Police Custody — What Everyone Needs to Know**”, the learned barrister made a case of Sierra Leone and the practice of arbitrary detention in the country. In other words, he shed light on the infringement of the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention of the individual in Sierra Leone.

In his introductory paragraph, he contested that one of the most pervasive forms of human rights violations in the country through out his practice in the Criminal Justice system is the “arbitrary arrest and detention of suspects by police officers. What particularly stood out, according to his article, is how ingrained and ‘normalized’ the practice had been that now people in the country had accepted it as norm. His assertion goes to corroborate the JSDP Annual Reports published indicating that detention centers in Sierra Leone are often overcrowded, and a huge chunk of these detentions are prolonged, baseless, and unjustifiable, hence arbitrary. And these detentions are often for minor offenses.

In his article, he cited a recent study, which indicated that more than half of all suspects invited to the police station end up being detained. This practice seemed to have gone unchecked, prompting an enquiry from the author:

(a) What does the law say regarding the detention of suspects?

⁹⁶ R. v. Rowson, 2015 ABCA 354 at paragraph 22 affirmed 2016 SCC 40).

(b) Do Police Officers have a carte blanche authority to lock up suspects?

(c) What are the effects of arbitrarily depriving a suspect of his liberty?

As mentioned in previous reviews, the greatest enemies of the rights of the individual more often than not turn out to be their ruling governments and state authorities that trample on their rights unchecked, with little or no chance to seek redress. Often, this has been ascribed to a weakened infrastructural system when it comes to dispensing justice at detention level, because the courts most times exercise their authorities according to law, and these law in Sierra Leone comprise of:

‘any orders, rules, regulations and other statutory instruments made by any person or authority pursuant to a power conferred in that behalf by this Constitution or any other law; [and this include Article 9 of the UDHR, and Article 9 of the ICCPR]’

The author, being a barrister at law, was urged to recount a scenario, a matter of some sort he had dealt with in the past regarding arbitrary detention of suspects. From his account, the victim had already been detained for more than 48 hours, four (4) days to be precise. He then approached the Station Head at the time, who was urged to release the suspect who had already been arbitrarily detained on a bogus and very weak case, cited no reason for his detention but instead sought to consult the complainant rather than his law books not even know he’s acting against the law despite being a police officer. The author, as he recounted, was stunned at the apparent lack of any justifiable basis for his client’s detention. The Officer’s chief concern was to consult the complainant, and no actual basis such as fear of interference with witnesses, flight risk or unreliable sureties.

What was striking in the author’s account was that even when he tried explaining to the office-in-charge of **Section 17** of the 1991 Sierra Leone constitution, which protects the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention, the officer proved utterly disinterested. This culminated into altercation, which eventually led to his client’s release. And most appalling, it later turned out that the investigation was later discontinued for an apparent lack of sufficient evidence. And his client was further not even compensated.

From this, we have witnessed the blatant infringement of the rights of the individual as guaranteed under the laws of Sierra Leone, **Section 17** and **Section 17 (4)** of the **1991**

Constitution.

In his third paragraph, the article examined the law in context of arbitrary detention in Sierra Leone. He quoted **Section 17** of the 1991 Constitution and **Section 80** of the Criminal Procedure Act, **1965** as the extant legal provisions dealing with detention of suspects in police custody. Both acts, he further submitted, clearly frown at unnecessary and unreasonable detention of suspects. The acts recommend detention of suspects at police station only as a last resort and in exceptional cases such as for felonies.

In context, he highlighted international legal treatises, which Sierra Leone is a signatory and its obligatory adherence to these treaties. He quoted **Article 6** of the African Charter on Human and Peoples Rights and **Article 9** of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. However, he did not include Article 9 of the UDHR, which, is actually binding as per force member states. Nevertheless, it clearly brought home the idea of arbitrary detention and the pervasiveness of the practice in the country.

He further explained that even though the law also recognizes that in certain situations, Police Officers while investigating a crime, may need to keep the suspects in custody, for example where there is likelihood that the suspect would escape or may interfere with prosecution witnesses. This power to detain, he admonished, is however subject to strict conditions including constitutional limits on the period of detention, which is 3 days for misdemeanors and 10 days for capital offenses. At the expiration of this period the police ‘must’ either charge the matter to court or release the suspect on bail. In practice however, he concluded, police officers often lock up suspects longer than the constitutional limit and by so doing, violate the rights and dignity of these suspects.

In wrapping his article, he made recommendations to improve the respect for and protection of the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention. Going forward, he disqualified the novelty of his client’s situation, purporting that it is now part of a worrying culture by some rogue police officers that abuse the power of detention as a tool for extortion, punishment or securing forced confessions. He cited a discussion paper entitled “*Justice Sector and the Rule of Law*”, published in January 2014, OSIWA noted that:

“Frequent reports of physical abuse, illegally assessed fees and unlawful detention continue to undermine the SLP’s credibility.”

In order to tackle this menace and strengthen respect for protection from arbitrary arrest

and detention as laid down by the law, he proposed, the following recommendations should be adopted: First, he urged that government and non-governmental organizations must as a matter of urgency intensify trainings for police investigators on human rights law, especially the principles relating to pretrial detention. Listing OSIWA, ADVOCIAD and LEWAF as willing to help in this direction.

Second, he submitted for the Criminal Procedure Act 1965 to be reviewed to reflect international human rights best practices. For example, subject to few exceptions bail, he wrote, must be made mandatory for all minor offences such as assault, public disorder and insulting conduct. The new act, he advocated, must spell out clearly that bail can only be refused for minor offences in exceptional circumstances and that order must come from the Inspector General of Police under a certificate issued in his name.

Furthermore, he encouraged that the Sierra Leone Police should have a police officer with a legal background at each police station that should determine the issue of bail and every decision to deny bail must be in writing and subject to review after every 24 hours. And finally called on civil society organizations and the general public to be encouraged to speak out against arbitrary arrest and detention, as this study presently preaches. He further urged members of the public to utilize the disciplinary mechanism within the police namely the Complaint Discipline and Internal Investigation Department (CDIID) and the Independent Police Complaint Board so as to end impunity. The Police Discipline Regulations of 2001, he hinted, presents the opportunity to promote accountability and discipline within the police force and the public ought to make use of same to ensure dignity of suspects. The author's plea was self-explanatory, i.e., in a bid to discourage arbitrary arrests and detention, he pushed for the adherence to both national and international legislation during arrests and detention so that the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention is protected and guaranteed

We shall then proceed to review a very significant yet comprehensive report by the OHCHR in together with UNIPSIL, titled: **“Report on the Situation of Detention in Sierra Leone: Behind Bars.”**

The report was structured into 5 chapters — the first chapter introducing their study on the practice of detention, followed by the second chapter, which looked at both national and institutional framework, and the third chapter, which was the meat of the research, examined the practice of detention in Sierra Leone, entitled **“Analysis: The Situation of**

Detention in Sierra Leone.”, where it looked at four (4) components — (a) material, logistical and infrastructural situation (b) conditions of detention (c) Administration of Justice and Protective Measures (d) Effectiveness of International Co-operation. Then the fourth chapter examined the correctional centers ensuring the human rights of convicts and detainees are protected, and its final chapter made recommendations to improve the situation of detention, by extension the protection and promotion of human rights in Sierra Leone. The 57-page report’s main object is the assessment of detention facilities in Sierra Leone in order to identify areas where improvement may be needed. These ranged from advocacy, human rights, decision-making in correction systems and the administration of justice. The also reviews the legal frameworks of Sierra Leone in light of international standards and the country’s obligation, providing an overall assessment of state infrastructure and systems. It looked at the national framework i.e. Section 17, and institutional framework in the correctional service center, which primary focus was given to the condition of the detention facilities, safety, sanitation and space.

One significant fact that the report uncovered was that the country’s national legal framework on detention dates back to colonial era and alignment with international standards had been really slow. This is seen in the challenges encountered in the administration of justice. And went to make recommendations at the onset of the report to the government, prison-service, police officers, and the judiciary.

The report relevantly looked at the: *“Legal Status and Situations of Persons under Detention without Sentence”* at page 32. 3.3.2. It vouched that the right to liberty and security of person is an overriding right in that no one ought to be arbitrarily deprived of his liberty in any circumstance whatsoever. Section 17 has domesticated principles from Article 9 of the ICCPR, it went on to state that the country ‘legal framework is weakened by its non-adherence to international standards and detainees in police custody have on several occasions been refused bail and kept for longer hours in detention

The report quoted Pamela Dale’s (2008) review, as a sub-review, on the situation of justice in Sierra Leone, titled: *“Access to Justice in Sierra Leone: A Review of the Literature”*. A literature, which exclusively focused on the equality of access to justice by each and every citizen in Sierra Leone and how situation of equity can be improved. A portion of her main thrust is reviewed in light of identifying the infrastructural gap in the administration of justice. For the purpose of our study, this ‘access to justice’ primarily revolves around prison and detention centers in the country, exposing the pervasiveness

of violation of the citizen's freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention. Her concern was the decentralization of justice to local levels, making it accessible. However, it primarily concerned the access to justice through decentralizing its access to provinces and local towns, however, the purpose the document served to our research is the gap of highlighted, which goes to show that the poor administration of justice is largely owed to an infrastructural lack. The purpose of her paper sought to establish a baseline level of knowledge on the current state of local level justice institutions and access to justice in Sierra Leone's provinces. It entailed a review of what is known and the gaps in the knowledge base, coupled with an analysis of recent events, possible entry points, and opportunities for intervention. ——— to identify practical solutions to problems of inaccess and inequitable access to justice.

It concluded its reports by making recommendations that will help improve the situation of detention in Sierra Leone, primarily focusing on adherence to the international legal framework and the country's obligations.

Prisoners all treated equally.

It reported also that majority of the inmates in Sierra Leone are not serving a sentence. As of March 2012, 57.5% of the prisoners were either on remand (26.2%), or on trial (31.3%), only 42.5% of those in prison were convicted:

From this, the study submitted, that the procedures employed by prison authorities as regards arrest and detention ought to be reviewed, revised and improved. In as much as, this area is primarily focused on the prison system as to what goes on in the prisoner's dome, yet, these data suffice to show how the issues of arrest and detention are treated lightly and it went to show that over a period of 5 years convicted prisoners have remained below 50% of the total number of inmates. Interestingly, however, the situation changed in that the number of those on remand decreased from 41%(892 prisoners) to 21% (588 prisoners) in 2012 In 2008, those on trial were only 14% (310 prisoners) of the total number and increased to 31% in 2012.

This data is presented in the chart graph below:

From this, the report concluded that despite the initial abysmal situation that existed, the country is set up for improvements in many areas, which over the course of time possess the possibility of changes and fixes.

We shall proceed to review our final journal by Global Campaign for Pretrial Justice: **“Pre-trial Detention and Torture: Why Pre-trial Detainees Face the Greatest Risk”**, published by the Open Society Foundations. The study basically centered on the effect of arbitrary detention that is from longer periods in custody,

maltreatment, inadequate facilities, torture, bribery poor conditions of detention centers. The study cited countries like Nigeria, Equatorial Guinea where these practices are prevalent. It goes to show that people often considered these detention centers and what happened behind those bars as secrets and little or nothing is known about them,

The study proposed the excessive and arbitrary pre-trial detention remains one of the most overlooked form of human rights abuse that affects millions of persons each year, grossly undermining the rule of law. Pre-trial detainees, it offered, undergo numerous constraints unnoticed, that is from losing their jobs and homes; contracting and spreading disease; be asked to pay bribes to secure release or better conditions of detention; and suffer physical and psychological damage that last long after their detention ends.

It called out to human rights campaigns, NGOs, practitioners, researchers and policy makers; to pilot innovative practices and methodologies aimed at finding effective, low-cost ways of carrying out detention and arrest especially as it related to individuals whose reason for detention was not given.

In its Chapter 3 & 4, it examined and delved into to ill treatment that goes on in these detention centres and asserted that torture and other ill-treatment are prohibited under international law and the right is non-derogable. Therefore, no one ought to be subjected to torture and other ill treatment under any circumstance, including during times of war or public emergency. The prohibition of torture and other ill-treatment is a rule of customary law: it is regarded as so absolute and universally accepted that even states which have not ratified any of the international treaties that explicitly prohibit torture and other ill-treatment are banned from using it against anyone, anywhere, at any time. It went further to state that the prohibition of torture is considered to be a peremptory norm of international law, which meant that all states are bound by this prohibition and may not withdraw from this obligation under any circumstance; their obligation to prohibit torture cannot be modified in any way, including by treaty, national law or custom, and no excuse, such as a threat to national security or a state of emergency, can be invoked to justify its use.

Also, the study looked at international instrument protecting against torture anywhere, to anyone, including the UN Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR), the UN Convention against Torture (UNCAT), the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child, the Geneva Conventions and

Additional Protocols, the African Charter for Human and Peoples' Rights, the American Convention on Human Rights, and the European Convention on Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms.

It defined torture, according to Article 1 of the UN Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment (UNCAT) as *“any act by which severe pain or suffering, whether physical or mental, is intentionally inflicted on a person for such purposes as obtaining from him or a third person information or a confession, punishing him for an act he or a third person has committed or is suspected of having committed, or intimidating or coercing him or a third person, or for any reason based on discrimination of any kind, when such pain or suffering is inflicted by or at the instigation of or with the consent or acquiescence of a public official or other person acting in an official capacity”*.

Concluding its **Chapter 4**, it noted other rights protected under binding international law for people who have been detained and charged with a criminal offense, including: The right not to be subjected to arbitrary detention, the right to be presumed innocent, The right to be informed of the reasons for the arrest , The right to be informed promptly of any charges , The right to not be compelled to confess guilt or testify against themselves , The right to challenge the lawfulness of the detention , The right to be brought promptly before a judge and the right to legal assistance.⁹⁷

The issue of prolonged and lengthy detention, which may amount to arbitrary arrest and detention, was also looked at. It estimated that conditions in police custody are particularly problematic when suspects are held for long periods of time. It suggested that suspects should only be held in police facilities only until the first judicial review of detention, which should take place within a maximum of 48 hours after arrest. However, this, as we have learnt from previous review, is not the case in many countries. One of the effect the study cited as a result of prolonged detention for months and years is the issue of overcrowding in police cells, which are often already severely under-resourced and do not meet the requirements for short-term (let alone long-term) detention. Due to this lack of space, it continued, detainees are sometimes forced to sleep in shifts or on a concrete floor in police cells that lack sufficient light and ventilation. And the study

1.⁹⁷ ICCPR, Arts. 9 and 14.

looked at other issues like access to sanitary facilities which is often restricted or completely absent, leading to critical hygiene conditions and the most basic amenities such as food, water, and medical care are frequently limited.

The situation in Sierra Leone is detainees are entirely dependent for such necessities on their families or fellow detainees. This denial of basic amenities may force detainees who lack outside support into slave-like dependency. Also, withholding medical treatment, officials can put detainees' lives at risk. And it is clear that these practices are against the *ACHPR'S Guideline Report on the Conditions of Arrest and Pre-trial Detention in Africa*, adopted 8 May 2014, which guaranteed regulations strictly regarding arrest, police custody, pre-trial detention, registers, procedures for serious violations of human rights in police custody, and lastly pre-trial detention and conditions of detention in police custody and pre-trial detention.

In its final chapter the study recommended that one of the most effective ways to prevent torture is through early access to legal aid, combined with a system of regular, unannounced visits to places of detention. Yet, of all formal detention facilities, pre-trial detention centres and police stations are typically the most difficult to gain access to, and information on people held in pre-trial detention is often limited or non-existent. In many cases, authorities do not make public data about their pre-trial detention populations, and in other cases authorities fail to accurately track pre-trial detainees. This lack of transparency perpetuates the problem of torture, which continues to occur with impunity in many states throughout the world. As former Special Rapporteur on Torture Sir Nigel Rodney put it:

“There needs to be a radical transformation of assumptions in international society about the nature of deprivation of liberty. The basic paradigm, taken for granted over at least a century, is that prisons, police stations and the like are closed and secret places, with activities inside hidden from public view. The international standards referred to are conceived of as often-unwelcome exceptions to the general norm of opacity, merely the occasional ray of light piercing the pervasive darkness. What is needed is to replace the paradigm of opacity by one of transparency. The assumption should be one of open access to all places of deprivation of liberty. Of course, there will have to be regulations to safeguard the security

of the institution and individuals within it, and measures to safeguard their privacy and dignity. But those regulations and measures will be the exception, having to be justified as such; the rule will be openness.”⁹⁸

The study then recommended the for state authorities to reduce the excessive and arbitrary use of pre-trial detention, put the prevention of torture and other ill-treatment into practice, invest in creating professional law enforcement services and engage with the legal and health professions.

2.6 SECTION 17: THE NATIONAL LEGAL FRAMEWORK

“Around the world, people are far more apt to be harmed by their own than by other governments. Harm results from numerous forms of misgovernment– political and military repression, graft, judicial corruption, economic discrimination against minorities and so on. Such behavior clearly offends against the norm of sovereignty. The norms nevertheless protects abusive governments and corrupt elites, who can appeal to sovereignty and insist on non-interference in their internal affairs whenever they face international pressure to reform. For this reason, some have called sovereignty a “refuge for scoundrels”.⁹⁹ (Donald Rothchild)

In Sierra Leone, the 1991 Constitution is the legal framework that is largely responsible for both legal and constitutional issues in the country. It internally regulates the operation, exercise and enjoyment of powers, rights and privileges nationally. It creates and disposes, empowers and strips, but it is there to govern and protect every citizen towards promotion of national development. In its Chapter 3, it confers as per right, the fundamental freedoms every citizen is entitled and further makes and obligation to protect these rights from breach or infringement and secure the citizen in the exercise of

⁹⁸ A/56/156, para 35.

⁹⁹ Donald Rothchild, “Responding to Africa’s Post-Cold War Conflicts,” in Edmond Keller and Donald Rothchild, eds., *Africa in the New International Order: Rethinking State Sovereignty and Regional Security* (Boulder: Lynne Rienner Publishers, 1996),231, quoted in International Council on Human Rights Policy, *Duties Sans Frontiers: Human Rights and Global Social Justice* (Geneva, 2003), 48.

these rights. Particularly, Section (17) gives the citizen the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention:

“17. (1) No person shall be deprived of his personal liberty except as may be authorized by law...”¹⁰⁰

The section goes further to provide exceptional circumstances where such liberty may be taken away, that is in the case of fulfilling a certain court order in respect of a criminal charge, executive order, suspicion; also for health reasons or extradition. These circumstances however do not add to the sum of acts that an individual may commit against the law for which he would be arrested. In any case, however, the law provides that any such person being arrested or detained must be informed or at least have an inkling of the reason for his arrest or detention of right, and immediately informed of his right of access to a lawyer.

The national framework also caters for not more than 72 hours or (10) ten days for the detention of an individual before bringing him to court. And goes further to provide that, if such is not the case, he shall thus be released unconditionally or conditionally such as showing up for later trials. And provides for compensation to any person whose detention is later proved to be unlawful, and such compensation must come from the other person. Critically observing the enactment, it becomes apparent the wording of the section and its exemptions are aimed at protecting citizens from being arbitrarily or unjustly detained and ensures that only if and when the exceptional cases occur before such persons are detained.

In 2015, the Campaign for Human Rights and Development Sierra Leone (CHRDSL) publicly in a statement called out the attention of the government of Sierra Leone to the continued unlawful, arbitrary and unjustifiable detention of over 78 innocent citizens by law enforcement officers. They went further to express that these citizens were arbitrarily arrested and have been detained unlawfully for over 84 months now without charges and have only attended trial once since 2007. The unlawful detention of these citizens is violating their human dignity and destroying their lives. To detain citizens without charge

¹⁰⁰ Sierra Leone’s 1991 Constitution, Chapter III, Section 17

and with no regard for due process is in clear violation of the laws of Sierra Leone and international Human Rights Law.¹⁰¹

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights states that no one may be subjected to arbitrary arrest, detention or imprisonment. All defendants have the rights to fair trial. In Sierra Leone today people are held without due process and prisoners are convicted in unfair trials.

In Sierra Leone one of the most pervasive forms of human rights violations have observed is the arbitrary arrest and detention of suspects by police officers. This arbitrary detention of suspects for even minor offenses has become so engrained and commonplace that most people have come to accept it as the norm. According to a recent study, more than half of all suspects invited to the police station end up being detained.¹⁰²

Section 17 of the Constitution of Sierra Leone 1991 and section 80 of the Criminal Procedure Act, 1965 are the extant legal provisions dealing with detention of suspects in police custody. Both acts clearly frown at unnecessary and unreasonable detention of suspects. The said acts recommend detention of suspects at police station only as a last resort and in exceptional cases such as for felonies. This is the same approach of international legal treaties to which Sierra Leone is a signatory as evidenced in Article 6 of the African Charter on Human and Peoples Rights and Article 9 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights.¹⁰³

However, in the researcher's view, persons in authority ought to know what does the law say regarding the detention of suspects, and even staffs of police should stop thinking that police officers have a carte blanche authority to lock up suspects, ignoring the effects of arbitrarily depriving a suspect of his liberty. It not doubted or disproved that the law also recognizes that in certain situations, police officers while investigating a crime, may need to keep the suspects in custody. This can be especially so where there is likelihood that the suspect would escape or may interfere with prosecution witnesses. This power to detain is however subject to strict conditions including constitutional limits on the period of detention, that is, 3 days for misdemeanors and 10 days for capital offenses as provided for in sub-section 3 of Section 17 of the 1991. At the expiration of this period

¹⁰¹ This statement was first published by CHRDSL on the 5th November 2015 <https://www.thesierraleonetelegraph.com/campaign-group-for-the-protection-of-human-rights-in-sierra-leone-speaks-out>

¹⁰² Alimamy Sultan Koroma Esq.: Clarifying the Law Relating to Detention of Suspects in Police Custody

¹⁰³ Article 9 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights

the police must either charge the matter to court or release the suspect on bail.

In practice however, police officers often lock up suspects longer than the constitutional limit and by so doing, violate the rights and dignity of these suspects.¹⁰⁴

The constitution and law prohibit arbitrary arrest and detention; however, government forces occasionally arrested and detained persons arbitrarily. Even though there is legislative provision for this, police corruption was a serious problem, in part exacerbated by low salaries. Some police and guards reportedly stole from detainees. There were continued reports that police officers required bribes at checkpoints, falsely charged motorists with violations, and impounded vehicles to extort money. Police also accepted bribes from criminal suspects in exchange for dropping charges or for having their rivals arrested and charged with crimes. In numerous instances, police, in exchange for kickbacks, refused to make arrests when warranted, or they arrested persons without charge for civil causes such as alleged breach of contract or failure to satisfy a debt.¹⁰⁵

According to the JSDP, impunity was less of a problem than in the past. The Police Complaints, Discipline, and Internal Investigations Department (CDIID) heard more complaints against police officers during the year than in the previous year, largely due to greater public awareness of and trust in the organization. There was also Police Council, which included the vice president, minister of internal affairs, inspector general, and others who accepted written complaints against senior police officers. The CDIID facilitated all hearings and trials related to complaints against junior police officers. An appeals process was available and used often. After the CDIID issued disciplinary measures against an SLP officer, the officer was also subject to the civilian court if criminal action was involved. An infrequently published SLP newsletter listed disciplinary actions against officers.¹⁰⁶

During the year the CDIID received 1,623 complaints countrywide, resulting in 689 officers being dismissed, demoted, suspended, or officially warned. Of the remainder, 408 cases were dismissed for lack of evidence or validity, 282 were resolved through dispute resolution, and 244 remained at various stages of investigation or review. The

¹⁰⁴ Report on the Situation of Detention, UNIPSIL, UN Office of the High Commissioner

¹⁰⁵ Interview with James M. S. Brima, Human Right and Civil Society Activist.

¹⁰⁶ 2007 Report Justice Sector Development Programme: “Justice Sector Reform Strategy and Investment Plan I which sets out “a platform for a coherent, prioritized, and sequenced set of activities to reform the operations of the justice system in Sierra Leone.”

most common complaints lodged against police were corruption, unfair treatment, lack of professionalism, and assault. Cases requiring dismissal of an officer most commonly involved criminal cases, such as officers fraudulently posing as landowners or businessmen to extort money. Police continued to receive professional, leadership, and human rights training, and new recruits received a six-month introductory course before deployment. The SLP retained a full-time UN technical advisor and a number of UN Civilian Police advisors. As a result of training programs during the year and the introduction of community policing conducted by the Department for International Development, the Commonwealth, and the JSDP, the professional conduct of the police force improved. However, its efficacy continued to be hampered by limited financial resources.¹⁰⁷

Many legal instruments, whether national or international, define the deprivation of liberty in various ways. The most commonly used terms are: arrest, detention, incarceration, prison, custody, etc. It is for these reasons that the United Nations Commission on Human Rights coined the term ‘deprivation of liberty’. This concept was chosen since it “relates to the protection of individuals against arbitrary deprivation of freedom in all its forms, and its mandate extends to deprivation of freedom either before, during or after the trial, as well as deprivation of freedom in the absence of any kind of trial (administrative detention).”¹⁰⁸

Arbitrary detention not only shatters public confidence in the state, but also symbolizes weak rule of law and tramples the dignity of individuals seeking to access justice. The first cause has been identified as the ruined legal culture, which can be attributed to two anomalies. Law enforcement practices reveal that the right to be presumed innocent until proven guilty does not exist. Also, there is a perverse understanding of the purpose of detention, which causes indiscriminate use of deprivation of liberty. The second cause has been identified as corruption in the criminal justice system, which has translated into the interference of the criminal justice process on different levels by various actors. Corruption can be used for the purposes of accelerating or decelerating the court process, to influencing the outcome of a trial. An inadequate legal framework has also been detected to cause arbitrary detention. On a statutory level, laws are not calculable and

¹⁰⁷ *ibid*

¹⁰⁸ The Working Group on Arbitrary Detention, *Fact Sheet No.26*, (Geneva: Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2000), 5.

there are articles in the Code of Criminal Procedure that legalize arbitrary detention and violate various rights of detainees, such as the right to a fair trial. On a procedural level, some arbitrary detentions occur out of a blatant disrespect and ignorance of the law. There is also a lack of procedural safeguards and mechanisms to overview whether or not the detention is just and reasonable in the given circumstances.

In the researcher's view, this caters adequately for the needed clarity as regards application and through implementation of the rule as is. It goes to show that even though the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention exists, its existence is direct consequence of the looming presence of state parties abusing the citizens right to liberty and freedom and security of persons.

H. Hannum (1995) in his publication "The Status of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights in National and International Law," in pg. 340-349, summed up the significance thus of these treaties recognizing similar rights and objectives. It does not only strengthens its universality but ensures that it is depicted in the very of legality and more than a customary international law, reinforced by state actions and opinion juris. He continued establishing factually that the right to liberty encompasses every other right following the right to life. Freedom is an essential phenomenon. Taken away, arbitrarily or justifiably, is unforgiving, and inexcusable.¹⁰⁹

The deprivation of liberty circles around the right of freedom of the individual to pursue his social, economic and political activity during his existence in the country. The bulk sum of human right documents all point to similar facts i.e. that the freedom of the individual is vital. And this vitality must be expressed in every term of both national and international frameworks. Thus, the right to liberty and security of person intertwines with or precedes the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention, in that the fundamental aim of the UDHR and other human right documents is to protect, secret and promote the rights of every individual, irrespective of their minute differences.

Article 9 has usually been invoked in the context of deprivation of liberty. However, the article also guards the right to security of the person. The significance of this right is controversial, for example, the European Court of Human Rights does not attribute any independent significance beyond personal liberty to the right to security in article 5 of the

¹⁰⁹ H. Hannum, The Status of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights in National and International Law," in pg. 340-349

ECHR.

Arbitrary arrest is illegal, but occurs, and although warrants are required under the law, most arrests are made without them, and some warrants were issued in irregular ways. In 2010, "only high-profile cases that were scrutinized publicly were known to have been properly handled", according to the U.S. State Department. Although the law requires that detainees be charged in court within 3 days of arrest (or, in some cases, 10), authorities routinely skirt this rule.¹¹⁰

The police lack equipment and are incapable of doing proper investigations or controlling riots. Police corruption is a major challenge, with officers dropping charges or making false arrests in return for payments, and demanding bribes at checkpoints on roads. Police brutality has declined, however, and so has impunity. Thanks to training in conduct and human rights, which is accomplished with the help of UN advisors, police are behaving more professionally and responsibly.

The (2011) *Annual Reports by the Human Rights Commission of Sierra Leone* praised "the stride taken by SLP [Sierra Leone Police to strengthen and improve on its capacity both in human resource and equipment despite the funding challenges confronting them". It noted that the Police Complaints Discipline and Internal Investigations Department (CDIID) had received 1589 complaints against police officers in 2011 and had dismissed 29 officers for unprofessional conduct and suspended, reduced the rank of, or served warning letters to, over 1000 officers.

In the Sierra Leone legal structure, it is provided in Article 9(5) for a right of compensation to all who have been unlawfully deprived of their liberty of person. And section 17(4) of the 1991 constitution. It says:

"Anyone who has been the victim of unlawful arrest or detention shall have an enforceable right to compensation."

It goes without saying, then, that even though the right of compensation is due person who had been arbitrarily detained, most times out of many, this compensation is not given.¹¹¹

¹¹⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Human_rights_in_Sierra_Leone#cite_note-state.gov-1

¹¹¹ UNDP' s Annual Report on the Justice Sector Development Programme scheme on 09/11, GC 08

2.9 CONCLUSION

There have been different opinions and theories on the practice of arbitrary detention, both self-opinionated and others based on the views of experts whose contributions have been sought. Irrespective of these contributions, what is clear is that they all come to terms with the singular resolve: Human rights, liberties and freedoms are special privileges given to all based on the simple fact that they are human beings. These added privileges also came along with elements, which made them binding and obligatory. The law of human right as it applies to arbitrary detention applies not only to a single state but also to all nations of the world. The standards founded on that faithful year of 1945 are universal, inalienable and inherent. They can neither be taken away nor suppressed. The significance of which is seen in the very essence of the right itself.

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 METHODOLOGY.

3.1 INTRODUCTION

This Chapter gives an account on the method and techniques used in carrying out this study. It does this by explaining the study area, the design of the study, the sample size, and sample techniques. It also establishes the sources of data, and the instruments of data collection, data analysis and procedures. It is the backbone of this study.

3.2 AREA OF STUDY

This study conducted in Freetown, the capital city of the Republic of Sierra Leone. The reason for this is partly because of considerations regarding accessing data from a sample of respondents within a given as required by the university. The researcher would have gone farther than this at least to have incorporated the provincial headquarter towns of Sierra Leone, but for the limited time and constraints to put together for the data collection. However, Freetown had been strategic enough and considered generally representative of other regions, this is not to disclaim the peculiarities to each of these regions. Also, it holds the mass subpopulation and the presence of key relevant stakeholders needed for the conduct of this study being one that is legally minded. Accounting for a huge number of the country's population, it houses almost all key government offices and other departments and institutions.

3.3 DESIGN OF THE STUDY

This study is an in-depth analysis on the *Right of Freedom from Arbitrary Arrest and Detention* as enshrined in Article 9 of the UDHR, also adopted in Section 17 of the 1991 Constitution of Sierra Leone. It explores at an extent everything that has gone wrong, and that might go wrong, even anything might be prevented from going wrong as it concerns arbitrary detention and arrest. It nose-dives into the very essence of Article 9; its compliance from state actors, its relevance, impact and challenges faced in the implementation and maintenance of this right and by extension the promotion of Human

Rights in Sierra Leone. This research is done with a view to assess the problems encountered in the implementation and enforcement of this right. That is, it looks into the “why’s” for a person’s right to liberty to be unfairly curtailed. The study also strictly takes note of standards already set by the UDHR document, local legislations, as replicated in Section 17 of the 1991 Constitution and embarks to address the loopholes in the implementation and protection mechanism.

3.4 SAMPLE SIZE

A total number of 60 respondents were sampled in this study and these were drawn from a frame that took into consideration the object of the thesis and guided by its research questions. Tailored in this way, it became increasingly clear to the researcher what obtains when it comes to arbitrary detention in the vicinity. Also, both probabilistic and non-probabilistic sampling methods were preferred in a bid to have a reliable and valid data that will reflect happening in the field. Below are the specific respondents identified for the interviews and the administration of questionnaires respectively.

Table 1.

FRAME	TOTAL RESPONDENTS
Human Right Experts	15
University Student	25
Public Servant	10
Civil Society	10
TOTAL	60

These individuals were tactically drawn from professionals down to an opinionated citizenry.

3.5 SAMPLE TECHNIQUES

Two different sampling techniques were used to get respondents from whom information was acquired through the put-to-use of the following techniques: *Simple Random and Purposive*

Simple Random was used to acquire information from the majority of respondent of whom questionnaires were administered to face-to-face. In the field, these respondents considering ethical issues were consented if they would allow the researcher put them in a group. After which respondents were selected randomly to answer questionnaires and few interviews conducted. The use of this *face-to-face* approach was to enable high return rate of questionnaires administered. The researcher assumed had the self-completion method been used, taking into account the busy schedules of theses selected respondents, they would not have got the time necessary to fill these questionnaires. Therefore the questionnaires were filled together with respondents and then collected.

Purposive Sampling as a technique was also used by the researcher to get the response from professionals and other experts in the field of Human Rights especially as concerned Right to Freedom from Arbitrary Detention, Right to Liberty, and Rights to Security of Person. These, being closely linked, can be easily discussed over and the information gathered will further enrich the research. Close attention was also paid to persons with knowledge of the workings of International Human Rights documents, especially knowledge of the UDHR and its unavoidable influence of Human Right laws in Sierra Leone.

Experienced legal practitioners were consulted and used as respondents for in-depth interviews that served as eye openers to lots of issues around arbitrary detention, the guarantee of the right, its abuse and interference by state actors in Sierra Leone. These respondents among other things were particularly selected based on their experience with the issue, working knowledge and specific positions held within the public service, university students and human right experts inclusive.

3.6 SOURCES OF DATA

Primary and Secondary data are used in this research

PRIMARY SOURCES

Primary data including interviews and questionnaires were administered in the field that enabled the researcher with first hand information on the perpetration of arbitrary

detention and peoples right to liberty in Sierra Leone. The Primary tools used in data collection helped the researcher with practical experiences on the ground and also enabled the researcher with critical issues bordering on the respect for and enforcement of Article 9 in the human rights laws in Sierra Leone

SECONDARY SOURCES

Secondary data including published and unpublished works, the credibility of which was painstakingly verified and ascertained in a bid to add richness and veracity to the research. Internet sources from E-Libraries, journals, articles and reports were also used in collecting data for the research. This partly contributed to an in-depth understanding of the concept of *arbitrary detention* and also created a theoretical framework from which empirical investigations were enhanced. Without which, it would have been virtually impossible for such detailed, theoretical and conceptual framework to be established. It also further helped with numerous international and other regional legal instruments on the issue of arbitrary arrest and detention and its contributions to the promotion of human rights in Sierra Leone. A comparative analysis led the researcher to incorporate the experience in other countries similarly replicated in Sierra Leone which all added to source of data contributed in the whole of the research.

3.7 INSTRUMENTATION

In carrying out this research the following instruments were used to collect information:

- a. **DOCUMENTATION:** in an attempt to enhance the review of literatures, the researcher had to read related documents on the right of freedom from arbitrary detention, and linked areas of right to liberty and security of persons, also international and national human rights laws. These contiguous publications were studied with a view to run across relevant areas on the subject matter. This was important as it created the opportunity to access publications on immediate occurrences around the subject matter. The bulk of these can be found in Chapter 2 in the literature review.
- b. **IN-DEPTH INTERVIEWS:** In research work, interviews cannot be dispensed with. The study needed empirical investigation, which could not be acquired without exploring primary tools of data collection. Interviews therefore serving as one of the primary tools were used to further probe into the subject area, tapping into the experience of experts and professionals in the this area of arbitrary detention and

arrest. These interviews were strictly guide by an interview guide found in **Appendix D**, streamlining the focus and makes for added clarity and depth to the research.

- c. **QUESTIONNAIRE:** These were used to acquire information from various groups of people that comprised the sample frame. The information gathered through this method further enriches the study in helping to get total number of percentages used in the study. That statistical precision and advantage affords the needed clarity for further research into this area of arbitrary detention. Questions drawn in the questionnaires were both closed and open-ended. This was deliberate on the part of the researcher to create room for further responses from respondents and at the same time allowing to be freely critical in their responses. The structure of the questionnaire was deliberately tailored in a way to obtain the most relevant answers and information about the research questions. A sample of the questionnaire is found in **Appendix A**. In Chapter Four, efforts were made to append side-by-side the sections answered, and the data collected as a result of the question posed.
- d. **GROUP DISCUSSIONS:** These took the form of gathering a set of people in a group setting, presenting the research questions and the aims of the study, and points deliberated on were taken down, and positions re-analysed and clarified in line with objective of the research. Another benefit of a focus group discussion is the unusually large amount of output as a result of a relatively relaxed environment, this had members participate freely in an amicable environment.

3.8 DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE

3.8.1 QUALITATIVE METHOD

Data used in this study were collected through reading documents, reviews, and articles from various sources and media, and the conducting of focus group discussions and interviews with seasoned experts and activists to get information on the topic. The researcher had to visit the research community and through the various sampling techniques was able to get respondents whose responses were acquired through the above-mentioned instruments.

Since having respondents to participate in a research often proves to be difficult, some are naturally unforthcoming. However, as a result of regular visiting methods to reach the research participants in the research communities and areas, the researcher endeavoured

to acquire data, as much as is reasonable, from them. Mostly there are four types of commonly used qualitative methods of research, which include the administration of questionnaires, the conducting of in-depth interviews, focus group discussions, and participation/observation. While in-depth interviews are generally based on the individual and personal perspectives or acquired experience on the subject matter under study, respondent's observations are appropriate for collecting data on the happenings occurring around and within their community. Also, with the help of focus groups discussion, useful data was collected especially as regards the behaviour of police officers and authorities in detention centres, from maltreatment, gross abuse, and bribery. The discussion groups highlighted numerous problems the respondents had encountered or seen someone encounter. This was extremely helpful for the researcher. Also, the these selected members often represent the views and experience of majority of the members in the community.

Field excursions to police centres were done in a bid to get a balanced view from both victims and perpetrators alike, despite the officers being unresponsive, hostile and deliberately unrevealing. The researcher was able to get interviews with a few detainees and some police officers. By way of interviews, also, the study solicited expert opinions on issues of freedom and access to justice in these detention centres within country. The questions asked often times receive contrasting answers, which disproved popularly held opinions about arbitrary arrest and detention. By this, it became increasingly clear to the researcher the core issue and its varying opinions that are prevalent, leading to a more solid findings, conclusions and further recommendations.

From these interviews and discussions, the structure of the questioning was tailored in direct response and answer to the respective research questions. From the relevance of Article 9 protecting against arbitrary arrest ad detention, its impact in Sierra Leone human rights law, the role of police, and mechanisms in place, down to the challenges faced in the implementation of the law.

The interviewees were drawn from legal practitioners and students, magistrate, police officers, detainees, former inmates, professionals, administrative staffs at human rights offices, human rights activists and personnel etc.

Added to this, the researcher employed a technique of involving some in-group discussions with focus on police activities and human rights laws being effective within the country. The sum of opinion garnered was added to the substance of this work.

3.8.2 QUANTITATIVE METHOD

The main method of data collection in this study is in the administration of questionnaires. These, when collected, are well parsed and analysed to ensure it strictly corresponds or complements the qualitative weight of the research (**See Appendix A**). From the bulk of data acquired, the results shall be presented in a form of a table, a pie, a graph or a bar chart which would clearly show the values of each data, simplified and demonstrated, and also for the reason that it makes for ease of reference and further research. Therefore, as a result of these charts being easy to understand and explanatory, it became mandatory to represent findings from this study quantitatively in that manner. They clearly show how the right of freedom from arbitrary detention and the practice of arbitrary detention impact the Sierra Leone legal system

3.8 DATA ANALYSIS

Data collected from respondents through questionnaires were treated in the following way:

1. Each questionnaire was serialized.
2. Each response from question was regarded and tabulated
3. Responses from questions were then represented in frequencies and percentages.
4. Analysis and conclusions were made for each question base on the frequency and percentage of the response.
5. Measure of central tendencies represented in bar graphs, pie charts was also included in the data analysis to further justify the efficiency of the research.

3.9 CONCLUSION

The study is an applied research that used both qualitative and quantitative approaches in data collecting. The focus of this study has been Freetown, the Capital city of the Republic of Sierra Leone. A sample of 100 respondents was used and sampling

techniques both probabilistic and non-probabilistic in nature. Sources of information/data both involved primary and secondary tools with a view to create more reliable and valid data.

CHAPTER FOUR

4.0 PRESENTATION OF RESEARCH FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

4.1 ARTICLE 9 OF THE UNIVERSAL DECLARATION OF HUMAN RIGHTS

The great English jurist, Sir William Blackstone (1723-1780), argued in his Commentaries on the Laws of England (1753) that one of the key "absolute rights of individuals" was the right to the preservation of one's personal liberty. Following from this principle he further argued that it was "a more dangerous engine of arbitrary government" to "secretly hurry" a man to jail where he might suffer unknown or forgotten by the people Sir William Blackstone provides a strong defence of personal liberty and concludes that to "secretly hurry" a man to prison is a "dangerous engine of arbitrary government" (1753):

‘Of great importance to the public is the preservation of this personal liberty; for if once it were left in the power of any the highest magistrate to imprison arbitrarily whomever he or his officers thought proper; there would soon be an end of all other rights and immunities. Some have thought that unjust attacks, even upon life or property, at the arbitrary will of the magistrate, are less dangerous to the commonwealth than such as are made upon the personal liberty of the subject... But confinement of the person, by secretly hurrying him to jail, where his sufferings are unknown or forgotten is a less public, a less striking, and therefore a more dangerous engine of arbitrary government.’¹¹²

In contrast to such absolute rights as the prohibition of slavery and torture, the basic right of personal liberty does not strive toward the ideal of a complete abolition of State measures that deprive liberty; rather, it merely represents a procedural guarantee. It is not the deprivation of liberty in and of itself that is disapproved of but rather, that which is arbitrary and unlawful. It is the obligation of the State's legislature to define precisely the cases in which is permissible and the procedure to be applied. The right to personal liberty under the UDHR is not unlimited, but detention must be in accordance with

¹¹² Commentaries on the Laws of England, Sir William Blackstone, 1753

national and international law. Authorities should only detain people following clear, public procedures. To avoid being classified as arbitrary, detention must be appropriate, predictable, proportionate, necessary – and based on justice. Thus, countries can deprive people of liberty – within certain limits – while they await trial, and after conviction and sentencing, among other situations.

“The right to personal liberty is fundamental and extends to all persons at all times and circumstances, including migrants and asylum seekers irrespective of their citizenship, nationality or migratory status.”¹¹³

With Article 9, part of the large section of the UDHR (Articles 6-11) devoted to standards for the administration of justice, the Universal Declaration makes clear that a person’s freedom does not automatically evaporate on arrest or conviction. The person still has rights in court or behind bars – and the right to hold arresting or imprisoning authorities to specific standards.

It remains that Article 9 covers the individual to the extent of his rights and responsibilities to his respective state. This is so that actual convicts do not escape the law under the guise of breach of right of freedom from arbitrary and arrest.

The sanctity of the human freedom protected by Article 9 of the UDHR, formerly, had been addressed in the Great Charter in 1215, the Magna Carta, which influenced the development of the Common Law then, requiring Kings to renounce certain rights, respect certain legal procedures and accept that the laws bound him. It unequivocally protected certain rights of the King's subjects, whether free or fettered—most notably the writ of habeas corpus, allowing appeal against unlawful imprisonment. It provided:

“No Freeman shall be taken or imprisoned, or be disseised of his Freehold, or Liberties, or free Customs, or be outlawed, or exiled, or any other wise destroyed; nor will We not pass upon him, nor condemn him, but by lawful judgment of his Peers, or by the Law of the Land. We will sell to no man, we will not deny or defer to any man either Justice or Right.”¹¹⁴

¹¹³ UN Working Group on Arbitrary Detention, February 2018

¹¹⁴ Clause XXIX of the Magna Carta

Centuries after then came the adoption by United Nation General Assembly of the UDHR, which made the rather terse references to “human rights and fundamental freedoms” in the Charter acquire an authoritative interpretation. The Universal Declaration recognised civil, cultural, economic, political and social rights, and, although it is not legally binding document per se, since it was adopted by a resolution of the General Assembly. The principles contained therein are now considered to be legally binding on States either as international customary law, general principles of law, or as fundamental principles of humanity (Robertson, 1972) ¹¹⁵

And also, it became a model for the development and protection of human rights in other countries. That is, countries, thus, ratify and domesticate treaties, and adopt best practices from international standards set in documents such the UDHR or the Great Charter itself. These documents have led to development of other human rights instruments, Sierra Leone as a county has accepted and affirmed to or ratified these and other human rights instrument (HRC-SL, 2007): ¹¹⁶This has led to the inclusion of fundamental freedoms and liberties of every citizen in *Chapter III* of the 1991 National Constitution. The period after the decade civil war also saw the establishment of the Human Rights Commission of Serra Leone mandated to protect and promote issues of human rights abuse and other related matters being. This is in partial fulfilment of the obligation of Sierra Leone had, to put mechanisms in place to provide for the protection of human rights abuses.

However, as regards compliance and enforceability, as prescribed in article 27 of the Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties, a State may not invoke the provisions of its internal law as justification for its failure to perform a treaty. On the other hand, States are free to choose their own modalities for effectively implementing their international legal obligations, and for bringing national law into compliance with these obligations. Thus, the peculiarities of domestic legal systems differ considerably, even though having some similarities; it will be for each domestic judge, prosecutor, and lawyer concerned to keep him or herself informed as to the manner of incorporation of the State’s international legal obligations into national law (Henry, 2000).¹¹⁷

¹¹⁵ A.H. Robertson, *Human Rights in the World* (Manchester, Manchester University Press, 1972), pp.15-20

¹¹⁶ HRC-SL (2007) - Submission to the 1st Report to Universal Periodic Review Mechanism, Freetown, Sierra Leone.

¹¹⁷ Henry J. Steiner and Philip Alston, *International Human Rights in Context. Law, Politics and Morals*, 2nd ed. (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2000);

Summarily, the relevance of Article has been brought home. The right of freedom from arbitrary is a well-grounded one. Its existence was urgent and deliberate. It was a timely response to a need, a lacuna to be filled, an excess of power to be checked. Article 9 of the UDHR, thus, became a shield against the abuse and violation carried out by powerful governments on their citizens, trampling on the individual's inherent freedom.

4.2 ANALYSIS OF QUESTIONNAIRES, INTERVIEWS, GROUP DISCUSSIONS AND REPORTS.

This chapter goes in-depth into the analysis of the research findings and investigations undertaken during the course of the study. These were tailored in such a way that it captures the core objectives and research questions of this research. The data are represented in tables, pie charts and bar graphs. This comes as an addition to the qualitative approach used to further enhance a clear explanation on the findings and research. The findings are the outcome of the questionnaires, interviews conducted and some desk reviews done on the research questions raised. There are also other areas where certain publications on arbitrary arrest and detention provide valuable answers so the researcher has added these areas to support the other empirical investigations done in line with such publications. The findings seek to provide answers to the objectives and research questions asked culminating towards right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention in Article 9 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. Thus, each section directly answers a research question and presenting facts accordingly.

The findings are arranged in sequential order, i.e. it tapers down from data acquired from questionnaires, interviews, and group discussions to desktop reviews of related materials. Each and every method answering the research questions as set out by the researcher. The aggregate number of respondents is 70 as stated, the sum of data gotten from all these media are tabulated, analysed and made sense of in line with research question of the study.

4.3 RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE (*Appendix A*)

Research questionnaires are a major source of data in carrying out this study. The questionnaires were administered to a total sum of seventy (70) persons from different facets of society, making up for a varied and balanced view, and enabling richness to the

overall body of work. Nevertheless, only a total of (60) were collected. This is largely owed to the fact that some of the respondents travelled out of town; some had unreasonably busy schedules, and a few admitted forgetfulness despite constant reminder. And given the timeframe to cover the research, it became prudent to assemble the data already present. The questionnaires were administered in this manner thus:

Table 2

CATEGORY DISTRIBUTED	NUMBER DISTRIBUTED	TOTAL NUMBER COLLECTED
Human Rights Activists/Experts	12	10
University Students	25	25
Public Servants	15	10
Civil Society Members	18	15
TOTAL	70	60

SOURCE: RESEARCH FRAME.

The sum category of respondents to whom questionnaires were administered and interviews conducted were four broad categories during the study and within the group of four — lawyers, magistrate, lecturers, police officers, OSDs, former inmates etc. are all included into these broad category. This categorisation accounted for a coherent reflection of the data and makes for easy interpretation and labelling. It also ensured that a well-balanced view was acquired that will, in an unbiased fashion, reflect that happenings as regards arbitrary detention and arrest in the vicinity.

This also afforded a look into the influence of **Article 9** on the human right laws in Sierra Leone, especially the law as it concerns the right of freedom from arbitrary detention, provided for in **Section 17** of the 1991 constitution.

Also by human right activists/experts it meant some personnel from Human Rights Commission of Sierra Leone, NAMATI, OSIWA and like organisations whose work revolve around championing human rights in its entirety. The sum of University Students were made up of student reading law and other contemporary programmes that are closely related to human rights, underlining arbitrary detention as a cause for common

concern. Also, public servants whose functions cover any of the three fundamental roles played by human rights through their numerous advocacy programmes. Civil society organisations play an active role in the recognition, protection and promotion of human rights through the numerous advocacy programmes as well. It was obvious they are included also.

The method used in completion the questionnaires was a *face-to-face* approach except for the few whose documents the researcher was deferred to check at a later date. But for each of the other categories, certain amount of questionnaires were administered and the same collected as a result of the *face-to-face* method of filling the questionnaires, ensuring a maximum turnout as best as possible.

4.3.1 CHARACTERISTICS & NATURE OF RESPONDENT

This section gives an account of demographic of respondents from whom information was elicited during the course of this study. The areas captured in this section are (a) respondent's sex (b) age mean (c) occupation etc. This makes the categorical delineation of respondents easy to know why one set thinks the way the do as oppose to the other.

Another benefit of this evaluating the response from respondent based on certain chosen characteristic or traits is that it shows where a sum of opinion may be lop-sided. For example, the ratio of male to female representation in activism as regards issues of detention and arrest may slightly differ. Also, the number of former inmates amongst the female is less represented than that of the male counterparts. This also enabled the researcher to identify areas of biased opinion as a result of one or more personal characteristics. This is so because whilst a sect of white-collar employees may stand greatly at a variance in opinion from their blue-collar counterparts, similarly one group of students offering a particular programme at university may also differ in views.. Thus, this, in the researcher's view, is what may account for the depth, accuracy, and comprehensiveness of the study.

However, some civil servants concealed their actual occupation for whatever reason, but it was easy to infer for the researcher their exact place of work and occupation. Also, this is true as regards age, a certain age brackets may hold certain opinion that may seem absurd to the other or an elderly age bracket. These are the numerous benefits of acquiring first some personal information about the respondents. It ensures that every contributing factor in place is captured and examined. Nevertheless, these characteristic

conjectures or assumptions did not replace the asking of ‘Why’ to further know the respondent’s reason for answering in a selected manner.

4.2.2 RESPONDENTS SEX

The research wanted to know the sex of respondents in a bid to know the level of representation for both men and women during the study. The pie chart below shows the findings:

Table 3

SEX	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
MALE	52	86%
FEMALE	8	14%
TOTAL	60	100%

Source: Questionnaire Q.1.2

Figure 1.

SOURCE: Questionnaire

From 60 questionnaires collected, 86% of the respondents were male and 14% of them were female. This shows that male respondents participated in the study more than female. The finding also revealed the fact that the male respondents were present in

almost all the areas constituting the frame. Even though both sexes have a role to play in the promotion and protection of human rights in Sierra Leone, however, what has been observed by the study is that men have played a more active role than women. This is partly owed to the patriarchal nature of our societies despite campaigns for gender balance and partly limited number of female representatives formal sectors different altogether. That is to say, not many women have gained formal employment in these areas so as a result the possibility for them to have equal responsibility and role in the protection and promotion of the fundamental human rights of people could be slim. Strictly, however, detention or arrest can be experienced by either sex indiscriminately, so it goes without saying that equality in the views expressed can also be demonstrated.

4.3.3 AGE OF RESPONDENTS

The researcher during this journey deliberately opted for different age brackets. The reason for this is to reflect a wider range of responses needed for the study. Different takes and turns on the issue ensure that it is critically dealt with and addressed. The graph below shows the age differences of respondents who took part in the study

Table 4: Showing the ages of each category of respondent represented in the study.

AGE MEAN	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
18-25 years	18	30%
26-30 years	12	20%
31-35 years	15	25%
36-40 years	10	16%
50+	5	9%
TOTAL	60	100%

Source: Research Questionnaire - Q. 1C

Figure 2

This is a diagrammatic pie that shows the mean representation of frequency of the different age brackets. Each value corresponds to the data recorded in table above. The depiction of these data serves the purpose of enhanced clarity and driving the point of variety and inclusiveness as regards the age of respondents curated for this research study. [See pie below]

Out of 60 respondents contacted during the course of the study, 9% of them had attained the age of 50 and above. This accounted well for the researcher as they proved to be very versatile and open as regards the issue of protection of the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention in Sierra Leone, and its impact in the development of human rights in Sierra Leone. Another 16% were between the ages 36-40 years who had also given their practical experience and studied observation on the issue of arbitrary detention towards improving human rights law in Sierra Leone. 30% were 18-25 years who were young but proved to have some wealth of experience based on their involvement or dabbling with political, human right affairs, and through their academic. Then, 25% were 31-35 years and 12% of respondents were 26-30 years. With this rich, diverse background, the study have been able to tap from the different levels of respondents with different opinions and views with respect to arbitrary detention and its impact on the development of human rights in Sierra Leone. From this chart, thus, it shows that majority of the respondents were within the ages of 18 – 35 years. Of this number is a composition of individuals from different walks of life. However, most of them are at present involved in legal practice, civil service, and some being office staffs or interns. The legally minded persons in this category turned out to give informed answers

demonstrating the unjustness of arbitrary detention in the society. They supported that the practice of arbitrarily detaining an individual without following laid down procedures and structures ought to be curbed at very level where authority is exercised. And that being that, police detention centers are to be supervised on a regular basis for people who have been held in detention for long period of time without trial or bail.

The judicial system of Sierra Leone caters for the healthy exercise of power by people in places of authority and such persons have to be checked in the manner power is exercised. These viewpoints attested to their experience they had got in their career, field of study or as a result of their roles played in the different organisations or their practical involvement in the human rights activism itself.

An almost similar viewpoint was held by five (5) of ten (10) respondents within ages 26-35 years old is that the protection of the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention is rendered fragile due to police non-adherence to best practices in the execution of arrest and detention. That is, they often went overboard and abuse these powers for the sake of bribery and tokens.

In a similar vein, this view is re-echoed by respondents within the categories of ages 36-40 years who believed that the responsibility rested on the police officers to act according to mandate, and code of conduct rather than acting based on political, personal, or corrupt tendencies. In the event when individuals are arrested for crimes they allegedly committed, after they are taken to the police station, they more often than not remain for a long duration without taking the matter to court or granting them bail. It is clear that respondents within this age gap are mostly experienced career persons, re-echoing an informed standpoint, taking an earnest stance on the matter. Thus, it is assumed by the researcher that the propositions of members of this category were mostly based on experience, research, and some opinions as conjectures even though the reports from the police stations compiled by JSDP stated otherwise.

Respondents within the ages of 50+ expressed opinion mostly geared towards the idea of a deficient structure in the judicial system and a poor infrastructural setup from detention centres to courtrooms.

4.3.4 RESPONDENT'S EDUCATION

As being part of the criteria considered by the researcher in choosing the respondents, the study also took considerations of the educational level of respondents as key hence, it

was believed that their level of education would determine the level of contribution to be made in respect of the research questions that would be posed. This is to say that, opinions from lawyers, and human rights experts may differ from students at different levels offering different programmes. The researcher, thus, became keen on acquiring the respective level of education for the respondents. This is often done through a polite request put to the respondent requesting them to state their level of education in the questionnaire. Despite a few of them proved reluctant, it was largely successful. The chart below shows these findings.

Table 5: Showing the Respective Educational Level of Candidates

EDUCATIONAL LEVEL	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Tertiary	35	59%
Secondary	20	33%
Primary	5	8%
None	0	0%
TOTAL	60	100%

Source: Research Questionnaire Q. 1. 5

Figure 3: Representing the Educational Level of Respondents

Source: Questionnaire Q. 2.0

Irrespective of the platform created to have involved different category of respondents, there were those respondents who could not provide details as to their educational background. This outcome required the researcher to further make moves that would indirectly indicate their level of education and experience on the issue of arbitrary detention and arrest. In total, there were four different levels of education created by the researcher. The researcher proved that a healthy 59% of respondents during the study had attained tertiary education with degrees in different areas of study including law. Following them was 33% who had attained secondary school education with other professional qualifications and experience based on either their role performed at the different places they work or practical experience as stated. And 8% at least had gotten some form of primary education or the like with relevant experience in the understanding of arrest and detention in human right laws. As a result, this accounted for a fact that majority of respondents had attained tertiary education and in turn often meant an informed point of view in response, enriching the research further in answer to its research questions.

4.3.5 ADDRESSING THE MAIN CONCERNS IN THE QUESTIONNAIRES

At this juncture, it is mandatory to represent the views of the respondents based on the various issues raised in the questionnaire for tactical application. The data will then be carefully checked and analysed to answer the research questions. The questionnaire was divided into five sections, **Sections A through E**, representing the number of research questions posed at the helm of the study.

- 1. SECTION A - WHAT RELEVANCE HAS THE RIGHT OF FREEDOM FROM ARBITRARY DETENTION POSED IN THE DEVELOPMENT AND IMPLEMENTATION OF SIERRA LEONE'S HUMAN RIGHTS LAW?**
- 2. SECTION B – WHAT HAS BEEN THE IMPACT OF ARTICLE 9 OF THE UDHR THUS FAR?**
- 3. SECTION C – DO OUR LOCAL POLICING PROCEDURES ADEQUATELY ABIDE BY INTERNATIONAL LEGAL STANDARDS APPLICABLE TO ARREST AND DETENTION?**
- 4. SECTION D – HAS SIERRA LEONE AS A COUNTRY FACED ANY CHALLENGES IN THE IMPLEMENTATION AND PRACTICE OF ARTICLE 9 OF THE UDHR?**
- 5. SECTION E - WHAT FOCUSED MECHANISM HAS THE GOVERNMENT PUT IN PLACE TO PROMOTE THE PROTECTION OF THIS RIGHT OF FREEDOM FROM ARBITRARY ARREST AND DETENTION?**

The following shall represent the position of the various respondents to these research questions. The data are quantified and analysed in answer to the research inquiries.

4.3.5 APPLICATION OF DATA IN THE QUESTIONNAIRES IN ANSWER TO THE RESEARCH QUESTIONS.

Please note that each research question is in turn brought under critical analysis and the respective data acquired from the research questionnaire are presented against it accordingly and represented in the various methodologies as specified in **Chapter 3**.

4.3.6 SECTION A - WHAT RELEVANCE HAS THE RIGHT OF FREEDOM FROM ARBITRARY DETENTION POSED IN THE DEVELOPMENT AND IMPLEMENTATION OF SIERRA LEONE’S HUMAN RIGHTS LAW?

Sierra Leone’s foremost document responsible for the protection of human rights in the country is the 1991 Constitution. In Chapter III, it set as its aim the recognition and protection of the various ‘fundamental human rights and freedoms of the individuals’. In Section 17, it protects the right of the citizen not be arrested or detained arbitrarily without trail or bail, and went further to provide for compensation for persons who turned out to be blameless at law. The right of freedom from arbitrary detention became an important one. The responsibility lies both with the legislators and the law enforcement agencies, the police and other security personnel. The relevance of **Article 9**, by extension **Section 17** is that it does not only guarantee that persons are not arbitrarily detained but it also ensures that their right to liberty of person and security of person are ensured and thereby protected. This assurance of safety and peaceful thriving of the human rights laws in the country is what would make up for the development of Sierra Leone human rights laws. The principal reference point for this has been the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, which is generally agreed to be the foundation of human rights law and trailing In Article 9, it sets out clearly that:

*“No person shall be arbitrarily arrested, detained or exiled”*¹¹⁸

This provision lies amongst the core principles of human rights and its influence numerous national legislations are greatly felt in the issue of restricting or limiting the individual’s movement and freedom. In Sierra Leone, the fundamental freedoms of the citizen are protected in Chapter 3, and the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention is protected by **Section 17** of the 1991 Constitution of Sierra Leone:

“17. (1) No person shall be deprived of his personal liberty except as may be authorized by law . . .”¹¹⁹

This has resulted in one of the visible impact and relevance of the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention, marking its universal appeal and necessity amongst states and legal systems. The right to liberty and security of persons ties with the right of freedom from arbitrary detention and arrest, i.e. where there is one, there is bound to be

¹¹⁸ Article 9 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, 1945.

¹¹⁹ Chapter III, Section 17 of the Sierra Leone 1991 Constitution

the other and this shared lines of freedom augurs well for the individual to battle his case from every fronts.

Sierra Leone, thus, ought to recognize the rights of liberty for the individual because when a State pursues a deliberate policy of denying persons within its territory their fundamental rights, not only is internal security of the State in Jeopardy, but in serious situations there is spillover effect that imperils the peace and security of other states as well. This hard-won lesson has been confirmed on numerous occasions in every part of the world. (Salvator, 1999)¹²⁰

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights advocates for universality, indivisibility, interdependence, equality and non-discrimination as it concerns every human right guaranteed and as such, granting one and refusing the other equally and indiscriminately amounts to not granting any. Arbitrary arrest or detention, as it is, robs not only the individual arbitrarily detained of his freedom, but also desecrates the sanctity of the human right laws of the state. Ensuring persons are arbitrarily detained is one step towards validating the other rights. Freedom is indispensable. This is so because even the right to life is a right of freedom in itself.

The relevance of the right of freedom from arbitrary detention and arrest is further shown thus in other international human right documents and protocol papers advocating against the practice. Among these also is **Article 9** of the International Convention on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR), a treaty that Sierra Leone has ratified and its optional protocol in 1996, as with other treaties like the Convention Against Torture, International Convention on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights, Convention on the Rights of the Child. Sierra Leone, being signatory to these treaties, with exception of the UDHR, which is only a declarative document, now, bears the responsibility to ensure that the rights of its citizens are protected. As with every human right abuse, it does not only come with the infringement of the right but also other infringements as in this case, persons arbitrarily arrested also suffer various forms of torture and cruel treatments, that could not have happened but for their being arbitrarily detained. This joint consequence of one right against the other presses more urgently the need and importance for respect, enforcement and practice of the international standards sets by international human right documents, at the head front, the Universal Declaration of Human Right, UDHR.

¹²⁰ Salvatore Peledda, (1999) On being Human. Interpretations of Humanism from the Renaissance to the Present, 1997.

Thus, the protection and promotion of this right is mandated in every sphere where humans exist, and their inherent rights protected and secured. The right of freedom from arbitrary detention and arrest remains one of the fundamental rights of the UDHR, it clearly set out the conditions and requirement both for right bearers and duty holders. This creates a divide between authorities trampling on these rights as opposed to the individuals themselves. All said and done, a man’s liberty ought to be ensured. The liberty of every individual is sacrosanct irrespective of his or her origin, nationality, tribe, religion. It caters for as much enjoyment as warrants the other rights in the UDHR. The right to life is nothing without freedom.

In Sierra Leone, this, even more importantly underscores the relevance of the individual’s freedom, equated to his enjoyment of all the other rights contained in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and the national constitution. It goes then without saying that depriving the individual from his right of freedom from arbitrary detention impacts his other inalienable, inherent human rights and freedoms.

In conducting the research, the researcher first ensured that the each and very respondent was aware of the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention, i.e. they possessed a working knowledge of the operations of **Article 9**, by extension, **Section 17** in the country’s national constitution; assessing whether it’s in actual practice nationwide. The respondents were, then, requested to demonstrate their awareness level of the right to freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention in Sierra Leone. See data below:

Table 6: Showing the Awareness Level of Respondents of Their Right to Freedom from Arbitrary Arrest and Detention. – Source: Questionnaire (*Index Q1A*)

AWARENESSS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGES
Very High	37	61%
High	14	24%
Average	9	15%
Low	0	0%
TOTAL	60	100%

Figure 7: Demonstrating Awareness Level of Candidates in a graph

From gauging their appropriate awareness levels of their rights, by extension their awareness of the operations of **Article 9** of the UDHR, and **Section 17**, ensuring they are actually aware of their right to freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention, we then proceeded to quantify the relevance of that right, setting the stage for a more accurate assessment from respondents.

Therefore, to quantify the relevance of Article 9 in the development and promotion of human rights in Sierra Leone, respondents were assessed in the questionnaires to indicate how relevant is Article 9 of the UDHR or the Right of Freedom from Arbitrary Arrest and Detention in this regard. Their perceptions are then analysed in light of the data. These findings are discussed and analysed below:

Table 7 – Showing How Relevant Respondents Consider The Right of Freedom From Arbitrary Arrest and Detention — (*Source: Research Questionnaire: Index 2A*)

RELEVANCE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Very Relevant	45	75%
Relevant	10	17%
Fairly relevant	5	8%
Not Too Relevant	0	0%
TOTAL	60	100%

Figure 5: Demonstrating the Relevance of the Right of Freedom from Arbitrary Arrest and Detention in a graph

(Source: Research Questionnaire)

Out of the 60 respondents, 75% of them considered the right of freedom from arbitrary detention and arrest a relevant in Sierra Leone. This shows they accept the fact that the right of the individual to freedom and liberty should not be deprived. This is followed by another 17% of the respondents who stated that it is just relevant, on the grounds that it is essential for the full enjoyment of the right to life, and 8% of these respondents did not think same, based on their experience, or standpoint, considered the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention as fairly relevant. However, this finding indicated that the right of freedom from arbitrary detention and arrest has a direct bearing on the human rights law in Sierra Leone. Therefore, if the promotion and protection of human rights are to be achieved, then the freedom of the individual ought to be unquestionable. This

according to respondents, they believe, has an involvement in all human right activities in Sierra Leone.

This also made clear the fact that the respondents agree that international human rights law, in the UDHR, ICCPR, and other documents, are to be respected by their national government. The obligation to respect means that states must refrain entirely from any abuse of the individual's human rights. In Sierra Leone, despite her commitment to these treaties, the rights of individuals are still being violated in the form of arbitrarily detaining persons without fact of commission of any crime under the law, restricting the individual's freedom and sometimes subjecting them to torture, physical or psychological, during these detentions. The refraining from interfering with or curtailing the enjoyment of human in every of their functions is thus paramount. This ought to be catered for in a way by having a policies planned out or a legislation that will ensure its protection. The obligation to fulfil means states must embark on positive actions to facilitate the enjoyment of basic human rights and under all circumstances these rights should be respected, promoted and respected.

The relevance thus is also shown through the ratification and domestication of treaties, which protect human rights. By this, Sierra Leone has shown commitments to implement strategies and measures in adherence to those treaty obligation and duties. The outcome mostly saw the enactment of domestic laws to safeguard these human rights guaranteed under these international law. Therefore, where domestic legal proceedings fail to address human right abuses, there are procedural mechanisms at regional and international levels to help ensure that international human rights standards are achieved.

Finally, they were further asked to state why do they think the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention is relevant to the development and promotion of human rights in Sierra Leone.¹²¹ This question was unguided, that is to say, there were no objectives, or answer directions as the researcher wanted an honest variety of opinions from the respondent without the interruption of pre-formatted answers, which will limit their answers. These opinions are categorised in groups of similarity accordingly. Not to the researcher's surprise, the bulk of the answers leaned towards the reason of because it's their fundamental human rights, and the infringement of which is intolerably unjust, and few others stated it's because Sierra Leone is a democratic country, that ought to

¹²¹ Questionnaire Index: Section 1, Question (1C)

respect its people fundamental rights. This question then successful set the tone to assess the impact that the right has had in Sierra Leone.

SECTION B – WHAT HAS BEEN THE IMPACT OF ARTICLE 9 OF THE UDHR THUS FAR?

4.4 IMPACT OF ARTICLE OF THE UDHR

After assessing both their awareness of the right, its relevance and reason for its relevance, to the development and promotion of human right in Sierra Leone, we then proceeded to gauge the impact of the right. The researcher ensured the respondent correctly understood the questions so as to gauge the appropriate answer to them. By impact, it is meant, whether the rights are actually being protected, whether there is a corresponding drop in the number of cases arbitrary detention, as a result of Sierra Leone's adherence to international treaties and to its Section 17 of the 1991 Constitution.

This exercise was aimed at measuring Sierra Leone's commitment to its obligations in treaties and conventions and human rights standards. The UDHR, in this respect, has remained the standard document that sets the fundamentals of human rights universally and these rights carry inherent attributes and as such every human being that walk the earth is by default entitled to these rights, and can readily seek redress at any court of competent jurisdiction. The document, as a whole, has influenced numerous other document in the same direct namely, ACHPR, ICCPR, ECHR etc. This often is seen in similar recognition, promotion and protection of similar rights and privileges. As per international law, countries who are part to treaties and such international agreements assume the obligations of not only respecting these laws or agreements set put in those treaties, but also to do everything in their power to ensure that it is implemented in the home country. This has resulted in the domestication of these laws, and enactments of legislation to reflect the standards set in these international document.

The impact of these international documents is seen in the fact that several major treaties, ratified by more than 100 countries, including Sierra Leone, trace their origins to the UDHR. They include, in chronological order: The International Convention on the Elimination of Racial Discrimination (1965), the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (1966). The International Covenant on Civil and Political

Rights (1966), the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (1979), the Convention Against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment (1984), the Convention on the Rights of the Child (1989) to name but a few.

In assessing impact, when a country ratifies an international agreement, it assumes a legal obligation. As signatories to these human rights treaties, they are required to prepare and submit regular reports on their promotion and protection of human rights in their country. This process is normally concerned with the implementation strategies put in place by the national government, in guaranteeing the citizens' freedoms. All these reports go to U.N. specialists, who study them carefully, analyse them and recommend where changes are ought to be made. Sierra Leone is a signatory to the above treaties and by reason has assumed full responsibility to protect the individual's rights and freedoms and restrain from any violations whatsoever.

The glaring impact of Section 17 has seen the development of prison rules and procedures to regulate arrest and detention, ensuring that every detainee is justly charged and not arbitrarily imprisoned. So, the study wanted to know these impacts that the UDHR, specifically Article 9, has created. And as such underscoring the fact whether international human rights laws actually do take a toll on states and influence their domestic policies and legislations.

Respondents were first assessed to gauge the contributions of Article 9 of the UDHR to the development and promotion of human rights Sierra Leone. They were required to tick, indicating their self-assessed contribution levels of Article 9, in any way they might have come across the influence of such international document. The data for this assessment is included below:

Table 8: Showing the Respondents Self-assessed Rate of Contributions Made by Article 9 of the UDHR.

RATE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGES
Vibrant	31	52%
Fairly Vibrant	25	41%
Average	4	7%

Useless	0	0%
TOTAL	60	100%

Figure 6: Demonstrating the data of Rate of Contribution of Article 9 in a pie.

Source: Research Questionnaire Q. 2.A

Out of 60 respondents contacted during the course of the study, 52% of them agreed that the contribution of Article 9 is al-time vibrant one. This, it was taken, they considered that the fact they country has incorporated in t its Section 17 and according it the reliance of any other human rights, equally showed the impact it has had. However, this impact has not only been seen in Sierra Leone’s 1991 Constitution alone, other countries have also adopted it into their legislative systems, and in these modern times, there are numerous treaties that guarantee and safeguard the similar rights, from the American Convention on Human Rights, European Convention on Human Rights to the African Charter on Human Rights. These respondents were followed by another 41% of respondents who believed the rate of contribution to “fairly vibrant”. They were also taken to have in one or the other encountered through activism, debates, and challenging human rights injustice, the impact such an Article has on our legal and policing system. There were also 7% of the respondents who believed that the rate of contribution was average enough.

Following from this assessment, respondents were then asked whether the current legal framework in Sierra Leone adequately supported the practice of this right? This enquiry will act as a follow-up to the rate of contribution of article 9, i.e., because we have agreed

that the right if freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention has somewhat contributed to the promotion of human rights in Sierra Leone, can we say the ‘legal framework’ from police procedures, arresting practices, detainee’s rights etc., support the efficient practice of this right.

TABLE 6: Showing Whether The Current Legal Framework Supports The Practice Of Article 9 Of The UDHR Or Section 17

OPTIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
YES	19	31
NO	34	56
I DON'T KNOW	7	11%
TOTAL	60	100%

FIGURE 4: Demonstrating Whether Our Current Legal Framework Supports Article 9 of the UDHR.

From the analysis and assessment, it was hardly surprising to get such an unbalanced view from the category of respondents. A majority of 56% of the respondents agreed that our present legal framework hardly support the practice of Article 9, whilst 31% agreed to structures in place but when later asked why to provide reasons for their answer, they were leaned towards the idea that despite these structures are in place, is the authorities who deliberately ignore and choose to go about abusing the individual's right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention. The 7%, I took to be included with those who said "No", who I considered much less vouching for the same thing.

Thirdly, in accordance to the above assessment, respondents were respectively asked to provide reasons for their answers, most of the answers were 'circular', and this was the intended purpose of the question. That is to say, they respondents mostly answered that because the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention still continues to be abuses and disrespected by the police an detaining officers despite these contributions they were fairly vibrant. (*See Index, Questionnaire, Q. 2B*)

Finally, to actually acquire certainty from the respondents, they were then asked in an unguided question format to state the specific impact that has been created by Article 9, covering your freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention to the development of human right law in Sierra Leone (*Index 3B*). To these, they were categorised the answers into three (3):

- (a) Constitutional Impact: This is seen in Section 17 of the 1991 Constitution, and Section 80 Criminal Procedures Act of 1965
- (b) HR Annual Assessment Reports – this often took the form of annual assessments, and recommendations given to government to improve on the protection of the rights they failed to implement adequately. These assessments urged governments to take actions.
- (c) Other treaties/conventions SL is signatory – By this, it was meant that even though the UDHR is more of a customary, international human rights document, yet its impact in other treaties which are binding, indirectly impact the implementation of the rights in the respective country. For example, SL is signatory to the ICCPR, and in actual fact, bound to uphold essentially majority of the rights provide for similarly in the UDHR.

The country's adherence to international standards set by international human rights

documents is reflected in its commitment also in Section 10, showing the rate of contribution of international laws in general, paragraph (d), “...*respect for international law and treaty obligations, as well as the seeking of settlement of international disputes by negotiation, conciliation, arbitration or adjudication.*” This is in line with one of the four purposes of the United Nations is, according to Article 1(3) of the Charter:

“2. To achieve international co-operation in solving international problems of an economic, social, cultural, or humanitarian character, and in promoting and encouraging respect for human rights and for fundamental freedoms for all without distinction as to race, sex, language, or religion”.

Article 9 of the UDHR undoubtedly set the groundwork for the implementation of the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention, which can also be seen in article 9 of the ICCPR, a treaty which Sierra Leone has ratified. This binding obligation created the necessary impact on the country’s human rights development, to an extent that the HRC, in partnership with HR Assessment Committees, provide annual reports of the countries performance as it relates to its respect and promotion of human rights.

The ICCPR sets out civil and political rights according to international standards. It recognizes the freedom of the individual and protects it against arbitrary abuse. The dualist system which the country practices makes it legal and flexible to adopt many international provisions even though there is laid down procedure such treaty, agreements and convention will have to take. And according to the *dualist* theory, municipal law and international law are different legal systems. Municipal law is supreme, and for municipal judges to be competent to apply international treaty rules, for instance, these have to be *specifically adopted or transposed* into domestic law. It follows that local judges cannot in principle invoke a human rights treaty ratified by the State concerned unless the treaty is incorporated into municipal law, a process which normally requires an Act of Parliament.

This has seen its ratification of the African Charter on Humans and Peoples’ Right (ACHPR), the said document in Article 6 similarly protested against arbitrary arrest and detention:

“Every individual shall have the right to liberty and to the security of his person. No one may be deprived of his freedom except for reasons and conditions previously laid down by law. In particular, no one may be arbitrarily arrested or detained”.

The right of freedom from arbitrary detention continues to bear wider impact and this as demonstrated in the Tehran's case in the International Court of Justice noted in its dictum in the hostages in Tehran case, the Court stated that:

“Wrongfully to deprive human beings of their freedom and to subject them to physical constraint in conditions of hardship is in itself manifestly incompatible with the principles of the Charter of the United Nations, as well as with the fundamental principles enunciated in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights”.¹²²

Another major contribution achieved courtesy of Article 9 of the UDHR can also be seen in the setting up of institutions and semi-autonomous bodies to regulate the enforcement of these human rights standards and investigate abuses. In Sierra Leone, HRC 2004 Act set up the Human Rights Commission, empowered in section 8, to investigate into every are of human rights abuses and advise the government of solution and recommendations In line with international human rights standards. Therefore, what have been the specific impacts created by International Law in developing the human rights in Sierra Leone? This will have relations with the tangibles in terms of best international practices in relation to human rights law in Sierra Leone. According to respondents, one critical aspect of this could be the establishment of commissions in Sierra Leone like those of the human rights, National Democracy, National Electoral, institutionalized commission specifically focusing on specific social groups.

The impact of article 9 of the UDHR has not only been demonstrated locally but across regions in a way influencing the human rights laws of local legal systems internationally. A clear consequence of this is reflected in Article 7(1) of the ECHR and Article 22 and 23 Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court. The right of freedom from arbitrary detention created a universal outcome in legal systems, and off shoots documents of the UDHR. On the whole, international human rights law and practices have always been able to create platform of equality before the law despite their status. No one ought to be deprived of his or her freedom. Every human being should be treated equally by the same courts ad should have the same rights bestowed on all despite the differences in economic status or political affiliations. This equality is, however, not absolute since certain professional groups, such as military, lawyers and civil servants are sometimes

¹²² *ICJ Reports 1980*, p. 42, para. 91.

judged in in their status by specialized courts. This practice is not contrary to the rule of law; within these groups equality before the law also applies to the full extent in line with national legislative practices and procedures.

SECTION C – DO OUR LOCAL POLICING PROCEDURES ADEQUATELY ABIDE BY INTERNATIONAL LEGAL STANDARDS APPLICABLE TO ARREST AND DETENTION?

It is indisputable that many people are locked in prison cells for indiscriminate periods of time. This is even without having their cases heard because of either no access to legal representation, or procedural practices, which, unreasonably, detain individuals arbitrarily. When it comes to arbitrary arrest and detention, the police are nearly the biggest culprits. This is so because they are charged primarily with the duty of arrest and detention duly suspected persons, in the same vein, this power to detain has been continually abused by police in Sierra Leone, as there are a very large number of inmates who have been detained in police stations for over the constitutional periods whether for civil or criminal offences without been discharged or charged to court, leading to massive overcrowding in the detention centres.

It is undoubtedly clear that next to execution (capital punishment), the power to detain individuals is the most invasive power that the state possesses. And the deprivation of liberty is non-compensable and such unjust deprivations shatter our tenuous sense of autonomy and self-determination.¹²³ The common law wisdom proclaims that the state is not permitted to detain individuals against their will save and except for a proper arrest that is premised upon reasonable and probable grounds of criminal activity.

Discretion is the hallmark of individualized justice but it contains the seeds of an inequity. All too often discretion is exercised in a manner not consonant with the goals and spirit of valid legislative objectives.¹²⁴

Freedom from arbitrary detention should mean more than protection from official caprice because the notion of capricious state action is far too under-inclusive to capture the real

¹²³ Young, Allan, “**Arbitrary Detention and the Police Function: All Along the Watchtower**. Osgoode Hall Law Journal Vol. 29. No.2 (1991) : 329-397 p://digitalcommons.osgoode.yorku.ca/ohlj/vol29/iss2/3

¹²⁴ Ibid. Pg. 332

dangers presented by detention for investigatory purposes. State intrusion in the name of law enforcement has a tendency to expand into social control of groups perceived to be deviant or marginalized.

In Sierra Leone, police, on numerous occasions, have refused to release detainees even after being informed of their supposed malpractice, they most times either call for the complainant or until some higher authority call to order the release. It goes to show that they are accustomed to ignoring best practices as regard arrest and detention.¹²⁵ In connection with this, police also detain suspects invited to stations under the guise of invitation to answer police’s call.

In light of the above, respondents were thus asked to self-assess, through their interactions directly and indirectly with the police in the country, whether they honestly believe the police strictly and respectably abide by the directives in Section 17 of the 1991 Constitution, by extension Article 9 of the UDHR, and also procedures or body of rules governing arrest and detention. Below is a general perceptive assessment:

TABLE 11: Showing Data for Police’s Adherence to Article 9 During Arrest and Detention

OPTIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Yes	2	3%
No	58	97%
TOTAL	60	100%

From the assessment, a sweeping 97% of respondents agree that the police hardly abide by vest practices as prescribed by the Sierra Leonean constitution, international treaties, conventions and protocols. Immediately, they were then asked to quantify and rate the performance of the police as regards respecting the individual are right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention.

Table 8: Showing Respondents-assessed Rate of Performance of the Police in adhering to Article 9 of the UDHR

¹²⁵ Brief Interview with Lawyer Alimamy Sultan Koroma, about his article: “Clarifying the law relating to the Detention of Suspect in Police Custody”, on Tuesday, 24, September, 2019 11:45am

OPTIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGES
GOOD	2	3%
AVERGE	11	18%
BELOW AVERAGE	16	26%
POOR	31	51%
TOTAL	60	100%

Figure 8: Demonstrating the Rate of Police Performance in a graph.

From this assessment, it was clear that whilst some 21%, constituting of those that voted “*Good*” and “*Average*”, believing their performance was somewhat good, a majority state their performance thus far was abysmal. There were also some 26% who believed that their performance as regards respecting the individual’s right of freedom from arbitrary arrests and detention had been sub-par, constituting nothing more than being bare poor in every respect where rightful arrest and detention is concerned. The researcher then wanted to know whether with government intervention might the situation might get better.

TABLE 9: Showing Respondents Poll for Whether the Government’s Intervention might improve the situation of Arbitrary Detention in Sierra Leone.

Source: Research Questionnaire Q. 3C

Options	Frequency	Percentages
Yes, Definitely	33	55%
Well, It could help	22	37%
No, I don’t think so	5	8%
It’s No Good	0	0%
TOTAL	60	100%

FIGURE 11: Showing Respondents Poll for Whether the Government’s Intervention might improve the situation of Arbitrary Detention in Sierra Leone.

From the assessment, the bulk of findings leaned towards optimism, that is, if the government could actively implement strategic measure aimed at protecting the individual’s right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention, the situation is bound to improve.

SECTION D – HAS SIERRA LEONE AS A COUNTRY FACED ANY CHALLENGES IN THE IMPLEMENTATION AND PRACTICE OF ARTICLE 9 OF THE UDHR?

Despite the improvements and few success stories, there remains to be numerous challenges that plague the promotion and protection of human rights in Sierra Leone as a whole. There is evidence to the effect.

The right to freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention, captured in Article 9 of the UDHR, and replicated in Section 17 of the 1991 Constitution is barely exempted. In 2011, the United States Department in Sierra Leone published a report on human rights promotion and protection where it made it crystal clear that Sierra Leone despite its commitments to reflecting and, maintaining human rights standards, there are still problems the country is faced with and key among these have been:

“...security force abuse and use of excessive force with detainees, including juveniles; harsh conditions in prisons and jails; official impunity; arbitrary arrest and detention; prolonged detention, excessive bail, and insufficient legal dispersion of demonstrators; widespread official corruption, societal discrimination and violence...”

Also, in its discussion paper entitled Justice Sector and the Rule of Law, published in January 2014, OSIWA noted, “Frequent reports of physical abuse, illegally assessed fees and unlawful detention continue to undermine the SLP’s credibility.” The Sierra Leone Police till this day lack police officers with a sufficient legal background at each police station that is primarily responsible for the determination of the issue of bail and every decision to deny bail ought to be in writing and subject to review after every 24 hours.

Further, the police do not strictly abide by the limits imposed by the constitution on police custody, e.g. prevent torture in pre-trial detention as numerous accounts have indicated that detainees are often subjected to torture and other inhuman treatments. The procedures and practises of the SLP as regards detention are hardly at par with recognised international standards.

This phenomenon of non-adherence is not new. Sierra Leone has ratified numerous treaties e.g. International Convention on Civil and Political Rights, International Convention on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, Convention Against Torture, Convention on Rights of the Child, African Charter on Human and Peoples’ Right, but putting these in practice with full implementation of the law is by seemingly insurmountable challenges.

Whilst administering questionnaires, respondents were then asked to state whether in their views had there been challenges in the full protection of the individuals and right

OPTIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Yes	57	95%
No	3	5%
TOTAL	60	100%

and freedom from arbitrary detention in the promotion of human right in Sierra Leone, The findings in this area are disclosed below in the chart compiled.

Table 8: Showing Whether There Had Been Any Challenges Faced by The Sierra Leone Government in Implementing/Adhering to Article 9 of the UDHR

(Source: Research Questionnaire Q. 1D)

Figure 8: Showing data representation for Question 1D

Out of 60 respondents, 95% of respondents were positive that there had been challenges faced by the government. And these challenges are impeding the smooth operation of Article 9. Therefore, it was important to highlight these challenges encountered in the protection of the individual's freedom from arbitrary detention to further improve human right law in Sierra Leone. However, the other 5% stated that there have been no

challenges in this drive. The researcher took it to mean that they are either unaware of these challenges or considered otherwise that what others have considered as challenges ought not to be so.

The finding then sought to pinpoint some of these challenges and they are displayed in the graphs below:

Table 11: Showing data for the Challenges Faced in Implementing the Right of Freedom from Arbitrary Arrest and Detention.

Challenges	Frequency	Percentage
Inadequate Resources	4	6%
Lack in Infrastructure	5	9%
Corruption	30	50%
Politics	7	11%
Weak Law Enforcement	10	16%
Obsolete Laws	2	4%
Attitude of Individuals	2	4%
TOTAL	60	100%

(Source: Research Questionnaire, Q 3D.)

Figure 9

Out of the 60 respondents who participated in a multiple choice question response system, 50% of them mentioned that corruption is one major challenge, about 16% of them had mentioned that weak law enforcement has also militated against the drive, 11% blamed politics, 9% stated inadequate resources, 6% ascribed it to infrastructural lack, 4% stated that obsolete laws or legal system is a culprit, and a final 4% stated that the attitude of individuals is responsible.

Next to that in the ladder were **11%** of respondents who believed politics also posed a major challenge in the promotion and practice of Article 9 of the UDHR. This ranged from the influence of politicians in their missions of vendetta against other politicians, and also using detention as a tool to silence an opposing voice against their government. Politics has also been another major challenge in the particularly when it pertains upholding of human rights of eve individual within the state. One of the key attributes of the UDHR is non-discrimination, that the enforcement of the rights is effected without discrimination on grounds of power, wealth or status. The contrary is often the reality. This debacle is also even seen in the selection of stakeholders in government institutions responsible for the promotion ad protection of human rights appointed and approved on political affiliations. This, according to respondents has dampened the spirit of many to pursue their human rights even when violated.

The majority of the respondents, that is **50%** of them, ascribed the failure to maintain the right of freedom arbitrary arrest and detention to corruption or corrupt practices, which they believed underpins the majority of the lapses encountered in the efficient protection of the rights of the individual's freedom from arbitrary detention. This act of corruption continually plagues police detention centres. It has stifled every progress fought for in the promotion and protection of Section 17. This has taken the forms of bribery; curry favours and acting out of sentiments. It is part of a worrying culture by some rogue police officers that continue to abuse the power of detention and using it as a tool for extortion, punishment or securing forced confessions. In a discussion paper entitled Justice Sector and the Rule of Law, published in January 2014, OSIWA noted, "Frequent reports of physical abuse, illegally assessed fees and unlawful detention continue to undermine the SLP's credibility." This amongst others show evidence for the lapse in the enforcement of Section 17. Every step taken by authorities and complain victims has been tampered with by corruption and its vices. This outcome has become so serious to the extent many victims simply just abandon the cause of challenge for the human rights, Saddened by the

apparent lack of respect or disregard, the individual's plight is left undressed, and his freedoms continued to be taken advantage of. This also can be ascribed to police officers who deliberately ignore the rules that exist in the name of their own procedures. And this has continually militated against best practice and procedure in maintaining the citizen's right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention.

A solid **6%** of the respondents blamed lack of infrastructure for the poor implementation and practice of the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention. This category and those

Also, a sum of **9%** of the respondents believed inadequate resources had militated against implementation primarily, which had to do with equipping of police officers with legal resource and education, provision of paralegals providing advisory service to detainees on their rights in a quasi-judicial capacity; and the setting up special monitoring mechanisms that frequent prisons and detention centres to address the rude abuse of the right are just few amongst these infrastructural lacks. As at now, every complaint lodged in respect of human rights abuse is either laid before HRC or the Ombudsman, which are most times overwhelmed and under-resourced.¹²⁶

The area of weak law enforcement has also hampered the implementation and practice of Article 9, thereby Section 17, **16%** of the respondents believed. It has however been observed by law enforcement mechanism put in place by the police in Sierra Leone is seriously challenged. It is either the resources to police are not sufficient or orders are given from higher authorities, which is commonplace in Sierra Leone. These have without doubt challenged the implementation of Section 17.

Another **4%** of respondents have thrown some light on obsolete laws, which either stagnates the development of our legal system, or militate against the introduction and operation of improved, modernised practise and procedures and as such leaving the entire system strangled, and robbed of its efficiency.

The attitude of individuals has also posed a significant challenge in the fight for protection against arbitrary arrest and detention, **4%** of the respondents agreed. The attitude of Sierra Leones is known to be very naive and reluctant and this has shown itself in instances where they ought to report abuses of arbitrary detention to human

¹²⁶ Interview with Mr. Sultan Koroma, Human Rights Activists

rights authorities instead they rather callously ignore, allowing perpetrators to have their way, however the law should take precedence.

SECTION E - WHAT FOCUSED MECHANISM HAS THE GOVERNMENT PUT IN PLACE TO PROMOTE THE PROTECTION OF THIS RIGHT OF FREEDOM FROM ARBITRARY ARREST AND DETENTION?

The study as part of its objectives is to explore the structures, if any, that has been put in place nationally to effect the full promotion and protection of the right of freedom from arbitrary detention and curbing the abuse of arbitrary detention. Therefore, the implementation of strategic and systematic measures aimed at restricting the persistence of arbitrarily detaining an individual is analogous to promoting and protecting the functionality of the right. This to say, step taken in one direction will equally impact the other end. Engaging with civil societies, human right advocacy groups, international human right bodies are few amongst the co-operative strategies that the government can employ at will. There have, however, been a couple of findings having implications on this structure but this section purposely sheds light on it.

The research entailed a study on whether there had been any structures and the outcome of this saw data from the research tabulated and represented in statistical forms. Questions were specifically created and tailored in line with the objective of the researcher to achieve the desired object as well as a balanced opinion and further reasons for it.

Table 9: Showing Data for Structures in Place to Protect the individual’s Right of Freedom from Arbitrary Detention and Arrest.

OPTIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Yes	33	55%
No	27	45%
TOTAL	60	100%

Source: Research Questionnaire Q. 1E

Figure 10

Out of 100 respondents, about 50% of them had stated that they are aware of a national structure already in place to combat the abuse and effectively protect the right, whereas the other 50% stated 'No', i.e. there has not been any national structure in place to do such. This finding has however pointed to the fact that not much has been done in this respect from what has been found out in the past objectives. The lapse is felt in every area where the researcher enquired about the protection of the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest.

The effectiveness of such system was also considered key in this assessment. As a result, respondents were asked to state how effective has this system been in protecting against the abuse of arbitrary detention in Sierra Leone. The finding in this area has also been captured in the chart below:

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Very Effective	14	14%
Effective	6	6%
Fairly Effective	30	30%
Not Effective	29	29%

Don't Know	21	21%
------------	----	-----

Source: Research Questionnaire

Source: Research Questionnaire

Out of 100 respondents, 30% which happens in this case to be the highest has confirmed that the system had not been too effective but rather fairly effective. Another 29% of the respondents had mentioned that the system had not been effective with only few stating that they could not tell and others stating it had been very effective. This finding has clearly shown that this system has not been effective at all. Despite the fact that it was discovered to be existing, but its effectiveness has been questioned especially when it comes to utilizing effective mechanisms on the protection of the right of freedom from arbitrary detention in Sierra Leone.

They were then asked to show the structures in place and recommend any two (2) ways they think will improve the protection of their right to freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention.' When it comes to structures, the set of respondents who said yes, mostly their response ranged from laws and systems guaranteed by the Human Rights Commission of Sierra Leone, NGOs, and Civil Society activism like Transparency International and Human Rights Watch. These structures in the form of institutions have been extremely performing to ensure that provisions in the constitution adopted from international human rights documents are implemented in Sierra Leone and thereby forming the basis for the

promotion and protection of the human rights laws in Sierra Leone. Their monitoring approach have been effective in the areas of reporting gross human rights abuse both local and international stakeholders respectively.

The police and the HRC in their monitoring and supervising role. The solutions they recommended were:

- (a) HRC workers should visit detention centres and search for individuals who have been detained for longer period without trial
- (b) Civil Society groups should pioneer the advocacy for the freedom of the individual to be respected and protected
- (c) They also urged the Police Disciplinary Committee to ensure that there practices are aligned with international law
- (d) They recommended government's non-interference into the workings of the law enforcement agencies, i.e. the independence of the police must be protected. Under this, they further recommended that they be paid well in order to discourage corruption and encourage performance.

4.9 CONCLUSION

The right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention has proved to be instrumental in the development and promotion of our human rights laws in Sierra Leon. It underscores more than just mere freedom of the individual from arbitrary arrest, but also ensures that the rights to liberty and security of persons are equally protected. This ripple effect is what makes its relevance and the need for respect all the more sacrosanct and urgent. It has tremendously impacted the way our human rights laws develop, and irrespective of these impacts it has faced many challenges in various forms. These challenges have helped mould the right in steeper directions, covering wider spheres of influence and its overall bearing on the human right laws in Sierra Leone. What stands clear, however, is the fact that the act of arbitrarily detaining persons will continue fester as long as it is left unchecked.

4.4 INTERVIEWS AND FOCUS GROUP DISCUSSIONS (APPENDIX B – INTERVIEW GUIDE)

As part of its methodology, and considering the fact that the researcher opted for a variety of data to enhance the richness of the research, interviews and focus group discussion were employed, since the scope of legal aid is wide, the student researcher conducted a number of interviews with key personalities on the subject matter. These group discussions took the form of handing out topic guides to the candidates, introduce the object of the gathering and target of the research, and stimulate inputs in the direct answer to the subject issue. This information were tallied and used to enhance the richness of this work.

As mentioned in Chapter 4, there were lawyers, human rights experts and activists, students, lecturers contacted during this study. Their respective information can be found in the appendix. In conducting the interviews of the personalities encountered during the research from whom an interview was to be conducted were handed out the questionnaires in substitution, where an interview would produce just about the same statements. However, they similarly provided valuable insights to the subject.

On the whole however, the study remains a direct and exhaustive one.

CHAPTER FIVE

5.0 Summary, Conclusion, and Recommendations

5.1 Summary

The right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention remains an integral part of every democratic society yet the ever-increasing menace from right abusers and perpetrators also remains extant. Its functioning in tandem with rights of liberty and rights to security of person together have made it to be considered ‘the most fundamental of all freedoms’. In Sierra Leone, the proper protection of this right is greatly marred largely due to infrastructural and political lapse, systemic maladministration and inadequate cooperative schemes aimed towards the protection of human rights in the country. This renders its Section (17) of the 1991 SL Constitution wiggly, less powerful and unprotected, and by extension hindering the promotion and development of human rights in the country. The SLP being the most notorious amongst other institutions, in this respect, has grossly underperformed its mandate to adequately protect and respect the human rights of the people of the this country.

The aim of this study had been to examine the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention in light of Article 9 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and replicated in Section 17 of the Sierra Leone’s 1991 Constitution. In its first chapter, the study fully examined the backdrop of Article 9, highlighting its source, and providing clarifications of meaning for core terms within a context, which the researcher hopes, it is understood by. And it goes further to establish the intent of the study, which had been to explore the relevance of the right of freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention, its impact, implementation, and challenges as revealed in the research questions. In the following chapter, the research nose-dives into the opinions of experts, other researchers, opinions, and literatures bordering on arbitrary detention, and amalgamates these opinions into a review, paired with the researcher’s point of view to highlight the lacuna in these literatures to modern times. With a well-designed method of research, as shown in the third chapter, gathering the needed data to answer the research questions became relatively easy, and provided the needed depth and clarity of the research.

Summarily, the majority of the opinion leaned towards massive intolerance and aversion to the act of arbitrary arrest and detention, and outrightly discourages the practice in

whatever form, or manner it is couched. At this juncture, the researcher goes on to conclude thus.

5.2 Conclusion

The practice of arbitrarily detaining someone remains one of the vilest evils and challenges our human right laws had to undergo. This phase is unpleasant. We must all equally share in this concern just as if we were victims, because the likelihood is ever-present.

This piece of work has not commissioned a fight against it. Fighting is all that has been done, but rather it sought to reinforce our understanding of the true value of freedom for every individual. It sought to accredit our progress now to our respect for the sanctity of human freedoms. Our development as race and a country is stifled when this has gone amiss.

The relevance of the right to freedom from arbitrary arrest and detention had its place ingrained into every fabric of our society. Our society immediately stops growing when it losses sight of or deliberately disregards this. It is necessary. Necessitated by this relevance, it leaves us no choice, as a nation's development is not far-removed from its human right development. And, respect for the inherent and inalienable human rights do not only ensure a peaceful co-existing but affords the harmony necessary for national co-operation by extension national development as a whole.

'Let them be uncuffed!' is not just a plea for undeserved freedom for criminal convicts but a language each one of us uses at one point in our lifetime. Our human rights are what made us humans after all.

5.3.0 Recommendations

5.3.1 'Panacea'

The Sierra Leone Police (SLP)

In its discussion paper entitled Justice Sector and the Rule of Law, published in January 2014, OSIWA noted, "Frequent reports of physical abuse, illegally assessed fees and

unlawful detention continue to undermine the SLP's credibility." Thus, the Sierra Leone Police ought to have a police officer with a sufficient legal background at each police station that determines the issue of bail and every decision to deny bail must be in writing and subject to review after every 24 hours. The police ought to strictly abide by the limits imposed by the constitution on police custody, preventing torture in pre-trial detention.

Also, Government and non-governmental organizations must as a matter of urgency intensify trainings for police investigators on human rights law, especially the principles and procedures relating to pre-trial detention. A number of non-governmental organizations working on access to justice including OSIWA, ADVOCIAD and LEWAF to name but a few might be quite willing to help in this direction.

Human Right Commissions

The Human Right Commission of Sierra Leone plays an all-important role in the protection and promotion of human right nationally. Charged with this mandate, it has powers to receive individual complaints and even issue binding orders to public officials while at the same working as an advisory body to the government. Empowered by Section 8 of Human Right Commission Act 2004, the HRC has the free reigns to investigate human rights violations, as well as visit jails, prisons, and places of detention to inspect inmate conditions and make recommendations.

They must make systematic visits to places of detention and also conduct visits in response to complaints, either as a result of formal judicial proceedings or following information received, for example, from even a family member. Often stifled by their reactive natures, they must regard their engagement with pretrial detention as ad hoc. Also, to be more effective and reach the many victims of torture who are unable to lodge a complaint, the HRC need should conduct systematic '*unannounced*' visits to all places of detention.

Laws of Sierra Leone

The Criminal Procedure Act (1965) must be reviewed to reflect international human rights best practices. For example, subject to few exceptions bail must be made mandatory for all minor offences such as assault, public disorder and insulting conduct. The new act must spell out clearly that bail can only be refused for minor offences in

exceptional circumstances and that order must come from the Inspector General of Police under a certificate issued in his name. The HRC Act of 2004 must be reviewed in light to empower the HRC to independently carry out its enforcement and promotion of the rights contained I Chapter III of our 1991 Constitution.

Civil Society

Civil Society movements sit at the helm of national advocacy and sensitization. Apprised of the 'real' problems, they are well positioned to speak against it. They and the general public should be encouraged to speak out against arbitrary arrest and detention. Members of the public must also utilize the disciplinary mechanism within the police namely the Complaint Discipline and Internal Investigation Department (CDIID) and the Independent Police Complaint Board so as to end impunity. The Police Discipline Regulations of 2001 presents a glorious opportunity to promote accountability and discipline within the police force and the public must make use of same to ensure dignity of suspects.

These organizations should also help in monitoring places of detention, where possible through regular visits to detention facilities. The model includes the use of an array of instructional methods to inform pretrial detainees of their rights and train them to represent themselves. Paralegals also work directly with prison authorities to monitor the status of files, ensure detainees are aware of the charges against them, and identify individuals eligible for bail.

Ombudsman

An ombudsman is at helm of receiving complaints at times when justice had gone amiss, that is addressing complaints related to the proper administration of justice is the paramount focus of the ombudsperson, even though their involvement in preventive measures is limited. Generally, they can become involved with monitoring detention sites through complaints and using their quasi-judicial powers, including the ability to resolve individual cases. These visits will further help the police to be self-vigilant against it.

Government

The Sierra Leone Government should formulate a strategy and plan of action to end arbitrary detention in consultation with relevant national stakeholders, including judges,

prosecutors, lawyers, human rights activists, law enforcement and security officials; as well as relevant United Nations entities and other members of the international community. The plan should outline concrete measures to be taken, to commit relevant authorities to specific deadlines, and layout sanctions for failure to meet them. The plan should aim to:

This action must be exclusive aimed at releasing all those detained arbitrarily or otherwise unlawfully deprived of their liberty, especially, individuals detained without a factual and legal basis of their detention.

The government must devise and implement a prosecutorial strategy to ensure that all detainees are screened by independent judicial bodies to determine whether they should be immediately released or referred for trial to face criminal charges in proceedings meeting international fair trial standards. Given the large number of detainees and facilities, priority for screening should be given to vulnerable groups including children, women at risk of abuse, pregnant women, and 2011 conflict-related detainees held for over six years without sentencing.

They should provide all those released with documentation indicating the length and place of their detention and information on whether they were released without charge or trial or on their charges and sentences. Ensure commensurate reparations for all those subjected to unlawful deprivation of liberty.

NGOs

NGOs should lobby with development partners to enable them to support financially the activities of human rights protection and promotion in Sierra Leone. Also as part of the working mechanism of the country, they can embark on scheme against human rights violation, and voluntarily visit prisons and detention facilities, advocating against arbitrary detention or they can even files complaints regarding arbitrary detention to the following institutions: The United Nations Working Group on Arbitrary Detention, United Nations Human Rights Committee, European Court of Human Rights, African Commission of Human and People's Rights, in the event of disregard from authorities.

International Organisations

The UN Special Rapporteur on Torture Manfred Nowak noted:

The very fact that national or international experts have the power to inspect every place of detention at any time without prior announcement, have access to prison registers and other documents, are entitled to speak with every detainee in private and to carry out medical investigations of torture victims has a strong deterrent effect. At the same time, such visits create the opportunity for independent experts to examine, at first hand, the treatment of prisoners and detainees and the general conditions of detention. Many problems stem from inadequate systems which can easily be improved through regular monitoring. By carrying out regular visits to places of detention, the visiting experts usually establish a constructive dialogue with the authorities concerned in order to help them resolve problems observed.

A number of organizations already engage in such monitoring, including international bodies such as the International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC), the UN Special Rapporteur on Torture, and regional bodies like the Committee for the Prevention of Torture. On a national level, many states have established their own mechanisms, such as human rights commissions, ombudspersons offices, and statutory visiting bodies. Many civil society organizations have come up with various initiatives to supplement such monitoring.

None of these bodies, acting alone, can prevent torture and other ill-treatment. They operate with different mandates and engage with the criminal justice system at different levels and in distinct ways. International bodies lend more independence, have a higher profile and an external perspective, but their engagement is often infrequent. Their work can be of great value only if it is complemented by national mechanisms that ensure contextual analysis and a regular in-country presence. National mechanisms often need the clout and authority of international and/or regional mechanisms to ensure compliance at the national level. Effective national mechanisms can also strengthen feedback and communication between international and regional bodies and national authorities. Civil society organizations add another dimension, as they may have an easier time earning the trust of detainees who have been abused by the authorities, and are often more flexible in their programming and in responding to changing needs.

Also, International Treaty Protocols are key in the strengthening the effect of the treaty as a whole.

One of the most important recent developments in the field of torture prevention is the creation of Optional Protocol to the Convention Against Torture (OPCAT). Sierra Leone is signatory to CAT. This international treaty focuses specifically on the *prevention* of torture and other ill-treatment through the establishment of an international Subcommittee on Prevention of Torture (SPT) and obliges States Parties to “set up, designate or maintain at domestic level one or several visiting bodies,” known as National Preventive Mechanisms (NPMs). These bodies engage with the wider criminal justice system by making recommendations to authorities and engaging with the legislative frameworks. The obligation of the States Parties to establish NPMs is a major step in advancing the torture prevention agenda at national levels.